

Exposure	Outcome	SNP	Beta	SE	P
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs77023203	0.8319953	1.950514	0.6697058
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs2074312	2.0666459	2.3608919	0.3813745
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs116842927	3.1035294	6.7995643	0.6480803
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs7110898	3.6756681	10.029872	0.7140128
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4937311	-8.381587	7.1657619	0.2421332
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs5219	-0.068127	1.1258129	0.9517467
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4148631	-4.832748	6.4557762	0.4541026
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs10766393	3.2183727	2.3133885	0.1641665
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs5210	1.1500862	2.0333916	0.5716658
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs10766395	0.9898321	2.0679023	0.6321771
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs189603359	-7.666401	6.868035	0.2643178
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs10766392	3.253125	2.2938047	0.1561259
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs7110037	0.4417947	2.6205632	0.8661209
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs77902362	-0.224708	5.5562662	0.9677405
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs35271178	0.7576093	1.2641039	0.548956
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs147673442	-6.154715	4.5040155	0.1717836
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs2355016	0.1027461	2.7646167	0.9703537
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs2285676	1.1510195	2.0137829	0.5676128
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs739688	-5.007425	4.9731796	0.3139895
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs79506407	-7.028637	7.7137956	0.3622018
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs7112030	1.1320174	2.0526998	0.5813065
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs117973841	3.5345364	6.0883775	0.5615517
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs12816749	-4.053746	5.5626568	0.4661591
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs74732083	1.4616009	4.9105157	0.7659725
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs10841887	2.8027118	2.7762382	0.3127178
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs59406438	-1.008829	4.3140381	0.8151031
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	0.6854221	0.3727012	0.0659055
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	0.6854221	0.5006617	0.1709891
SU	Acute myeloid leukemia	All - MR Egger	1.8744098	1.3169276	0.1675139
AGI	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs72681706	3.2743794	6.1377986	0.5937029

AGI	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs72692396	4.9758683	5.4643114	0.3624998
AGI	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs174587	1.5338659	5.424	0.777336
AGI	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs112968754	-2.725598	6.0982114	0.6549109
AGI	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs8037100	-2.747056	7.6729744	0.7203305
AGI	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs1659215	-3.266589	8.0803243	0.6860181
AGI	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs73402785	-2.980249	6.2102954	0.6313067
AGI	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs34359922	-1.898475	5.9761441	0.7507311
AGI	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs111917515	-2.361155	5.5526937	0.6706712
AGI	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs113126535	-2.772204	6.00096	0.6441099
AGI	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs112898001	-4.079163	6.007012	0.4970954
AGI	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4924660	-2.100017	6.8905172	0.760542
AGI	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	-0.966549	0.8761379	0.2699434
AGI	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.966549	1.7785734	0.5868264
AGI	Acute myeloid leukemia	All - MR Egger	4.7634412	6.5830155	0.4858958
DPP-4i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4233648	10.621935	6.7107903	0.1134638
DPP-4i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs2080714	4.9227597	5.4756753	0.3686402
DPP-4i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs75850673	-0.197901	7.7514286	0.9796315
DPP-4i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs188581353	-0.688767	6.127184	0.910497
DPP-4i	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	3.8285836	2.5167252	0.1281956
DPP-4i	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	3.8285836	3.1808274	0.2287272
DPP-4i	Acute myeloid leukemia	All - MR Egger	-3.332798	7.3226825	0.6936462
Biguanides	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs150243609	6.0333	5.4194714	0.2655953
Biguanides	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs17485664	-2.141045	6.1554647	0.7279692
Biguanides	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	2.4638011	4.054256	0.5433816
Biguanides	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	2.4638011	4.0675978	0.5447047
GLP1RA	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs10305525	-6.733418	8.7750633	0.4428821
GLP1RA	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs228817	7.5898837	6.5047984	0.2432859
GLP1RA	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs12215108	-6.026425	6.1517617	0.3272708
GLP1RA	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs28360624	-2.262138	6.505509	0.7280456
GLP1RA	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs11963172	-1.240178	5.1558389	0.8099128
GLP1RA	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs880347	3.4025502	3.901823	0.3831859

GLP1RA	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs9462535	-3.339542	5.3624387	0.5334386
GLP1RA	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs142878626	9.496129	6.7699309	0.1607087
GLP1RA	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	0.5967449	1.8825202	0.7512492
GLP1RA	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	0.5967449	2.013859	0.7669864
GLP1RA	Acute myeloid leukemia	All - MR Egger	7.9120622	8.5929549	0.3926908
Insulin	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4031066	4.731089	5.7810685	0.4131424
TZD	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4684833	0.7404605	4.2305	0.8610568
TZD	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs2881654	-1.862018	1.3782525	0.1766957
TZD	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs1373641	-4.688468	3.8402568	0.2221338
TZD	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs2120825	-1.423768	1.4818335	0.3366451
TZD	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs111327339	-0.082591	4.6083535	0.985701
TZD	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4135247	-4.816702	2.1898391	0.0278375
TZD	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs1699348	11.28256	6.533488	0.0841889
TZD	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs310752	-0.251093	6.2416769	0.967911
TZD	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs76763697	0.186554	6.6437054	0.9775985
TZD	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs2920503	-4.667256	5.2112442	0.3704597
TZD	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	-1.920956	0.7515503	0.0105886
TZD	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.920956	0.8248652	0.019869
TZD	Acute myeloid leukemia	All - MR Egger	-2.455176	1.3139161	0.0986199
Amylin analog	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4663804	-4.758529	8.3866373	0.5704464
Amylin analog	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs11869741	-0.275507	5.4836212	0.9599297
Amylin analog	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs12603201	-3.177802	3.2877976	0.3337719
Amylin analog	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs11654396	-19.84044	6.8487647	0.0037683
Amylin analog	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs12941945	-8.282402	4.7693886	0.0824622
Amylin analog	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs1078523	-0.36613	5.028475	0.9419562
Amylin analog	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs9905939	-0.672091	5.2531623	0.8981963
Amylin analog	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs59795094	-0.558031	6.2222692	0.9285393
Amylin analog	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs9892728	-0.641895	5.2987961	0.9035804
Amylin analog	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs73111954	-0.56334	4.0607447	0.8896648
Amylin analog	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs11772021	-2.527557	2.289441	0.2695905
Amylin analog	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4724382	3.1492072	7.3611081	0.6687844

Amylin analog	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs75390434	8.7863248	8.6452137	0.3094759
Amylin analog	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	-2.516475	1.2214061	0.0393689
Amylin analog	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.516475	1.2641452	0.046519
Amylin analog	Acute myeloid leukemia	All - MR Egger	-3.02703	2.8639891	0.313204
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4561482	-9.608034	6.9813675	0.1687475
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs8057326	-6.668581	7.6419238	0.3828641
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs34497199	-3.198488	6.2644419	0.6096463
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs142133957	-0.400343	5.1376672	0.9378893
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs11150624	-0.827418	6.6874672	0.9015317
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs11865835	-4.967765	7.7522522	0.5216424
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs8057029	-4.722164	7.3024828	0.5178573
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs12448775	-1.105391	6.5710256	0.8664086
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs8054784	-1.990892	7.4163604	0.7883561
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	-3.295854	1.0284307	0.0013518
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.295854	2.2355028	0.1403946
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	All - MR Egger	0.8247431	5.4547522	0.8840852
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4561482	-9.608034	6.9813675	0.1687475
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs8057326	-6.668581	7.6419238	0.3828641
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs34497199	-3.198488	6.2644419	0.6096463
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs142133957	-0.400343	5.1376672	0.9378893
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs11150624	-0.827418	6.6874672	0.9015317
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs11865835	-4.967765	7.7522522	0.5216424
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs8057029	-4.722164	7.3024828	0.5178573
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs12448775	-1.105391	6.5710256	0.8664086
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs8054784	-1.990892	7.4163604	0.7883561
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	-3.295854	1.0284307	0.0013518
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.295854	2.2355028	0.1403946
SGLT2i	Acute myeloid leukemia	All - MR Egger	0.8247431	5.4547522	0.8840852
SU	Anal cancer	rs77023203	-3.80528	3.329229	0.2530421
SU	Anal cancer	rs2074312	-4.183432	4.0269459	0.2988699
SU	Anal cancer	rs116842927	3.1760349	11.74366	0.7868166

SU	Anal cancer	rs7110898	-15.77477	17.26417	0.3608595
SU	Anal cancer	rs4937311	12.891429	12.246032	0.2924773
SU	Anal cancer	rs5219	-3.574509	1.9204441	0.0627028
SU	Anal cancer	rs4148631	10.602797	11.043916	0.3370262
SU	Anal cancer	rs10766393	-5.27727	3.9445932	0.1809456
SU	Anal cancer	rs5210	-3.335123	3.472266	0.3368019
SU	Anal cancer	rs10766395	-4.328672	3.5314787	0.2202969
SU	Anal cancer	rs189603359	23.160311	11.78107	0.0493111
SU	Anal cancer	rs10766392	-5.200599	3.911224	0.1836302
SU	Anal cancer	rs7110037	1.6852974	4.4847895	0.7070799
SU	Anal cancer	rs77902362	9.3627597	9.4390584	0.3212382
SU	Anal cancer	rs35271178	-2.161984	2.157969	0.3164108
SU	Anal cancer	rs147673442	-11.65886	7.7239378	0.1311851
SU	Anal cancer	rs2355016	0.7971028	4.73025	0.8661807
SU	Anal cancer	rs2285676	-3.294756	3.438878	0.3380172
SU	Anal cancer	rs739688	13.508024	8.4933533	0.1117395
SU	Anal cancer	rs79506407	10.611338	13.128759	0.4189459
SU	Anal cancer	rs7112030	-3.614516	3.5045906	0.3023691
SU	Anal cancer	rs117973841	-15.21609	10.481192	0.1465705
SU	Anal cancer	rs12816749	1.6453787	9.4777515	0.8621764
SU	Anal cancer	rs74732083	-4.594507	8.3267937	0.5811033
SU	Anal cancer	rs10841887	7.7953824	4.7486765	0.1006749
SU	Anal cancer	rs59406438	11.299408	7.3698943	0.1252304
SU	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.159371	0.9260222	0.0197071
SU	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.159371	0.8547744	0.0115289
SU	Anal cancer	All - MR Egger	-6.500439	2.2939644	0.0091798
AGI	Anal cancer	rs72681706	13.102506	10.420304	0.2086083
AGI	Anal cancer	rs72692396	5.4883234	9.2930339	0.5547987
AGI	Anal cancer	rs174587	-1.864358	9.2427933	0.840144
AGI	Anal cancer	rs112968754	-1.33272	10.418049	0.898209
AGI	Anal cancer	rs8037100	5.3208718	13.117538	0.6850142

AGI	Anal cancer	rs1659215	4.7009135	13.818919	0.7337213
AGI	Anal cancer	rs73402785	-3.270886	10.610084	0.7578686
AGI	Anal cancer	rs34359922	-2.174114	10.220466	0.8315441
AGI	Anal cancer	rs111917515	1.8922362	9.491476	0.8419799
AGI	Anal cancer	rs113126535	4.02016	10.2572	0.6951059
AGI	Anal cancer	rs112898001	-0.911936	10.258884	0.9291675
AGI	Anal cancer	rs4924660	1.6733966	11.788218	0.8871155
AGI	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.0124351	1.354311	0.137293
AGI	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.0124351	3.0356669	0.5073753
AGI	Anal cancer	All - MR Egger	10.748854	11.205778	0.3600634
DPP-4i	Anal cancer	rs4233648	-13.59016	11.465403	0.2358913
DPP-4i	Anal cancer	rs2080714	-17.31981	9.3256494	0.0632795
DPP-4i	Anal cancer	rs75850673	2.0287453	13.218385	0.8780205
DPP-4i	Anal cancer	rs188581353	-4.340864	10.276383	0.6727246
DPP-4i	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-9.680623	4.2310536	0.0221379
DPP-4i	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-9.680623	5.3996305	0.073
DPP-4i	Anal cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.135865	12.294725	0.8780764
Biguanides	Anal cancer	rs150243609	-14.362	9.3013571	0.12257
Biguanides	Anal cancer	rs17485664	-10.20825	10.498364	0.3308685
Biguanides	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-12.53533	2.0617474	1.20E-09
Biguanides	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-12.53533	6.9619624	0.0717746
GLP1RA	Anal cancer	rs10305525	5.7638418	15.019557	0.7011595
GLP1RA	Anal cancer	rs228817	9.5383721	11.110233	0.3906046
GLP1RA	Anal cancer	rs12215108	-5.605907	10.453057	0.5917557
GLP1RA	Anal cancer	rs28360624	0.1689335	11.087784	0.9878439
GLP1RA	Anal cancer	rs11963172	1.1657944	8.8001667	0.8946093
GLP1RA	Anal cancer	rs880347	1.3951005	6.66689	0.8342468
GLP1RA	Anal cancer	rs9462535	-4.377226	9.1552258	0.6325703
GLP1RA	Anal cancer	rs142878626	-5.58765	11.575622	0.6293028
GLP1RA	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.0639358	1.6914374	0.9698474
GLP1RA	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0639358	3.4375629	0.9851609

GLP1RA	Anal cancer	All - MR Egger	-10.21734	14.685263	0.5126164
Insulin	Anal cancer	rs4031066	-7.777466	9.8531507	0.4299145
TZD	Anal cancer	rs4684833	0.4451623	7.2348246	0.9509367
TZD	Anal cancer	rs2881654	-3.649346	2.3393348	0.1187615
TZD	Anal cancer	rs1373641	5.2045946	6.5643694	0.4278622
TZD	Anal cancer	rs2120825	-1.321552	2.5105062	0.5986043
TZD	Anal cancer	rs111327339	4.8406798	7.7894411	0.5343094
TZD	Anal cancer	rs4135247	3.1109651	3.736622	0.4050925
TZD	Anal cancer	rs1699348	17.82448	11.15704	0.1101322
TZD	Anal cancer	rs310752	0.6199931	10.657538	0.9536099
TZD	Anal cancer	rs76763697	6.8403125	11.377232	0.547688
TZD	Anal cancer	rs2920503	1.1399535	8.9100581	0.8981964
TZD	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.449543	1.2583336	0.7209025
TZD	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.449543	1.4016975	0.7484275
TZD	Anal cancer	All - MR Egger	-3.850978	2.2317078	0.1227034
Amylin analog	Anal cancer	rs4663804	0.8127578	14.321667	0.9547442
Amylin analog	Anal cancer	rs11869741	3.5653482	9.3890529	0.7041424
Amylin analog	Anal cancer	rs12603201	-0.167761	5.6098381	0.976143
Amylin analog	Anal cancer	rs11654396	9.8545588	11.692206	0.3993227
Amylin analog	Anal cancer	rs12941945	-1.78076	8.1827948	0.8277233
Amylin analog	Anal cancer	rs1078523	-0.538461	8.5895	0.9500147
Amylin analog	Anal cancer	rs9905939	-2.107117	8.9774675	0.8144325
Amylin analog	Anal cancer	rs59795094	-2.060415	10.627538	0.8462737
Amylin analog	Anal cancer	rs9892728	0.4154914	9.0508553	0.9633849
Amylin analog	Anal cancer	rs73111954	-7.838383	6.9301702	0.2580332
Amylin analog	Anal cancer	rs11772021	-1.968878	3.8832919	0.612146
Amylin analog	Anal cancer	rs4724382	11.773874	12.562973	0.3486616
Amylin analog	Anal cancer	rs75390434	11.085897	14.711624	0.4511214
Amylin analog	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.603628	1.2298401	0.6235549
Amylin analog	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.603628	2.1548586	0.7793822
Amylin analog	Anal cancer	All - MR Egger	-4.574931	4.8353775	0.364399

SGLT2i	Anal cancer	rs4561482	-25.81906	11.937009	0.0305456
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	rs8057326	-18.76505	13.050095	0.1504556
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	rs34497199	-6.681186	10.691938	0.5320493
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	rs142133957	15.643458	8.6823654	0.0715846
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	rs11150624	-22.9377	11.425902	0.0446945
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	rs11865835	-9.102	13.220348	0.4911479
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	rs8057029	-30.81198	12.507672	0.0137608
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	rs12448775	-17.67795	11.264904	0.1165794
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	rs8054784	-28.13486	12.675586	0.0264452
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-12.81547	5.5662843	0.0213161
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-12.81547	3.8130014	0.0007766
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	All - MR Egger	14.152463	9.254576	0.1700535
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	rs4561482	-25.81906	11.937009	0.0305456
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	rs8057326	-18.76505	13.050095	0.1504556
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	rs34497199	-6.681186	10.691938	0.5320493
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	rs142133957	15.643458	8.6823654	0.0715846
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	rs11150624	-22.9377	11.425902	0.0446945
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	rs11865835	-9.102	13.220348	0.4911479
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	rs8057029	-30.81198	12.507672	0.0137608
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	rs12448775	-17.67795	11.264904	0.1165794
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	rs8054784	-28.13486	12.675586	0.0264452
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-12.81547	5.5662843	0.0213161
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-12.81547	3.8130014	0.0007766
SGLT2i	Anal cancer	All - MR Egger	14.152463	9.254576	0.1700535
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs77023203	-0.421117	0.5306939	0.4274743
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs2074312	-0.8399	0.6422676	0.1909715
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs116842927	4.7354684	1.8664662	0.0111765
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs7110898	5.8910213	2.7275277	0.0307851
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4937311	6.0066111	1.9521746	0.0020918
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs5219	-0.243852	0.3066783	0.4265326
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4148631	-0.369443	1.759	0.833644

SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs10766393	-0.640743	0.6291365	0.3084651
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs5210	-0.44002	0.55333	0.4264849
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs10766395	-0.560767	0.5627268	0.3189989
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs189603359	1.3504689	1.8801109	0.4725772
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs10766392	-0.609214	0.6238464	0.3287949
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs7110037	-0.267611	0.7142237	0.7078931
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs77902362	1.2456169	1.5132565	0.4104303
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs35271178	-0.395947	0.3442946	0.2501337
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs147673442	0.8122332	1.2223031	0.5063637
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs2355016	-0.420092	0.7533583	0.5771003
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs2285676	-0.427678	0.5479951	0.4351311
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs739688	-0.172852	1.3546347	0.8984651
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs79506407	-1.106659	2.109326	0.599826
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs7112030	-0.482846	0.5584814	0.3872749
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs117973841	1.2611192	1.6607152	0.4476234
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs12816749	1.5826746	1.5122544	0.2952996
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs74732083	-0.435948	1.3371839	0.7444094
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs10841887	0.6368647	0.7558147	0.3994409
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	rs59406438	0.2999154	1.17926	0.7992444
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.243846	0.1532839	0.1116519
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.243846	0.1363148	0.0736401
SU	Basal cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.954278	0.3806245	0.0193442
AGI	Basal cell carcinoma	rs72681706	1.1997611	1.6767002	0.4742699
AGI	Basal cell carcinoma	rs72692396	1.5589002	1.4948303	0.2970127
AGI	Basal cell carcinoma	rs174587	4.8174972	1.4793799	0.0011282
AGI	Basal cell carcinoma	rs112968754	-1.630862	1.6576911	0.3252063
AGI	Basal cell carcinoma	rs8037100	-1.650477	2.0867795	0.4289903
AGI	Basal cell carcinoma	rs1659215	-1.713541	2.1974486	0.4355166
AGI	Basal cell carcinoma	rs73402785	-1.333852	1.68927	0.4297598
AGI	Basal cell carcinoma	rs34359922	-1.51939	1.6263517	0.3501842
AGI	Basal cell carcinoma	rs111917515	-1.263738	1.5102399	0.4027164

AGI	Basal cell carcinoma	rs113126535	-1.245712	1.631984	0.4452777
AGI	Basal cell carcinoma	rs112898001	-1.707729	1.6338367	0.2959184
AGI	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4924660	2.7342069	1.875908	0.144968
AGI	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.0168585	0.6596535	0.979611
AGI	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0168585	0.4843895	0.9722363
AGI	Basal cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-1.244644	2.5338695	0.6338843
DPP-4i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4233648	3.9579516	1.8287097	0.0304382
DPP-4i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs2080714	-3.335844	1.4880195	0.0249742
DPP-4i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs75850673	0.4015764	2.1092733	0.8490066
DPP-4i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs188581353	-0.734081	1.6553567	0.6574344
DPP-4i	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.373529	1.5576251	0.81048
DPP-4i	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.373529	0.8637521	0.6654147
DPP-4i	Basal cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-1.953848	4.1914545	0.6869497
Biguanides	Basal cell carcinoma	rs150243609	1.1241414	1.4854429	0.4491865
Biguanides	Basal cell carcinoma	rs17485664	-2.518033	1.6762454	0.1330489
Biguanides	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.477945	1.8078711	0.7914958
Biguanides	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.477945	1.111732	0.6672612
GLP1RA	Basal cell carcinoma	rs10305525	1.0929177	2.3903861	0.6475173
GLP1RA	Basal cell carcinoma	rs228817	2.7728682	1.7716899	0.11756
GLP1RA	Basal cell carcinoma	rs12215108	-0.14736	1.6704301	0.9297046
GLP1RA	Basal cell carcinoma	rs28360624	0.2605886	1.7693892	0.8829142
GLP1RA	Basal cell carcinoma	rs11963172	-0.002734	1.4037944	0.9984462
GLP1RA	Basal cell carcinoma	rs880347	-1.057981	1.0624689	0.3193591
GLP1RA	Basal cell carcinoma	rs9462535	0.946471	1.4607419	0.5170247
GLP1RA	Basal cell carcinoma	rs142878626	-2.110571	1.8402995	0.2514383
GLP1RA	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.003951	0.4820643	0.9934606
GLP1RA	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.003951	0.5481094	0.9942485
GLP1RA	Basal cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-5.02387	2.337565	0.0751904
Insulin	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4031066	-1.591904	1.574589	0.3120181
TZD	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4684833	0.5024561	1.1545702	0.6634253
TZD	Basal cell carcinoma	rs2881654	-0.242417	0.3753191	0.5183466

TZD	Basal cell carcinoma	rs1373641	-1.252491	1.0459279	0.2311146
TZD	Basal cell carcinoma	rs2120825	-0.5222	0.4035917	0.195706
TZD	Basal cell carcinoma	rs111327339	1.2451193	1.2509079	0.3195551
TZD	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4135247	-0.586791	0.5962708	0.3250657
TZD	Basal cell carcinoma	rs1699348	-1.335408	1.779592	0.4530131
TZD	Basal cell carcinoma	rs310752	-1.139515	1.7004154	0.5027689
TZD	Basal cell carcinoma	rs76763697	-0.238887	1.8046027	0.8946867
TZD	Basal cell carcinoma	rs2920503	-2.885244	1.421843	0.042435
TZD	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.447372	0.1960464	0.022491
TZD	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.447372	0.2246335	0.0464187
TZD	Basal cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.092403	0.3578363	0.8027517
Amylin analog	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4663804	-3.121961	2.2833235	0.1715351
Amylin analog	Basal cell carcinoma	rs11869741	-0.669546	1.4950251	0.6542619
Amylin analog	Basal cell carcinoma	rs12603201	-1.212126	0.8950364	0.1756486
Amylin analog	Basal cell carcinoma	rs11654396	0.9764412	1.8625441	0.6001038
Amylin analog	Basal cell carcinoma	rs12941945	-2.396908	1.2999127	0.0651978
Amylin analog	Basal cell carcinoma	rs1078523	-1.097656	1.3692563	0.4227588
Amylin analog	Basal cell carcinoma	rs9905939	-0.679909	1.4306234	0.6346061
Amylin analog	Basal cell carcinoma	rs59795094	-1.332654	1.6941385	0.4315007
Amylin analog	Basal cell carcinoma	rs9892728	-0.878737	1.4429539	0.5425346
Amylin analog	Basal cell carcinoma	rs73111954	-2.171851	1.1062383	0.0496141
Amylin analog	Basal cell carcinoma	rs11772021	0.9472816	0.6237226	0.1288243
Amylin analog	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4724382	-1.631541	2.0055045	0.4159136
Amylin analog	Basal cell carcinoma	rs75390434	-1.735009	2.3518034	0.4606753
Amylin analog	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.641539	0.3629225	0.0771105
Amylin analog	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.641539	0.3443097	0.0624254
Amylin analog	Basal cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.8298777	0.7744626	0.3068681
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4561482	0.5386692	1.901547	0.7769626
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs8057326	-0.513689	2.0815333	0.8050756
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs34497199	-0.212388	1.705876	0.9009166
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs142133957	1.3982496	1.3973279	0.3169914

SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs11150624	0.5384082	1.8210738	0.7674941
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs11865835	-3.583609	2.1078348	0.0891051
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs8057029	-0.24995	1.9887586	0.8999841
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs12448775	-0.027657	1.7931635	0.9876941
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs8054784	0.0341472	2.0199279	0.9865123
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.012637	0.4385237	0.9770104
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.012637	0.6087277	0.9834374
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	1.4295213	1.4848652	0.3677538
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4561482	0.5386692	1.901547	0.7769626
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs8057326	-0.513689	2.0815333	0.8050756
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs34497199	-0.212388	1.705876	0.9009166
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs142133957	1.3982496	1.3973279	0.3169914
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs11150624	0.5384082	1.8210738	0.7674941
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs11865835	-3.583609	2.1078348	0.0891051
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs8057029	-0.24995	1.9887586	0.8999841
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs12448775	-0.027657	1.7931635	0.9876941
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	rs8054784	0.0341472	2.0199279	0.9865123
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.012637	0.4385237	0.9770104
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.012637	0.6087277	0.9834374
SGLT2i	Basal cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	1.4295213	1.4848652	0.3677538
SU	Bladder cancer	rs77023203	0.0019383	0.0024549	0.4297796
SU	Bladder cancer	rs5219	0.0021678	0.0014224	0.1275076
SU	Bladder cancer	rs5210	0.0017028	0.0025665	0.5070096
SU	Bladder cancer	rs10766395	0.0011537	0.0026085	0.6582717
SU	Bladder cancer	rs35271178	0.0017768	0.0015954	0.2654031
SU	Bladder cancer	rs2285676	0.0016315	0.0025416	0.5209316
SU	Bladder cancer	rs739688	-0.001539	0.006238	0.8051224
SU	Bladder cancer	rs7112030	0.0017738	0.0025887	0.4932087
SU	Bladder cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.0017822	0.0001897	5.71E-21
SU	Bladder cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0017822	0.0007712	0.0208282
SU	Bladder cancer	All - MR Egger	0.0029801	0.0022663	0.2365511

DPP-4i	Bladder cancer	rs4233648	-0.002681	0.0083721	0.7487674
DPP-4i	Bladder cancer	rs2080714	-0.005251	0.0068979	0.4465396
DPP-4i	Bladder cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.004212	0.001261	0.0008375
DPP-4i	Bladder cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.004212	0.0053237	0.4288677
GLP1RA	Bladder cancer	rs228817	-0.018549	0.0082007	0.0237078
GLP1RA	Bladder cancer	rs880347	-0.01261	0.0049141	0.0102873
GLP1RA	Bladder cancer	rs9462535	-0.004853	0.0067461	0.4719502
GLP1RA	Bladder cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.01156	0.0033539	0.0005673
GLP1RA	Bladder cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.01156	0.0035748	0.0012216
GLP1RA	Bladder cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.008205	0.0236424	0.7873413
Insulin	Bladder cancer	rs4031066	-0.001933	0.0072874	0.7908628
TZD	Bladder cancer	rs1373641	0.002667	0.004825	0.5804414
TZD	Bladder cancer	rs4135247	-4.68E-04	0.0027505	0.8649341
TZD	Bladder cancer	rs1699348	-8.48E-04	0.0082137	0.9177907
TZD	Bladder cancer	rs310752	-0.002275	0.007862	0.7723473
TZD	Bladder cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.63E-05	0.0008327	0.9844279
TZD	Bladder cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.63E-05	0.0022025	0.9941127
TZD	Bladder cancer	All - MR Egger	2.72E-04	0.0051077	0.9623562
Amylin analog	Bladder cancer	rs4663804	0.0037439	0.0103552	0.7176933
Amylin analog	Bladder cancer	rs12603201	-1.21E-04	0.0041467	0.9767942
Amylin analog	Bladder cancer	rs1078523	0.0078254	0.0063491	0.2177578
Amylin analog	Bladder cancer	rs9905939	0.0058054	0.0066062	0.3795184
Amylin analog	Bladder cancer	rs59795094	0.0089996	0.0078312	0.2504754
Amylin analog	Bladder cancer	rs9892728	0.0079268	0.0066889	0.2359869
Amylin analog	Bladder cancer	rs4724382	-0.002893	0.0092853	0.755382
Amylin analog	Bladder cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.0039008	0.0016575	0.0186036
Amylin analog	Bladder cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0039008	0.0024584	0.1125818
Amylin analog	Bladder cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.001383	0.0087854	0.8810413
SGLT2i	Bladder cancer	rs4561482	-0.021517	0.0088052	0.0145396
SGLT2i	Bladder cancer	rs8057326	-0.017814	0.009654	0.0650061
SGLT2i	Bladder cancer	rs34497199	-0.007992	0.0078932	0.3112933

SGLT2i	Bladder cancer	rs11150624	-0.020955	0.008447	0.0131086
SGLT2i	Bladder cancer	rs8057029	-0.016109	0.0091915	0.0796771
SGLT2i	Bladder cancer	rs8054784	-0.010761	0.0093405	0.2492902
SGLT2i	Bladder cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.015646	0.0023392	2.25E-11
SGLT2i	Bladder cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.015646	0.0036039	1.42E-05
SGLT2i	Bladder cancer	All - MR Egger	0.0082425	0.0545275	0.8871647
SGLT2i	Bladder cancer	rs4561482	-0.021517	0.0088052	0.0145396
SGLT2i	Bladder cancer	rs8057326	-0.017814	0.009654	0.0650061
SGLT2i	Bladder cancer	rs34497199	-0.007992	0.0078932	0.3112933
SGLT2i	Bladder cancer	rs11150624	-0.020955	0.008447	0.0131086
SGLT2i	Bladder cancer	rs8057029	-0.016109	0.0091915	0.0796771
SGLT2i	Bladder cancer	rs8054784	-0.010761	0.0093405	0.2492902
SGLT2i	Bladder cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.015646	0.0023392	2.25E-11
SGLT2i	Bladder cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.015646	0.0036039	1.42E-05
SGLT2i	Bladder cancer	All - MR Egger	0.0082425	0.0545275	0.8871647
SU	Breast cancer	rs77023203	0.4906542	0.1518692	0.0012346
SU	Breast cancer	rs2074312	0.5378378	0.1837838	0.0034283
SU	Breast cancer	rs116842927	0.2004357	0.4989107	0.6878704
SU	Breast cancer	rs7110898	-0.46383	0.9106383	0.6105099
SU	Breast cancer	rs4937311	0.452381	0.547619	0.4087548
SU	Breast cancer	rs5219	0.1655451	0.0861373	0.0546215
SU	Breast cancer	rs4148631	-0.377622	0.5034965	0.4532547
SU	Breast cancer	rs10766393	0.4776903	0.183727	0.0093224
SU	Breast cancer	rs5210	0.4605911	0.1600985	0.0040157
SU	Breast cancer	rs10766395	0.5012531	0.1629073	0.0020915
SU	Breast cancer	rs189603359	0.9980545	0.5700389	0.0799712
SU	Breast cancer	rs10766392	0.4739583	0.1822917	0.0093224
SU	Breast cancer	rs7110037	-0.221053	0.2078947	0.2876499
SU	Breast cancer	rs77902362	0.1038961	0.487013	0.831067
SU	Breast cancer	rs35271178	0.1922481	0.0976744	0.0490388
SU	Breast cancer	rs147673442	-0.11399	0.3445596	0.7407751

SU	Breast cancer	rs2355016	-0.211111	0.2194444	0.3360369
SU	Breast cancer	rs2285676	0.4512195	0.1585366	0.0044251
SU	Breast cancer	rs739688	-0.592814	0.3832335	0.1218934
SU	Breast cancer	rs79506407	-0.712895	0.6155718	0.2468221
SU	Breast cancer	rs7112030	0.4764268	0.1612903	0.0031384
SU	Breast cancer	rs117973841	0.2516556	0.5331126	0.6368913
SU	Breast cancer	rs12816749	-0.08284	0.4556213	0.8557254
SU	Breast cancer	rs74732083	-0.266816	0.4035874	0.5085411
SU	Breast cancer	rs10841887	-0.020588	0.2176471	0.9246368
SU	Breast cancer	rs59406438	-0.137421	0.3509514	0.6953787
SU	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.2542533	0.0519439	9.84E-07
SU	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.2542533	0.0391488	8.33E-11
SU	Breast cancer	All - MR Egger	0.335253	0.1370147	0.022112
AGI	Breast cancer	rs72681706	-0.173302	0.4941452	0.7258052
AGI	Breast cancer	rs72692396	-0.043912	0.497006	0.9295958
AGI	Breast cancer	rs174587	0.396648	0.4469274	0.3748098
AGI	Breast cancer	rs112968754	0.2439024	0.4837398	0.6141197
AGI	Breast cancer	rs8037100	0.2102564	0.6	0.726018
AGI	Breast cancer	rs1659215	0.1027027	0.6378378	0.8720801
AGI	Breast cancer	rs73402785	0.2025316	0.4894515	0.6790256
AGI	Breast cancer	rs34359922	0.3855932	0.4661017	0.4080825
AGI	Breast cancer	rs111917515	0.2398524	0.4428044	0.5880482
AGI	Breast cancer	rs113126535	0.224	0.48	0.6407384
AGI	Breast cancer	rs112898001	0.1593625	0.4820717	0.7409629
AGI	Breast cancer	rs4924660	-0.235632	0.5344828	0.6593142
AGI	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.1572245	0.057792	0.0065178
AGI	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.1572245	0.1433252	0.2726515
AGI	Breast cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.089089	0.5551502	0.8757007
DPP-4i	Breast cancer	rs4233648	-0.427419	0.5725806	0.4553782
DPP-4i	Breast cancer	rs2080714	0.1038961	0.474026	0.8265113
DPP-4i	Breast cancer	rs75850673	0.5652174	0.6273292	0.3675936

DPP-4i	Breast cancer	rs188581353	0.3241552	0.6433041	0.6143379
DPP-4i	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.1106267	0.2015684	0.5831225
DPP-4i	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.1106267	0.2833194	0.6961918
DPP-4i	Breast cancer	All - MR Egger	0.5879409	0.7577324	0.5189839
Biguanides	Breast cancer	rs150243609	0.14	0.4971429	0.7782432
Biguanides	Breast cancer	rs17485664	0.6356877	0.4869888	0.1917759
Biguanides	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.3929577	0.2477911	0.112775
Biguanides	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.3929577	0.3478875	0.2586643
GLP1RA	Breast cancer	rs10305525	-0.696203	0.7025316	0.32169
GLP1RA	Breast cancer	rs228817	0.5658915	0.5271318	0.2830336
GLP1RA	Breast cancer	rs12215108	0.134715	0.4766839	0.7774768
GLP1RA	Breast cancer	rs28360624	-0.245509	0.497006	0.6213232
GLP1RA	Breast cancer	rs11963172	-0.011111	0.4055556	0.9781429
GLP1RA	Breast cancer	rs880347	0.2440191	0.3253589	0.4532547
GLP1RA	Breast cancer	rs9462535	0.0580645	0.4129032	0.8881662
GLP1RA	Breast cancer	rs142878626	0.2557604	0.5806452	0.6595923
GLP1RA	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.0926742	0.1039213	0.3725147
GLP1RA	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0926742	0.1613066	0.5656147
GLP1RA	Breast cancer	All - MR Egger	0.1833595	0.7197113	0.8074096
Insulin	Breast cancer	rs4031066	0.1575342	0.4794521	0.7424796
Insulin	Breast cancer	rs144057856	0.8213097	0.4739179	0.0830919
Insulin	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.4932749	0.3318653	0.1371811
Insulin	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.4932749	0.3370501	0.1433289
TZD	Breast cancer	rs4684833	0.4561404	0.3289474	0.1655434
TZD	Breast cancer	rs2881654	-0.173619	0.1059752	0.1013596
TZD	Breast cancer	rs1373641	-0.54955	0.2972973	0.0645322
TZD	Breast cancer	rs2120825	-0.085489	0.1113611	0.4426792
TZD	Breast cancer	rs111327339	0.4879154	0.3746224	0.1927731
TZD	Breast cancer	rs4135247	-0.407507	0.1689008	0.0158349
TZD	Breast cancer	rs1699348	0.96	0.504	0.056811
TZD	Breast cancer	rs310752	-0.984615	0.4923077	0.0455003

TZD	Breast cancer	rs76763697	0.5982143	0.5758929	0.2989165
TZD	Breast cancer	rs2920503	-1.680233	0.4011628	2.81E-05
TZD	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.176541	0.1240766	0.1547822
TZD	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.176541	0.0632829	0.0052754
TZD	Breast cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.075311	0.2041595	0.721786
Amylin analog	Breast cancer	rs4663804	-0.843137	0.6372549	0.1858098
Amylin analog	Breast cancer	rs11869741	0.189415	0.4373259	0.6649269
Amylin analog	Breast cancer	rs12603201	-0.635628	0.2550607	0.0127003
Amylin analog	Breast cancer	rs11654396	-0.139706	0.5220588	0.7890029
Amylin analog	Breast cancer	rs12941945	-0.593886	0.3668122	0.105437
Amylin analog	Breast cancer	rs1078523	-0.15	0.3875	0.6986846
Amylin analog	Breast cancer	rs9905939	0.6233766	0.4025974	0.1215291
Amylin analog	Breast cancer	rs59795094	-0.038462	0.4769231	0.9357241
Amylin analog	Breast cancer	rs9892728	-0.151316	0.4078947	0.7106616
Amylin analog	Breast cancer	rs73111954	-0.178723	0.3234043	0.5805157
Amylin analog	Breast cancer	rs11772021	-0.15942	0.1884058	0.3974669
Amylin analog	Breast cancer	rs4724382	-0.342342	0.5675676	0.5463925
Amylin analog	Breast cancer	rs75390434	0.2735043	0.6923077	0.6927973
Amylin analog	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.206395	0.0947175	0.0293271
Amylin analog	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.206395	0.0998387	0.0387071
Amylin analog	Breast cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.252308	0.2287445	0.2935683
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	rs4561482	-0.42735	0.5726496	0.4555051
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	rs8057326	-0.6	0.6	0.3173105
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	rs34497199	-0.465116	0.496124	0.3485014
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	rs142133957	-0.097879	0.5970636	0.8697828
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	rs11150624	-0.647541	0.5409836	0.2313184
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	rs11865835	-0.565217	0.6608696	0.3924055
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	rs8057029	-0.637931	0.5862069	0.2764912
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	rs12448775	1.25	0.6217949	0.0443985
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	rs8054784	-0.621622	0.5945946	0.2958129
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.33758	0.1922153	0.0790444

SGLT2i	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.33758	0.1934316	0.0809475
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	All - MR Egger	0.8020101	0.5879014	0.2147446
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	rs4561482	-0.42735	0.5726496	0.4555051
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	rs8057326	-0.6	0.6	0.3173105
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	rs34497199	-0.465116	0.496124	0.3485014
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	rs142133957	-0.097879	0.5970636	0.8697828
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	rs11150624	-0.647541	0.5409836	0.2313184
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	rs11865835	-0.565217	0.6608696	0.3924055
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	rs8057029	-0.637931	0.5862069	0.2764912
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	rs12448775	1.25	0.6217949	0.0443985
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	rs8054784	-0.621622	0.5945946	0.2958129
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.33758	0.1922153	0.0790444
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.33758	0.1934316	0.0809475
SGLT2i	Breast cancer	All - MR Egger	0.8020101	0.5879014	0.2147446
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs77023203	-1.53403	0.7508505	0.0410468
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs2074312	-2.272041	0.9083027	0.0123699
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs116842927	-0.33393	2.6401525	0.8993508
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs7110898	-2.513174	3.8761149	0.5167427
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs4937311	-0.654364	2.7619762	0.8127197
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs5219	-0.182197	0.4337699	0.6744633
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs4148631	2.9626783	2.4888042	0.2338883
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs10766393	-1.765619	0.888685	0.0469471
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs5210	-1.72469	0.783197	0.0276572
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs10766395	-1.814175	0.7964436	0.0227358
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs189603359	2.9753113	2.6561673	0.262649
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs10766392	-1.564987	0.8812031	0.0757385
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs7110037	2.0239368	1.0123421	0.04558
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs77902362	0.3115942	2.1213312	0.8832219
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs35271178	-0.312081	0.4872636	0.5218632
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs147673442	0.9089637	1.7457098	0.6025867
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs2355016	2.1239889	1.0665722	0.0464352

SU	Bronchial cancer	rs2285676	-1.679937	0.7756537	0.0303239
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs739688	4.0523174	1.9170719	0.0345319
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs79506407	3.8031873	3.0040633	0.2055079
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs7112030	-1.833305	0.7904293	0.0203745
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs117973841	0.5431854	2.3623907	0.8181459
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs12816749	-0.47982	2.1377101	0.8224031
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs74732083	-0.726047	1.8686525	0.6976161
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs10841887	0.7600618	1.0714676	0.4780979
SU	Bronchial cancer	rs59406438	-1.603569	1.6657949	0.3357258
SU	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.640001	0.2627222	0.0148491
SU	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.640001	0.1928646	0.0009054
SU	Bronchial cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.059279	0.6993841	0.1429366
AGI	Bronchial cancer	rs72681706	-0.811429	2.3642623	0.7314436
AGI	Bronchial cancer	rs72692396	-0.545794	2.10998	0.7958877
AGI	Bronchial cancer	rs174587	0.9080223	2.0822235	0.6627765
AGI	Bronchial cancer	rs112968754	-1.541374	2.344622	0.5109184
AGI	Bronchial cancer	rs8037100	-1.103687	2.9523795	0.708531
AGI	Bronchial cancer	rs1659215	-1.031978	3.1095676	0.7399859
AGI	Bronchial cancer	rs73402785	-1.130156	2.3877004	0.635982
AGI	Bronchial cancer	rs34359922	-1.908881	2.3025932	0.4070966
AGI	Bronchial cancer	rs111917515	-0.91179	2.13569	0.6694305
AGI	Bronchial cancer	rs113126535	-0.411464	2.30764	0.8584834
AGI	Bronchial cancer	rs112898001	-1.598602	2.3088167	0.4886925
AGI	Bronchial cancer	rs4924660	0.0765333	2.6541782	0.9769962
AGI	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.7947	0.2365776	0.0007818
AGI	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.7947	0.6844173	0.2455878
AGI	Bronchial cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.667542	2.5370784	0.5258464
DPP-4i	Bronchial cancer	rs4233648	-2.959379	2.5870645	0.2526594
DPP-4i	Bronchial cancer	rs2080714	-0.568448	2.101513	0.7867797
DPP-4i	Bronchial cancer	rs75850673	2.1044845	2.9843602	0.4807038
DPP-4i	Bronchial cancer	rs188581353	1.1980338	2.2971214	0.6019927

DPP-4i	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.158719	1.0245421	0.876887
DPP-4i	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.158719	1.2147954	0.8960485
DPP-4i	Bronchial cancer	All - MR Egger	2.2139283	2.7497889	0.5052493
Biguanides	Bronchial cancer	rs150243609	0.9723729	2.1063857	0.644346
Biguanides	Bronchial cancer	rs17485664	2.0301561	2.3630595	0.3902733
Biguanides	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.4407172	0.5254145	0.0061055
Biguanides	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.4407172	1.5723852	0.3595294
GLP1RA	Bronchial cancer	rs10305525	-2.349475	3.3847532	0.4875977
GLP1RA	Bronchial cancer	rs228817	-1.414876	2.5047132	0.5721517
GLP1RA	Bronchial cancer	rs12215108	1.8093627	2.355171	0.442338
GLP1RA	Bronchial cancer	rs28360624	-1.761449	2.503018	0.4816009
GLP1RA	Bronchial cancer	rs11963172	-1.722339	1.9849333	0.3855552
GLP1RA	Bronchial cancer	rs880347	-1.318856	1.5025311	0.3800759
GLP1RA	Bronchial cancer	rs9462535	2.4948	2.0673226	0.2275175
GLP1RA	Bronchial cancer	rs142878626	-6.064101	2.5939631	0.0193989
GLP1RA	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.035084	0.8560744	0.2266223
GLP1RA	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.035084	0.7747653	0.1815502
GLP1RA	Bronchial cancer	All - MR Egger	-6.336652	3.2991515	0.1031672
Insulin	Bronchial cancer	rs4031066	-1.46511	2.2245753	0.5101514
TZD	Bronchial cancer	rs4684833	1.7855526	1.6335	0.2743569
TZD	Bronchial cancer	rs2881654	1.3213078	0.5294431	0.0125724
TZD	Bronchial cancer	rs1373641	-0.721959	1.4804234	0.6257829
TZD	Bronchial cancer	rs2120825	1.502216	0.5688099	0.0082666
TZD	Bronchial cancer	rs111327339	0.4549577	1.7497885	0.7948582
TZD	Bronchial cancer	rs4135247	0.7250429	0.8426756	0.3895654
TZD	Bronchial cancer	rs1699348	-3.239392	2.516184	0.1979471
TZD	Bronchial cancer	rs310752	1.9053154	2.4046615	0.428161
TZD	Bronchial cancer	rs76763697	2.0282098	2.5646741	0.4290458
TZD	Bronchial cancer	rs2920503	3.4427674	2.0099302	0.0867348
TZD	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.1898547	0.2833884	2.68E-05
TZD	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.1898547	0.3169481	0.000174

TZD	Bronchial cancer	All - MR Egger	1.5163072	0.5048034	0.0169742
Amylin analog	Bronchial cancer	rs4663804	1.4405098	3.2284706	0.6554603
Amylin analog	Bronchial cancer	rs11869741	1.3272173	2.1172256	0.5307469
Amylin analog	Bronchial cancer	rs12603201	2.6796397	1.2663239	0.0343382
Amylin analog	Bronchial cancer	rs11654396	-0.923853	2.6398824	0.7263688
Amylin analog	Bronchial cancer	rs12941945	-0.608376	1.8445066	0.7415276
Amylin analog	Bronchial cancer	rs1078523	3.0233063	1.9369438	0.1185558
Amylin analog	Bronchial cancer	rs9905939	3.3358312	2.0243636	0.0993851
Amylin analog	Bronchial cancer	rs59795094	3.5418846	2.3965385	0.13943
Amylin analog	Bronchial cancer	rs9892728	3.07275	2.0411118	0.1322137
Amylin analog	Bronchial cancer	rs73111954	-0.139977	1.5629234	0.9286363
Amylin analog	Bronchial cancer	rs11772021	0.4513188	0.8800041	0.6080493
Amylin analog	Bronchial cancer	rs4724382	1.7145856	2.8363243	0.5455048
Amylin analog	Bronchial cancer	rs75390434	-2.732974	3.3135128	0.409487
Amylin analog	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.2456623	0.4369588	0.0043616
Amylin analog	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.2456623	0.4867446	0.0104922
Amylin analog	Bronchial cancer	All - MR Egger	0.3226228	1.0937647	0.7735129
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	rs4561482	2.4111111	2.6890342	0.369908
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	rs8057326	-3.75321	2.9456571	0.2026102
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	rs34497199	-3.24538	2.4129147	0.178624
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	rs142133957	-0.226362	1.9480914	0.9074965
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	rs11150624	-1.88368	2.576918	0.4647902
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	rs11865835	-6.738948	2.9770696	0.0235976
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	rs8057029	0.0361117	2.8124397	0.9897554
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	rs12448775	-0.807179	2.5360032	0.7502665
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	rs8054784	-0.992207	2.8570811	0.728381
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.476205	0.8130222	0.0694163
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.476205	0.8585535	0.0855399
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	All - MR Egger	0.0847521	2.0785659	0.9686144
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	rs4561482	2.4111111	2.6890342	0.369908
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	rs8057326	-3.75321	2.9456571	0.2026102

SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	rs34497199	-3.24538	2.4129147	0.178624
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	rs142133957	-0.226362	1.9480914	0.9074965
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	rs11150624	-1.88368	2.576918	0.4647902
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	rs11865835	-6.738948	2.9770696	0.0235976
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	rs8057029	0.0361117	2.8124397	0.9897554
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	rs12448775	-0.807179	2.5360032	0.7502665
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	rs8054784	-0.992207	2.8570811	0.728381
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.476205	0.8130222	0.0694163
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.476205	0.8585535	0.0855399
SGLT2i	Bronchial cancer	All - MR Egger	0.0847521	2.0785659	0.9686144
SU	Cervical cancer	rs77023203	-0.663539	0.4313741	0.124
SU	Cervical cancer	rs2074312	-1.131465	0.51967	0.02946
SU	Cervical cancer	rs116842927	0.7073462	1.5441779	0.6469
SU	Cervical cancer	rs7110898	0.5370226	2.2264606	0.8094
SU	Cervical cancer	rs4937311	2.8681783	1.5980179	0.07268
SU	Cervical cancer	rs4148631	1.8278782	1.4367786	0.2033
SU	Cervical cancer	rs10766393	-0.943257	0.5088088	0.06376
SU	Cervical cancer	rs5210	-0.696961	0.44936	0.1209
SU	Cervical cancer	rs10766395	-0.737564	0.4575957	0.107
SU	Cervical cancer	rs189603359	-0.897275	1.5089984	0.5521
SU	Cervical cancer	rs10766392	-0.943988	0.5044488	0.0613
SU	Cervical cancer	rs7110037	0.4461958	0.5847099	0.4454
SU	Cervical cancer	rs77902362	0.1366508	1.23789	0.9121
SU	Cervical cancer	rs35271178	-0.254795	0.2813275	0.3651
SU	Cervical cancer	rs147673442	1.5608311	1.0157928	0.1244
SU	Cervical cancer	rs2355016	0.5310033	0.6149914	0.3879
SU	Cervical cancer	rs2285676	-0.700199	0.4459683	0.1164
SU	Cervical cancer	rs739688	1.3872023	1.1484766	0.2271
SU	Cervical cancer	rs79506407	-0.768707	1.7050302	0.6521
SU	Cervical cancer	rs7112030	-0.648602	0.4543225	0.1534
SU	Cervical cancer	rs117973841	0.0694635	1.3413826	0.9587

SU	Cervical cancer	rs12816749	2.0590832	1.2199067	0.09143
SU	Cervical cancer	rs74732083	1.1477138	1.0485412	0.2737
SU	Cervical cancer	rs10841887	0.4147095	0.6158546	0.5007
SU	Cervical cancer	rs59406438	1.6025732	0.9347266	0.08644
SU	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.298124	0.1533758	0.0519259
SU	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.298124	0.1237944	0.0160306
SU	Cervical cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.314732	0.4044472	0.003524
AGI	Cervical cancer	rs72681706	-1.082328	1.3584402	0.4256
AGI	Cervical cancer	rs72692396	0.2046383	1.2099975	0.8657
AGI	Cervical cancer	rs174587	2.3091544	1.2239085	0.0592
AGI	Cervical cancer	rs112968754	-0.749152	1.3573445	0.581
AGI	Cervical cancer	rs8037100	-0.957603	1.709203	0.5753
AGI	Cervical cancer	rs1659215	-0.888341	1.7946274	0.6206
AGI	Cervical cancer	rs73402785	-0.227235	1.3863193	0.8698
AGI	Cervical cancer	rs34359922	0.2166546	1.3166677	0.8693
AGI	Cervical cancer	rs111917515	-0.46204	1.2353816	0.7084
AGI	Cervical cancer	rs113126535	-0.678218	1.3397602	0.6127
AGI	Cervical cancer	rs112898001	-0.455553	1.3374765	0.7334
AGI	Cervical cancer	rs4924660	-0.450033	1.5289701	0.7685
AGI	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.162344	0.281653	0.5643466
AGI	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.162344	0.3957688	0.6816597
AGI	Cervical cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.228123	1.4615686	0.4203895
DPP-4i	Cervical cancer	rs4233648	-2.743135	5.2424905	0.6008
DPP-4i	Cervical cancer	rs2080714	0.1232596	1.2272727	0.92
DPP-4i	Cervical cancer	rs75850673	-3.579448	1.7046943	0.03575
DPP-4i	Cervical cancer	rs188581353	-0.667724	1.2482521	0.5927
DPP-4i	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.995284	0.8087393	0.2184497
DPP-4i	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.995284	0.7700925	0.1962114
DPP-4i	Cervical cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.60422	1.9810415	0.7891789
Biguanides	Cervical cancer	rs150243609	0.0601264	1.2619933	0.962
Biguanides	Cervical cancer	rs17485664	-1.311175	1.3747287	0.3402

Biguanides	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.567	0.6831485	0.4065496
Biguanides	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.567	0.9296685	0.5419313
GLP1RA	Cervical cancer	rs10305525	0.0885456	1.8832845	0.9625
GLP1RA	Cervical cancer	rs228817	0.702236	1.4305189	0.6235
GLP1RA	Cervical cancer	rs12215108	1.3097309	1.3610453	0.3359
GLP1RA	Cervical cancer	rs28360624	-0.708368	1.4484316	0.6248
GLP1RA	Cervical cancer	rs11963172	-2.194952	1.1552697	0.05744
GLP1RA	Cervical cancer	rs880347	0.2590733	0.8674544	0.7652
GLP1RA	Cervical cancer	rs9462535	1.4417977	1.1790818	0.2214
GLP1RA	Cervical cancer	rs142878626	-0.173462	1.509277	0.9085
GLP1RA	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.0792555	0.4327116	0.8546724
GLP1RA	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0792555	0.4461618	0.8590069
GLP1RA	Cervical cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.749791	1.9677263	0.7162977
Insulin	Cervical cancer	rs4031066	-0.823793	1.2777269	0.5191
Insulin	Cervical cancer	rs144057856	-0.377524	1.0312396	0.7143
Insulin	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.553555	0.2181064	0.0111487
Insulin	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.553555	0.8024803	0.4903168
TZD	Cervical cancer	rs4684833	-0.161981	0.9352661	0.8625
TZD	Cervical cancer	rs2881654	0.2210432	0.3077502	0.4726
TZD	Cervical cancer	rs1373641	0.4299736	0.847467	0.6119
TZD	Cervical cancer	rs2120825	-0.01238	0.3417253	0.9711
TZD	Cervical cancer	rs111327339	-0.300614	0.9891706	0.7612
TZD	Cervical cancer	rs4135247	0.578171	0.4813551	0.2297
TZD	Cervical cancer	rs1699348	0.8514528	1.4475638	0.5564
TZD	Cervical cancer	rs310752	0.5171189	1.3742499	0.7067
TZD	Cervical cancer	rs76763697	0.3135989	1.499111	0.8343
TZD	Cervical cancer	rs2920503	0.8314991	1.1480513	0.4689
TZD	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.2150264	0.0882093	0.0147817
TZD	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.2150264	0.1850399	0.2452135
TZD	Cervical cancer	All - MR Egger	0.0264601	0.2955677	0.9308669
Amylin analog	Cervical cancer	rs4663804	5.9159048	6.0593171	0.3289

Amylin analog	Cervical cancer	rs11869741	2.9069642	4.9939344	0.5605
Amylin analog	Cervical cancer	rs12603201	0.3346455	0.7270141	0.6453
Amylin analog	Cervical cancer	rs11654396	-1.203335	1.5297393	0.4315
Amylin analog	Cervical cancer	rs12941945	-0.056732	1.0189632	0.9556
Amylin analog	Cervical cancer	rs1078523	-0.470517	1.1170532	0.6736
Amylin analog	Cervical cancer	rs9905939	0.5870613	1.1632886	0.6138
Amylin analog	Cervical cancer	rs59795094	-0.773103	1.3838746	0.5764
Amylin analog	Cervical cancer	rs9892728	-0.574873	1.1781889	0.6256
Amylin analog	Cervical cancer	rs73111954	-0.855179	0.9133243	0.3491
Amylin analog	Cervical cancer	rs11772021	-0.10586	0.5008334	0.8326
Amylin analog	Cervical cancer	rs4724382	-1.518659	1.6364605	0.3534
Amylin analog	Cervical cancer	rs75390434	-0.351148	1.9296163	0.8556
Amylin analog	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.211346	0.174885	0.2268611
Amylin analog	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.211346	0.2891553	0.4648357
Amylin analog	Cervical cancer	All - MR Egger	0.1878361	0.6677836	0.7837141
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	rs4561482	1.2472652	1.53937	0.4178
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	rs8057326	-0.12389	1.7327336	0.943
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	rs34497199	0.0077516	1.7670922	0.9965
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	rs142133957	-2.037014	1.2202144	0.09504
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	rs11150624	0.774136	1.4806951	0.6011
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	rs11865835	0.3904265	1.7177633	0.8202
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	rs8057029	1.1730175	1.6079896	0.4657
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	rs12448775	2.2571303	1.4023517	0.1075
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	rs8054784	1.7133339	1.6364235	0.2951
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.4844541	0.4825342	0.3153889
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.4844541	0.5122732	0.3443043
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.89867	1.2561254	0.4975062
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	rs4561482	1.2472652	1.53937	0.4178
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	rs8057326	-0.12389	1.7327336	0.943
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	rs34497199	0.0077516	1.7670922	0.9965
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	rs142133957	-2.037014	1.2202144	0.09504

SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	rs11150624	0.774136	1.4806951	0.6011
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	rs11865835	0.3904265	1.7177633	0.8202
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	rs8057029	1.1730175	1.6079896	0.4657
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	rs12448775	2.2571303	1.4023517	0.1075
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	rs8054784	1.7133339	1.6364235	0.2951
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.4844541	0.4825342	0.3153889
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.4844541	0.5122732	0.3443043
SGLT2i	Cervical cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.89867	1.2561254	0.4975062
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs77023203	-0.164795	1.7838949	0.9263968
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs2074312	0.4292351	2.1600541	0.8424857
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs116842927	5.997756	6.2713072	0.33888
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs7110898	14.491149	9.265617	0.1178246
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4937311	6.4064841	6.5531111	0.3282599
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs5219	0.1130061	1.031498	0.9127621
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4148631	9.9361538	5.9163427	0.093066
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs10766393	1.3182861	2.1155381	0.5331895
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs5210	-0.541071	1.8611084	0.7712614
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs10766395	-0.089167	1.8926466	0.9624236
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs189603359	-5.577782	6.2903891	0.3752324
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs10766392	1.3250833	2.0980365	0.5276597
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs7110037	0.5935789	2.4026447	0.8048677
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs77902362	1.7611753	5.0612987	0.7278634
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs35271178	0.2197225	1.1581225	0.8495262
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs147673442	-0.536598	4.1065544	0.8960373
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs2355016	0.6905444	2.5333361	0.7851738
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs2285676	-0.522039	1.8431268	0.7769963
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs739688	4.4128323	4.5627964	0.3334774
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs79506407	-1.793019	7.049562	0.7992292
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs7112030	0.2622258	1.877727	0.888936
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs117973841	-6.161821	5.6113245	0.2721588
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs12816749	4.0222367	5.0854497	0.4289846

SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs74732083	7.6230269	4.516861	0.0914722
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs10841887	0.8824235	2.5395382	0.7282352
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	rs59406438	-0.302928	3.9890486	0.9394669
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.448404	0.3445039	0.1930555
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.448404	0.4584669	0.3280491
SU	Cervix uteri cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.68682	1.2063613	0.1748204
AGI	Cervix uteri cancer	rs72681706	8.8196487	5.6266979	0.1170062
AGI	Cervix uteri cancer	rs72692396	11.107345	5.0081038	0.0265634
AGI	Cervix uteri cancer	rs174587	6.4652514	4.9853464	0.1946825
AGI	Cervix uteri cancer	rs112968754	-5.84878	5.5766667	0.2942724
AGI	Cervix uteri cancer	rs8037100	-8.511487	7.0168205	0.2251252
AGI	Cervix uteri cancer	rs1659215	-8.148865	7.3905405	0.2701977
AGI	Cervix uteri cancer	rs73402785	-6.211857	5.6835021	0.2744101
AGI	Cervix uteri cancer	rs34359922	-9.02678	5.4758898	0.0992585
AGI	Cervix uteri cancer	rs111917515	-5.687897	5.0818081	0.2630265
AGI	Cervix uteri cancer	rs113126535	-6.37392	5.48996	0.2456362
AGI	Cervix uteri cancer	rs112898001	-5.903068	5.498247	0.2829898
AGI	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4924660	-3.459753	6.3214368	0.5841693
AGI	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.952039	2.1620771	0.3666036
AGI	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.952039	1.6291353	0.230837
AGI	Cervix uteri cancer	All - MR Egger	10.411499	7.353305	0.1871907
DPP-4i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4233648	7.0006048	6.1621613	0.2559301
DPP-4i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs2080714	7.0327922	5.0087857	0.1602917
DPP-4i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs75850673	-15.1146	7.0901863	0.0330263
DPP-4i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs188581353	-5.189512	5.5876846	0.3530233
DPP-4i	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.018534	4.9461966	0.9970102
DPP-4i	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.018534	2.9096878	0.9949177
DPP-4i	Cervix uteri cancer	All - MR Egger	-8.384082	12.258234	0.5646154
Biguanides	Cervix uteri cancer	rs150243609	-7.406414	5.0346143	0.1412644
Biguanides	Cervix uteri cancer	rs17485664	-3.417494	5.6165799	0.5428789
Biguanides	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	-5.629254	1.982587	0.0045206

Biguanides	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-5.629254	3.7489318	0.1332102
GLP1RA	Cervix uteri cancer	rs10305525	-18.61038	8.0194304	0.0203051
GLP1RA	Cervix uteri cancer	rs228817	3.464186	5.9580465	0.5609508
GLP1RA	Cervix uteri cancer	rs12215108	6.2531606	5.6321762	0.2668885
GLP1RA	Cervix uteri cancer	rs28360624	-5.586048	5.9411796	0.347102
GLP1RA	Cervix uteri cancer	rs11963172	-3.00825	4.7201944	0.5239198
GLP1RA	Cervix uteri cancer	rs880347	3.5072919	3.5705215	0.3259564
GLP1RA	Cervix uteri cancer	rs9462535	2.2036774	4.910871	0.6536232
GLP1RA	Cervix uteri cancer	rs142878626	5.2794009	6.1868433	0.3934779
GLP1RA	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.7350858	2.2004899	0.7383377
GLP1RA	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.7350858	1.8427496	0.6899617
GLP1RA	Cervix uteri cancer	All - MR Egger	8.3034853	9.6253837	0.4214587
Insulin	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4031066	-0.530745	5.3008699	0.9202458
TZD	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4684833	3.4900088	3.9013202	0.3710163
TZD	Cervix uteri cancer	rs2881654	0.9266144	1.2682864	0.4650214
TZD	Cervix uteri cancer	rs1373641	-2.165824	3.5153018	0.5378197
TZD	Cervix uteri cancer	rs2120825	0.609	1.3613948	0.654633
TZD	Cervix uteri cancer	rs111327339	2.5595166	4.2494864	0.5469665
TZD	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4135247	2.0222064	2.0069249	0.3136396
TZD	Cervix uteri cancer	rs1699348	-7.288264	5.991272	0.223802
TZD	Cervix uteri cancer	rs310752	-0.813623	5.7144692	0.8867803
TZD	Cervix uteri cancer	rs76763697	-6.198348	6.0776786	0.3077974
TZD	Cervix uteri cancer	rs2920503	-8.55157	4.7797035	0.0735919
TZD	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.4781615	0.7423893	0.5195206
TZD	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.4781615	0.7579165	0.5281128
TZD	Cervix uteri cancer	All - MR Egger	2.0579075	1.2073778	0.1266977
Amylin analog	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4663804	-10.95676	7.6775392	0.1535455
Amylin analog	Cervix uteri cancer	rs11869741	-0.232038	5.0298329	0.9632047
Amylin analog	Cervix uteri cancer	rs12603201	5.4073684	3.0098623	0.0724071
Amylin analog	Cervix uteri cancer	rs11654396	1.3378309	6.2705882	0.8310539
Amylin analog	Cervix uteri cancer	rs12941945	1.8321616	4.3676856	0.6748646

Amylin analog	Cervix uteri cancer	rs1078523	-12.01563	4.6102813	0.0091535
Amylin analog	Cervix uteri cancer	rs9905939	-10.76312	4.809513	0.0252288
Amylin analog	Cervix uteri cancer	rs59795094	-17.16108	5.7075923	0.0026409
Amylin analog	Cervix uteri cancer	rs9892728	-12.93974	4.8593882	0.0077486
Amylin analog	Cervix uteri cancer	rs73111954	-3.142357	3.7193319	0.3981826
Amylin analog	Cervix uteri cancer	rs11772021	-2.540393	2.0946791	0.2252124
Amylin analog	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4724382	-2.469378	6.7482613	0.7144187
Amylin analog	Cervix uteri cancer	rs75390434	-2.83853	7.8984701	0.7193129
Amylin analog	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	-3.322455	1.7565412	0.0585609
Amylin analog	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.322455	1.1576049	0.0041033
Amylin analog	Cervix uteri cancer	All - MR Egger	2.6314265	3.604843	0.4806656
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4561482	8.0992564	6.4020256	0.2058325
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs8057326	-3.687448	7.0063333	0.5986784
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs34497199	-0.015035	5.7456977	0.9979121
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs142133957	-4.213116	4.7387113	0.3739575
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs11150624	-0.428057	6.1247213	0.9442812
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs11865835	-2.794783	7.0960696	0.6936922
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs8057029	-2.330836	6.6904397	0.7275525
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs12448775	-2.144619	5.9901603	0.7203257
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs8054784	1.0607477	6.799045	0.8760218
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.930403	1.2333887	0.4506411
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.930403	2.0500031	0.6499338
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	All - MR Egger	-4.475796	5.0152697	0.4017963
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4561482	8.0992564	6.4020256	0.2058325
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs8057326	-3.687448	7.0063333	0.5986784
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs34497199	-0.015035	5.7456977	0.9979121
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs142133957	-4.213116	4.7387113	0.3739575
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs11150624	-0.428057	6.1247213	0.9442812
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs11865835	-2.794783	7.0960696	0.6936922
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs8057029	-2.330836	6.6904397	0.7275525
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs12448775	-2.144619	5.9901603	0.7203257

SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	rs8054784	1.0607477	6.799045	0.8760218
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.930403	1.2333887	0.4506411
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.930403	2.0500031	0.6499338
SGLT2i	Cervix uteri cancer	All - MR Egger	-4.475796	5.0152697	0.4017963
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs77023203	-1.025701	0.9626168	0.2866344
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs2074312	-1.067568	1.1432432	0.3504039
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs116842927	1.5119826	4.2069717	0.7192964
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs7110898	3.2382979	3.2595745	0.3204797
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4937311	-3.206349	3.5	0.3596146
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs5219	-0.660834	0.5598923	0.2378855
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4148631	4.4265734	3.4195804	0.1955002
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs10766393	-0.267717	1.1181102	0.810767
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs5210	-0.684729	1.0098522	0.4977408
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs10766395	-0.711779	1.0275689	0.4885086
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs189603359	1.0311284	3.9494163	0.7940279
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs10766392	-0.226563	1.109375	0.8381774
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs7110037	1.5289474	1.4026316	0.2756884
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs77902362	-4.100649	3.6428571	0.2603059
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs35271178	-0.12093	0.6341085	0.8487536
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs147673442	-7.049223	2.507772	0.0049395
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs2355016	0.9388889	1.5111111	0.5343868
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs2285676	-0.685366	1	0.4931131
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs739688	5.0239521	2.4730539	0.0422066
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs79506407	-3.038929	2.379562	0.2015683
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs7112030	-1.081886	1.0198511	0.2887684
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs117973841	3.4437086	3.7980132	0.3645585
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs12816749	0.5147929	3.1183432	0.8688768
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs74732083	1.2309417	3.0022422	0.6818005
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs10841887	1.4882353	1.4617647	0.3086263
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs59406438	3.5708245	2.7251586	0.1900883
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.352915	0.2664932	0.1854056

SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.352915	0.2514887	0.1605261
SU	Cholangiocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	-1.262016	0.6892929	0.0795623
AGI	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs72681706	3.5831382	3.5550351	0.3135
AGI	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs72692396	3.0139721	3.251497	0.353953
AGI	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs174587	2.0446927	3.0502793	0.5026477
AGI	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs112968754	-4.601626	3.695122	0.2130125
AGI	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs8037100	-3.620513	3.8461538	0.3465341
AGI	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs1659215	-3.983784	4.0486486	0.325126
AGI	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs73402785	-4.649789	3.7721519	0.2177018
AGI	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs34359922	-5.063559	3.6440678	0.1646702
AGI	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs111917515	-4.940959	3.3247232	0.1372457
AGI	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs113126535	-5.768	3.596	0.1087131
AGI	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs112898001	-4.398406	3.5896414	0.2204602
AGI	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4924660	-2.212644	3.4597701	0.522475
AGI	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-2.25966	1.021091	0.0268986
AGI	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.25966	1.021916	0.0270221
AGI	Cholangiocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	1.8509437	3.7776365	0.6347234
DPP-4i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4233648	-2.959677	3.4274194	0.3878465
DPP-4i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs2080714	-6.266234	3.4285714	0.0676019
DPP-4i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs75850673	-1.857143	3.4409938	0.5893962
DPP-4i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs188581353	-3.227785	3.0450563	0.2891409
DPP-4i	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-3.558535	0.9150111	0.0001006
DPP-4i	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.558535	1.6609102	0.0321516
DPP-4i	Cholangiocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	-3.26242	3.6434996	0.4650589
Biguanides	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs150243609	3.0914286	3.4385714	0.368629
Biguanides	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs17485664	-5.933086	3.8513011	0.1234286
Biguanides	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.911521	4.4834217	0.8388933
Biguanides	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.911521	2.5649898	0.7223121
GLP1RA	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs10305525	-0.240506	3.6962025	0.9481195
GLP1RA	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs228817	-5.356589	3.372093	0.112172
GLP1RA	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs12215108	0.4507772	3.761658	0.9046141

GLP1RA	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs28360624	-1.419162	4.1077844	0.7297328
GLP1RA	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs11963172	-0.405556	3.2277778	0.9000126
GLP1RA	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs880347	-2.732057	2.2009569	0.2144933
GLP1RA	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs9462535	-5.341935	2.683871	0.0465486
GLP1RA	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs142878626	0.9976959	3.6198157	0.7828395
GLP1RA	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-2.237481	0.8621319	0.0094511
GLP1RA	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.237481	1.1120493	0.0442163
GLP1RA	Cholangiocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	3.7134618	4.596172	0.4499584
Insulin	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4031066	3.7260274	3.2465753	0.251101
Insulin	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs144057856	14.113208	9.8079911	0.1501647
Insulin	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	4.7517593	3.0987637	0.1251682
Insulin	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	4.7517593	3.0821103	0.123141
TZD	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4684833	3.6096491	2.1798246	0.0977349
TZD	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs2881654	-0.425028	0.7745209	0.5831683
TZD	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs1373641	1.0405405	2.009009	0.6045021
TZD	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs2120825	-0.51856	0.8121485	0.5231456
TZD	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs111327339	-7.427492	2.9592145	0.0120747
TZD	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4135247	-0.243968	1.0911528	0.8230785
TZD	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs1699348	-7.456	3.512	0.0337533
TZD	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs310752	3.9153846	3.1615385	0.2155519
TZD	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs76763697	0.4107143	3.2544643	0.8995734
TZD	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs2920503	-3.331395	2.505814	0.1836942
TZD	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.444293	0.6109909	0.4671233
TZD	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.444293	0.4458688	0.3190242
TZD	Cholangiocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.599512	1.0424373	0.5810296
Amylin analog	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4663804	-7.892157	4.1960784	0.0599935
Amylin analog	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs11869741	0.5125348	2.9916435	0.8639705
Amylin analog	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs12603201	-0.445344	1.6477733	0.7869523
Amylin analog	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs11654396	-3.25	3.8308824	0.3962328
Amylin analog	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs12941945	6.2532751	2.8646288	0.0290412
Amylin analog	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs1078523	0.61875	2.55	0.8082788

Amylin analog	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs9905939	0.9675325	2.6298701	0.7129469
Amylin analog	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs59795094	1.2461538	3.1461538	0.6920401
Amylin analog	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs9892728	0.6907895	2.6842105	0.7969063
Amylin analog	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs73111954	1.8425532	2.1021277	0.3807484
Amylin analog	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs11772021	2.1821946	1.3312629	0.1011734
Amylin analog	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4724382	1.3873874	3.9459459	0.7251396
Amylin analog	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs75390434	-1.230769	4.1794872	0.7683923
Amylin analog	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.9688902	0.6537126	0.1383044
Amylin analog	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.9688902	0.6777446	0.1528375
Amylin analog	Cholangiocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	3.3342496	1.5790917	0.0584249
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4561482	1.7863248	3.4700855	0.6067079
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs8057326	2.552381	4.7142857	0.5882222
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs34497199	2.9767442	3.503876	0.3955711
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs142133957	4.3213703	3.3230016	0.1934496
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs11150624	3.1147541	3.3360656	0.3504788
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs11865835	0.2782609	4.0608696	0.9453697
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs8057029	1.5948276	3.5862069	0.6565282
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs12448775	1.9903846	3.8301282	0.6032969
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs8054784	3.2792793	3.6756757	0.3723089
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	2.52973	0.3910896	9.90E-11
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	2.52973	1.2212522	0.0383193
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	3.9237368	3.4092289	0.2875589
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4561482	1.7863248	3.4700855	0.6067079
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs8057326	2.552381	4.7142857	0.5882222
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs34497199	2.9767442	3.503876	0.3955711
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs142133957	4.3213703	3.3230016	0.1934496
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs11150624	3.1147541	3.3360656	0.3504788
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs11865835	0.2782609	4.0608696	0.9453697
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs8057029	1.5948276	3.5862069	0.6565282
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs12448775	1.9903846	3.8301282	0.6032969
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs8054784	3.2792793	3.6756757	0.3723089

SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	2.52973	0.3910896	9.90E-11
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	2.52973	1.2212522	0.0383193
SGLT2i	Cholangiocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	3.9237368	3.4092289	0.2875589
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs77023203	1.5066472	1.8263224	0.409393
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs2074312	0.9286973	2.2110216	0.6744629
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs116842927	-7.625686	6.3734205	0.2315083
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs7110898	-6.480553	9.3992766	0.4905253
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs4937311	-6.887841	6.7052063	0.3043085
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs5219	-0.205738	1.054607	0.8453267
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs4148631	-7.992098	6.0517762	0.186628
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs10766393	0.1132748	2.1669921	0.9583113
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs5210	1.3979729	1.9039384	0.4627944
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs10766395	1.6271754	1.936411	0.4007375
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs189603359	-8.900584	6.5085603	0.1714625
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs10766392	0.0669003	2.1485417	0.9751599
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs7110037	-1.080134	2.4558342	0.6600648
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs77902362	2.0992825	5.1973701	0.6862771
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs35271178	0.5574651	1.1836047	0.6376484
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs147673442	-3.298964	4.2106736	0.4333474
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs2355016	-1.626819	2.5906694	0.5300345
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs2285676	1.3941537	1.8856024	0.4596837
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs739688	-5.414275	4.6547126	0.2447559
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs79506407	-6.945085	7.1680779	0.3325996
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs7112030	2.1961216	1.9219057	0.2531718
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs117973841	-1.46604	5.7061258	0.7972376
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs12816749	-12.37278	5.1961243	0.0172584
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs74732083	0.0841756	4.568296	0.985299
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs10841887	-0.479732	2.6025618	0.8537539
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	rs59406438	1.2238901	4.0560888	0.7628492
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	IVW(random effects)	0.0981231	0.4221913	0.8162167
SU	Chronic lymphocytic leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0981231	0.4688875	0.8342392

SU	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	All - MR Egger	2.6611194	1.2330687	0.0411396
AGI	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs72681706	12.797424	5.73363	0.0256154
AGI	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs72692396	8.4444511	5.1212375	0.0991664
AGI	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs174587	-6.222346	5.0707765	0.2197853
AGI	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs112968754	1.5718618	5.7054472	0.7829306
AGI	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs8037100	5.9245641	7.1842564	0.409565
AGI	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs1659215	5.7224324	7.5665946	0.4494839
AGI	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs73402785	1.4106582	5.8154008	0.8083363
AGI	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs34359922	-1.315314	5.5994068	0.8142846
AGI	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs111917515	4.0487085	5.1981181	0.4360506
AGI	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs113126535	4.80624	5.61848	0.3923108
AGI	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs112898001	3.6294064	5.6231076	0.5186389
AGI	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs4924660	1.2078103	6.4463218	0.851375
AGI	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	3.2645611	1.4713496	0.0265035
AGI	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	3.2645611	1.6647229	0.0498763
AGI	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	All - MR Egger	16.121839	6.1612216	0.0257447
DPP-4i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs4233648	8.0841129	6.28325	0.1982291
DPP-4i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs2080714	4.3660844	5.1227338	0.3940499
DPP-4i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs75850673	-6.748882	7.2357143	0.3509655
DPP-4i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs188581353	10.819462	5.7122403	0.0582139
DPP-4i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	5.0698583	3.402125	0.1361708
DPP-4i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	5.0698583	2.9724128	0.0880756
DPP-4i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	All - MR Egger	10.269863	8.6570603	0.3573291
Biguanides	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs150243609	1.8663714	5.0907143	0.7139005
Biguanides	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs17485664	-3.291911	5.7610037	0.5677199
Biguanides	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	-0.395364	2.5595356	0.8772416
Biguanides	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.395364	3.8147534	0.9174545
GLP1RA	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs10305525	-4.953778	8.2318987	0.5473217
GLP1RA	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs228817	8.0828682	6.0923023	0.1845965
GLP1RA	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs12215108	5.9194819	5.7394301	0.3023669
GLP1RA	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs28360624	-0.870844	6.0739521	0.8859951

GLP1RA	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs11963172	-2.555939	4.8207278	0.5959748
GLP1RA	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs880347	3.4619665	3.6545933	0.3434901
GLP1RA	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs9462535	2.1387484	5.0251419	0.6703924
GLP1RA	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs142878626	7.7266359	6.3562903	0.2241416
GLP1RA	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	2.5795351	1.4551751	0.0762846
GLP1RA	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	2.5795351	1.8850593	0.1711836
GLP1RA	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	All - MR Egger	6.1837451	8.0591694	0.4720113
Insulin	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs4031066	2.7369178	5.4152329	0.6132703
TZD	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs4684833	5.155614	3.9675175	0.1937875
TZD	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs2881654	0.3997001	1.2914318	0.7569401
TZD	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs1373641	5.6021171	3.5964865	0.1193129
TZD	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs2120825	0.3471721	1.3890551	0.8026384
TZD	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs111327339	5.3504834	4.2966465	0.2130327
TZD	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs4135247	3.7953619	2.0494155	0.0640367
TZD	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs1699348	-3.817728	6.116776	0.5325353
TZD	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs310752	8.0393077	5.8492154	0.1693098
TZD	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs76763697	7.8809821	6.2132143	0.204647
TZD	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs2920503	0.1696663	4.8874244	0.9723071
TZD	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	1.6229093	0.7611174	0.0329845
TZD	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	1.6229093	0.7727391	0.0357109
TZD	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	All - MR Egger	0.2036397	1.2311102	0.8727237
Amylin analog	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs4663804	3.1247157	7.8558725	0.6908105
Amylin analog	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs11869741	3.7689136	5.1434819	0.4637077
Amylin analog	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs12603201	2.7773239	3.07717	0.3667606
Amylin analog	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs11654396	-2.493897	6.4094338	0.6972037
Amylin analog	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs12941945	-4.781528	4.4779913	0.2856179
Amylin analog	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs1078523	0.3401506	4.7070625	0.9423919
Amylin analog	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs9905939	1.7356948	4.9184675	0.7241683
Amylin analog	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs59795094	1.9959538	5.8239615	0.7318135
Amylin analog	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs9892728	0.1056243	4.9599013	0.9830098
Amylin analog	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs73111954	-3.209634	3.8043915	0.3988563

Amylin analog	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs11772021	-0.625437	2.1467288	0.7707881
Amylin analog	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs4724382	0.4735135	6.8938198	0.945239
Amylin analog	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs75390434	-8.116402	8.0755726	0.3148699
Amylin analog	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	-0.18865	0.7518003	0.801868
Amylin analog	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.18865	1.1843769	0.873447
Amylin analog	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	All - MR Egger	-0.23988	2.664675	0.9298879
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs4561482	2.1207863	6.5333077	0.7454752
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs8057326	2.6614762	7.1592286	0.7100756
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs34497199	-0.62522	5.8653721	0.9151102
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs142133957	-2.719527	4.7752692	0.5690153
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs11150624	0.7650893	6.2652541	0.902807
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs11865835	8.3713478	7.2602957	0.2488976
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs8057029	-2.633172	6.8325603	0.6999515
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs12448775	-8.248782	6.2020833	0.1835177
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs8054784	-2.721396	6.9438378	0.6951208
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	-0.808914	1.4504603	0.5770528
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.808914	2.0921445	0.6990201
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	All - MR Egger	-6.229382	5.0905482	0.2606476
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs4561482	2.1207863	6.5333077	0.7454752
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs8057326	2.6614762	7.1592286	0.7100756
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs34497199	-0.62522	5.8653721	0.9151102
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs142133957	-2.719527	4.7752692	0.5690153
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs11150624	0.7650893	6.2652541	0.902807
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs11865835	8.3713478	7.2602957	0.2488976
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs8057029	-2.633172	6.8325603	0.6999515
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs12448775	-8.248782	6.2020833	0.1835177
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs8054784	-2.721396	6.9438378	0.6951208
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	-0.808914	1.4504603	0.5770528
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.808914	2.0921445	0.6990201
SGLT2i	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	All - MR Egger	-6.229382	5.0905482	0.2606476
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs77023203	0.407514	3.2856075	0.9012915

SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs2074312	0.9713865	3.9747027	0.8069271
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs116842927	-8.358148	11.535708	0.4687308
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs7110898	23.145149	16.884894	0.1704496
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4937311	4.3184683	12.078571	0.720694
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs5219	-1.563217	1.897389	0.410009
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4148631	8.0553846	10.876853	0.4589367
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs10766393	-2.487769	3.8948294	0.5229945
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs5210	-0.838458	3.4243596	0.8065717
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs10766395	-1.287356	3.4821805	0.7116074
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs189603359	1.0454611	11.497004	0.9275455
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs10766392	-1.863635	3.861849	0.6293969
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs7110037	-3.862605	4.4123684	0.3813541
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs77902362	-2.129893	9.3526299	0.8198546
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs35271178	-1.351702	2.1312403	0.525929
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs147673442	0.8627953	7.5812953	0.9093917
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs2355016	-3.955444	4.6554722	0.395529
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs2285676	-0.819398	3.3913659	0.8090802
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs739688	-8.574371	8.3686826	0.3055622
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs79506407	-3.251363	12.998175	0.8024791
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs7112030	0.4456228	3.4574194	0.8974456
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs117973841	-3.029166	10.226821	0.7670788
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs12816749	-3.462793	9.3565089	0.711312
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs74732083	3.953139	8.2501345	0.6318244
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs10841887	6.5281765	4.6734118	0.1624509
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs59406438	-9.378076	7.2772727	0.1975093
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	-1.016905	0.5448636	0.0619928
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.016905	0.8433623	0.2279046
SU	Chronic myelogenous leuk	All - MR Egger	-2.077183	2.2187585	0.3585002
AGI	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs72681706	-5.578829	10.384871	0.5911244
AGI	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs72692396	-7.541377	9.2577445	0.4153002
AGI	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs174587	14.464246	9.1406145	0.1135549

AGI	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs112968754	21.218577	10.272846	0.0388756
AGI	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs8037100	26.315026	12.920615	0.0416832
AGI	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs1659215	27.325027	13.604324	0.0445844
AGI	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs73402785	19.278354	10.491013	0.0661204
AGI	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs34359922	32.669703	10.347797	0.0015931
AGI	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs111917515	19.63941	9.3543911	0.0357741
AGI	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs113126535	20.9468	10.10924	0.0382612
AGI	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs112898001	21.460558	10.123227	0.0340117
AGI	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4924660	23.197069	11.611207	0.0457365
AGI	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	16.555292	3.6407948	5.44E-06
AGI	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	16.555292	3.0070402	3.68E-08
AGI	Chronic myelogenous leuk	All - MR Egger	-15.26785	11.130243	0.2001325
DPP-4i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4233648	0.9223468	11.299355	0.9349423
DPP-4i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs2080714	9.2331169	9.2287013	0.317079
DPP-4i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs75850673	4.4181242	13.057267	0.735088
DPP-4i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs188581353	22.055569	10.332466	0.0327946
DPP-4i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	10.002265	4.5863782	0.0291935
DPP-4i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	10.002265	5.3601068	0.0620334
DPP-4i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	All - MR Egger	25.943523	12.347381	0.17041
Biguanides	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs150243609	-2.712771	9.1450286	0.7667422
Biguanides	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs17485664	14.891859	10.35026	0.1502098
Biguanides	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	5.0053395	8.7352877	0.5666432
Biguanides	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	5.0053395	6.8531987	0.4651668
GLP1RA	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs10305525	0.549093	14.808354	0.9704213
GLP1RA	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs228817	8.6096124	10.953178	0.4318453
GLP1RA	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs12215108	13.685181	10.324611	0.1850083
GLP1RA	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs28360624	9.1777246	10.984072	0.403409
GLP1RA	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs11963172	7.8778333	8.6946111	0.3649045
GLP1RA	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs880347	-18.7266	6.5963636	0.0045265
GLP1RA	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs9462535	-1.618748	9.026	0.8576685
GLP1RA	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs142878626	6.7899309	11.315829	0.5484807

GLP1RA	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	-0.164557	4.505893	0.9708674
GLP1RA	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.164557	3.393057	0.9613192
GLP1RA	Chronic myelogenous leuk	All - MR Egger	-10.42467	20.22181	0.6246292
Insulin	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4031066	-3.071726	9.7289726	0.7522076
TZD	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4684833	8.1776754	7.118114	0.2506161
TZD	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs2881654	-1.876471	2.3146449	0.4175408
TZD	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs1373641	11.908333	6.4724775	0.0657915
TZD	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs2120825	-4.370045	2.4884027	0.0790603
TZD	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs111327339	8.1826435	7.732145	0.2899355
TZD	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4135247	-0.636938	3.685496	0.8627906
TZD	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs1699348	18.47352	11.00256	0.0931481
TZD	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs310752	2.6120077	10.509308	0.8037148
TZD	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs76763697	7.8442411	11.196384	0.4835496
TZD	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs2920503	-6.276802	8.7713372	0.474236
TZD	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	-0.697775	1.6804885	0.6779797
TZD	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.697775	1.3862292	0.6147098
TZD	Chronic myelogenous leuk	All - MR Egger	-4.80952	2.207796	0.061012
Amylin analog	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4663804	-9.058971	14.123039	0.521242
Amylin analog	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs11869741	8.578468	9.2970195	0.3561575
Amylin analog	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs12603201	-4.330202	5.5351012	0.4340284
Amylin analog	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs11654396	-3.765066	11.495662	0.7432742
Amylin analog	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs12941945	7.1965066	8.0314847	0.3702331
Amylin analog	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs1078523	13.097125	8.46925	0.1220001
Amylin analog	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs9905939	11.088247	8.8476623	0.2101183
Amylin analog	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs59795094	14.851385	10.481615	0.1565126
Amylin analog	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs9892728	13.567895	8.925	0.1284576
Amylin analog	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs73111954	-0.341482	6.8357872	0.9601583
Amylin analog	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs11772021	4.9745549	3.8470186	0.1959787
Amylin analog	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4724382	16.722342	12.383874	0.1769095
Amylin analog	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs75390434	-13.2594	14.573162	0.3629013
Amylin analog	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	4.5310503	2.0239673	0.0251756

Amylin analog	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	4.5310503	2.127832	0.0332194
Amylin analog	Chronic myelogenous leuk	All - MR Egger	2.9412251	4.7831362	0.5511188
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4561482	-4.189855	11.763761	0.7217161
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs8057326	-2.03679	12.874286	0.8742944
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs34497199	-5.796023	10.54907	0.5827073
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs142133957	-11.97491	8.6128548	0.1644216
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs11150624	-1.338164	11.283443	0.9055959
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs11865835	-3.164383	13.046174	0.8083521
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs8057029	-6.86819	12.307759	0.5768188
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs12448775	-6.919679	11.019135	0.530024
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs8054784	-5.848117	12.508739	0.6401261
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	-6.011016	1.2115888	7.00E-07
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	-6.011016	3.7613074	0.1100165
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	All - MR Egger	-12.40093	9.1470656	0.2172958
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4561482	-4.189855	11.763761	0.7217161
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs8057326	-2.03679	12.874286	0.8742944
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs34497199	-5.796023	10.54907	0.5827073
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs142133957	-11.97491	8.6128548	0.1644216
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs11150624	-1.338164	11.283443	0.9055959
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs11865835	-3.164383	13.046174	0.8083521
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs8057029	-6.86819	12.307759	0.5768188
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs12448775	-6.919679	11.019135	0.530024
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs8054784	-5.848117	12.508739	0.6401261
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	-6.011016	1.2115888	7.00E-07
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	-6.011016	3.7613074	0.1100165
SGLT2i	Chronic myelogenous leuk	All - MR Egger	-12.40093	9.1470656	0.2172958
SU	Coloc cancer	rs77023203	0.0040447	0.0028594	0.1572132
SU	Coloc cancer	rs2074312	0.0041068	0.0034718	0.2368481
SU	Coloc cancer	rs4937311	6.10E-04	0.0105137	0.9537235
SU	Coloc cancer	rs5219	0.0016432	0.0016568	0.3213132
SU	Coloc cancer	rs4148631	-0.013817	0.0094938	0.1455699

SU	Coloc cancer	rs10766393	0.0021046	0.0033992	0.5358083
SU	Coloc cancer	rs5210	0.0039118	0.0029894	0.1906815
SU	Coloc cancer	rs10766395	0.0043455	0.0030383	0.1526471
SU	Coloc cancer	rs10766392	0.0020437	0.0033709	0.544337
SU	Coloc cancer	rs35271178	0.0015922	0.0018582	0.3915438
SU	Coloc cancer	rs2285676	0.003854	0.0029604	0.1929565
SU	Coloc cancer	rs739688	-0.015756	0.0072659	0.0301225
SU	Coloc cancer	rs7112030	0.0036854	0.0030152	0.2216115
SU	Coloc cancer	rs12816749	-0.002135	0.0081611	0.793652
SU	Coloc cancer	rs10841887	-7.88E-04	0.0040813	0.8469632
SU	Coloc cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.0021889	0.0007373	0.002988
SU	Coloc cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0021889	0.0007925	0.0057447
SU	Coloc cancer	All - MR Egger	0.0050665	0.0019562	0.0224319
DPP-4i	Coloc cancer	rs4233648	0.014613	0.0097516	0.1339983
DPP-4i	Coloc cancer	rs2080714	1.65E-04	0.0080345	0.9836356
DPP-4i	Coloc cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.0060069	0.0070907	0.3969053
DPP-4i	Coloc cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0060069	0.0062009	0.3326855
GLP1RA	Coloc cancer	rs228817	0.0240702	0.0095519	0.0117378
GLP1RA	Coloc cancer	rs11963172	-7.17E-04	0.0075918	0.9247922
GLP1RA	Coloc cancer	rs880347	-0.007661	0.0057238	0.1807664
GLP1RA	Coloc cancer	rs9462535	-0.004642	0.0078577	0.5546709
GLP1RA	Coloc cancer	IVW(random effects)	-7.68E-04	0.0061289	0.9002591
GLP1RA	Coloc cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-7.68E-04	0.0036508	0.8333478
GLP1RA	Coloc cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.050793	0.0222212	0.149601
Insulin	Coloc cancer	rs4031066	0.0064486	0.0084882	0.4474211
TZD	Coloc cancer	rs1373641	-0.002071	0.0056201	0.7124901
TZD	Coloc cancer	rs4135247	0.0019211	0.0032037	0.5487477
TZD	Coloc cancer	rs1699348	0.0043522	0.0095671	0.6491688
TZD	Coloc cancer	rs310752	-0.011424	0.0091575	0.2122185
TZD	Coloc cancer	rs2920503	-0.00264	0.0076332	0.7294938
TZD	Coloc cancer	IVW(random effects)	-7.32E-05	0.0018747	0.968851

TZD	Coloc cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-7.32E-05	0.0024318	0.9759844
TZD	Coloc cancer	All - MR Egger	0.0046942	0.0058696	0.4823219
Amylin analog	Coloc cancer	rs4663804	-0.001744	0.0120614	0.8850123
Amylin analog	Coloc cancer	rs12603201	-0.008361	0.00483	0.0834563
Amylin analog	Coloc cancer	rs11654396	0.0103819	0.0100576	0.3019559
Amylin analog	Coloc cancer	rs1078523	0.0084029	0.0073953	0.2558512
Amylin analog	Coloc cancer	rs9905939	0.0081608	0.0076947	0.2888832
Amylin analog	Coloc cancer	rs59795094	0.0086222	0.0091216	0.3445342
Amylin analog	Coloc cancer	rs9892728	0.0090441	0.0077911	0.2457115
Amylin analog	Coloc cancer	rs4724382	-0.019832	0.0108152	0.0666959
Amylin analog	Coloc cancer	IVW(random effects)	8.10E-04	0.0036083	0.8223445
Amylin analog	Coloc cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	8.10E-04	0.0027541	0.7686275
Amylin analog	Coloc cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.00897	0.0137854	0.5393718
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	rs4561482	-0.023596	0.0102562	0.0214129
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	rs8057326	-0.001176	0.0112449	0.9167357
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	rs34497199	0.0028307	0.0091939	0.7581671
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	rs11150624	-0.01438	0.009839	0.143866
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	rs11865835	0.0058187	0.011399	0.6097313
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	rs8057029	-0.027224	0.010706	0.0109956
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	rs8054784	-0.022585	0.0108796	0.037907
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.011362	0.005149	0.0273409
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.011362	0.0039392	0.0039228
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	All - MR Egger	0.0251823	0.0891918	0.7889977
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	rs4561482	-0.023596	0.0102562	0.0214129
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	rs8057326	-0.001176	0.0112449	0.9167357
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	rs34497199	0.0028307	0.0091939	0.7581671
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	rs11150624	-0.01438	0.009839	0.143866
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	rs11865835	0.0058187	0.011399	0.6097313
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	rs8057029	-0.027224	0.010706	0.0109956
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	rs8054784	-0.022585	0.0108796	0.037907
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.011362	0.005149	0.0273409

SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.011362	0.0039392	0.0039228
SGLT2i	Coloc cancer	All - MR Egger	0.0251823	0.0891918	0.7889977
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs77023203	0.8168738	1.9276192	0.671731
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs2074312	0.4124432	2.3317649	0.8596024
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs116842927	1.5667386	6.7012854	0.8151428
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs7110898	-4.275915	9.956	0.6675731
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs4937311	-1.95573	7.0870952	0.7825815
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs5219	-0.779984	1.113751	0.4837265
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs4148631	4.1194266	6.390014	0.5191435
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs10766393	-0.235402	2.2849344	0.9179444
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs5210	0.673899	2.010303	0.7374572
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs10766395	0.6506692	2.0446892	0.750315
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs189603359	11.109202	6.7946304	0.1020496
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs10766392	-0.209357	2.2655781	0.926374
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs7110037	-2.057276	2.5941842	0.427758
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs77902362	-4.120455	5.4709091	0.4513555
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs35271178	-0.525876	1.2507504	0.6741579
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs147673442	-3.15671	4.4568135	0.4787661
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs2355016	-2.293147	2.7359972	0.4019524
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs2285676	0.6786415	1.9909415	0.7332055
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs739688	5.240006	4.9188204	0.2867414
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs79506407	10.221873	7.6780535	0.1830869
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs7112030	0.757933	2.0287792	0.7087089
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs117973841	0.6436921	6.0431457	0.9151729
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs12816749	1.7266095	5.4936331	0.7532986
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs74732083	-2.415785	4.8594843	0.6190989
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs10841887	-2.0209	2.7440265	0.4614432
SU	Connective tissue cancer	rs59406438	3.090444	4.2888795	0.4711732
SU	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.105301	0.3350989	0.75334
SU	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.105301	0.4951125	0.831576
SU	Connective tissue cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.046185	1.3026901	0.4298016

AGI	Connective tissue cancer	rs72681706	-6.833513	6.0735831	0.260538
AGI	Connective tissue cancer	rs72692396	-2.895749	5.4062675	0.5922156
AGI	Connective tissue cancer	rs174587	-7.616425	5.3633017	0.1555786
AGI	Connective tissue cancer	rs112968754	4.2615041	6.0315447	0.4798548
AGI	Connective tissue cancer	rs8037100	4.9812564	7.5845641	0.5113337
AGI	Connective tissue cancer	rs1659215	5.237573	7.9881081	0.5120357
AGI	Connective tissue cancer	rs73402785	5.9298734	6.1454008	0.3345805
AGI	Connective tissue cancer	rs34359922	3.9245932	5.9237288	0.5076375
AGI	Connective tissue cancer	rs111917515	2.492524	5.4904797	0.649849
AGI	Connective tissue cancer	rs113126535	3.321072	5.93288	0.5756336
AGI	Connective tissue cancer	rs112898001	1.3272869	5.9371713	0.8231033
AGI	Connective tissue cancer	rs4924660	1.0705057	6.8151149	0.8751832
AGI	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.7530545	1.3741367	0.5836781
AGI	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.7530545	1.7592968	0.6686199
AGI	Connective tissue cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.746648	6.5122165	0.6821173
DPP-4i	Connective tissue cancer	rs4233648	9.3066129	6.6432097	0.1612377
DPP-4i	Connective tissue cancer	rs2080714	7.3783766	5.4093831	0.1725688
DPP-4i	Connective tissue cancer	rs75850673	9.5385093	7.6591304	0.212993
DPP-4i	Connective tissue cancer	rs188581353	-0.816866	6.0566959	0.8927147
DPP-4i	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	5.9656106	2.4307414	0.0141185
DPP-4i	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	5.9656106	3.1443936	0.0577987
DPP-4i	Connective tissue cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.489568	7.2390026	0.7637052
Biguanides	Connective tissue cancer	rs150243609	5.9269857	5.4062286	0.2729364
Biguanides	Connective tissue cancer	rs17485664	-6.192677	6.0662454	0.3073294
Biguanides	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.5621043	6.0198504	0.9256056
Biguanides	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.5621043	4.0360336	0.8892356
GLP1RA	Connective tissue cancer	rs10305525	9.3631013	8.6665823	0.2799782
GLP1RA	Connective tissue cancer	rs228817	7.3136977	6.4392636	0.2560414
GLP1RA	Connective tissue cancer	rs12215108	6.3101036	6.068342	0.2984143
GLP1RA	Connective tissue cancer	rs28360624	-0.049614	6.4194611	0.9938335
GLP1RA	Connective tissue cancer	rs11963172	5.3401944	5.0954611	0.2946249

GLP1RA	Connective tissue cancer	rs880347	-0.853498	3.855823	0.8248177
GLP1RA	Connective tissue cancer	rs9462535	8.6142581	5.3036581	0.1043309
GLP1RA	Connective tissue cancer	rs142878626	-3.528594	6.6714516	0.5968682
GLP1RA	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.3502391	1.6419503	0.0413103
GLP1RA	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.3502391	1.9894907	0.0921878
GLP1RA	Connective tissue cancer	All - MR Egger	-10.32402	8.4808519	0.2691788
Insulin	Connective tissue cancer	rs4031066	-2.954288	5.7219315	0.6056383
TZD	Connective tissue cancer	rs4684833	-1.867149	4.196557	0.6563746
TZD	Connective tissue cancer	rs2881654	0.4096764	1.3637993	0.763877
TZD	Connective tissue cancer	rs1373641	1.2497387	3.7979009	0.74211
TZD	Connective tissue cancer	rs2120825	0.1351102	1.4652756	0.9265327
TZD	Connective tissue cancer	rs111327339	-0.449035	4.5400755	0.9212139
TZD	Connective tissue cancer	rs4135247	3.4044772	2.165126	0.1158543
TZD	Connective tissue cancer	rs1699348	-10.79848	6.464376	0.0948284
TZD	Connective tissue cancer	rs310752	2.2756692	6.1741692	0.7124415
TZD	Connective tissue cancer	rs76763697	-5.674911	6.57375	0.3879899
TZD	Connective tissue cancer	rs2920503	-5.263895	5.1588547	0.3075572
TZD	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.2931984	0.7433487	0.6932643
TZD	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.2931984	0.8158895	0.7193255
TZD	Connective tissue cancer	All - MR Egger	1.3413882	1.2996656	0.3322139
Amylin analog	Connective tissue cancer	rs4663804	3.401	8.2987941	0.681939
Amylin analog	Connective tissue cancer	rs11869741	6.7745682	5.4350418	0.2125952
Amylin analog	Connective tissue cancer	rs12603201	0.4872389	3.2504332	0.8808438
Amylin analog	Connective tissue cancer	rs11654396	5.2589338	6.7696397	0.4372526
Amylin analog	Connective tissue cancer	rs12941945	7.6237991	4.7254585	0.1066694
Amylin analog	Connective tissue cancer	rs1078523	-2.516369	4.9743313	0.6129474
Amylin analog	Connective tissue cancer	rs9905939	3.3954805	5.1961494	0.5134592
Amylin analog	Connective tissue cancer	rs59795094	-3.253015	6.1555538	0.5971743
Amylin analog	Connective tissue cancer	rs9892728	-2.835197	5.2417566	0.5885856
Amylin analog	Connective tissue cancer	rs73111954	-3.008668	4.0221106	0.4544408
Amylin analog	Connective tissue cancer	rs11772021	-2.31234	2.263354	0.30695

Amylin analog	Connective tissue cancer	rs4724382	-0.70735	7.2776847	0.9225721
Amylin analog	Connective tissue cancer	rs75390434	-3.367556	8.527265	0.6929047
Amylin analog	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.126662	1.0186834	0.9010469
Amylin analog	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.126662	1.2504707	0.9193191
Amylin analog	Connective tissue cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.985523	2.8115344	0.7325625
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	rs4561482	2.1128547	6.9045043	0.7595962
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	rs8057326	3.9582476	7.5588667	0.6005177
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	rs34497199	6.4097209	6.1941628	0.3007622
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	rs142133957	-1.109798	5.0242088	0.825178
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	rs11150624	4.9774918	6.6158115	0.4518328
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	rs11865835	-4.633226	7.6619739	0.5453757
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	rs8057029	7.6970086	7.2197069	0.2863735
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	rs12448775	3.6034295	6.5127885	0.5800681
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	rs8054784	10.200991	7.3363784	0.1643872
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.3773758	1.4496057	0.0198136
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.3773758	2.2065901	0.1258718
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.873286	5.3542602	0.8750477
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	rs4561482	2.1128547	6.9045043	0.7595962
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	rs8057326	3.9582476	7.5588667	0.6005177
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	rs34497199	6.4097209	6.1941628	0.3007622
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	rs142133957	-1.109798	5.0242088	0.825178
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	rs11150624	4.9774918	6.6158115	0.4518328
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	rs11865835	-4.633226	7.6619739	0.5453757
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	rs8057029	7.6970086	7.2197069	0.2863735
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	rs12448775	3.6034295	6.5127885	0.5800681
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	rs8054784	10.200991	7.3363784	0.1643872
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.3773758	1.4496057	0.0198136
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.3773758	2.2065901	0.1258718
SGLT2i	Connective tissue cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.873286	5.3542602	0.8750477
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs77023203	-0.341897	0.3694579	0.3547567
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs2074312	-0.282441	0.4486243	0.5289758

SU	Endometrial cancer	rs116842927	-2.4222	1.2480436	0.0522828
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs7110898	-2.305574	2.088366	0.2695893
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs4937311	0.2301111	1.3513492	0.864788
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs5219	-0.100659	0.2114038	0.6339707
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs4148631	1.2915385	1.2238042	0.2912665
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs10766393	-0.009447	0.4413491	0.9829219
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs5210	-0.37366	0.3867389	0.3339532
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs10766395	-0.38499	0.3943058	0.3288791
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs189603359	0.3670447	1.3231304	0.7814681
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs10766392	-0.007545	0.4376693	0.9862464
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs7110037	0.4269395	0.5036474	0.3966077
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs77902362	-0.356669	1.1596981	0.7584223
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs35271178	0.013977	0.238524	0.9532725
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs147673442	-0.769754	0.8396995	0.359299
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs2355016	0.4917361	0.5310806	0.3544895
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs2285676	-0.381117	0.3829463	0.3196277
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs739688	-1.055144	0.939994	0.2616497
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs79506407	-1.394944	1.4387616	0.3322734
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs7112030	-0.409953	0.3911216	0.294571
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs117973841	0.0077886	1.2877185	0.9951741
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs12816749	1.6658698	1.0780592	0.1222861
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs74732083	0.2944596	0.9534686	0.7574509
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs10841887	0.2607426	0.5331471	0.6247969
SU	Endometrial cancer	rs59406438	0.8379937	0.8294863	0.3123725
SU	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.117999	0.0819982	0.1501388
SU	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.117999	0.0951165	0.2147642
SU	Endometrial cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.228935	0.2491428	0.3672952
AGI	Endometrial cancer	rs72681706	-0.445426	1.1951265	0.7093701
AGI	Endometrial cancer	rs72692396	-0.541605	1.2015549	0.6521674
AGI	Endometrial cancer	rs174587	-2.078575	1.056581	0.0491526
AGI	Endometrial cancer	rs112968754	1.4368659	1.1560691	0.2139087

AGI	Endometrial cancer	rs8037100	1.7150872	1.4558154	0.2387592
AGI	Endometrial cancer	rs1659215	1.8911189	1.5302054	0.2165108
AGI	Endometrial cancer	rs73402785	1.4082869	1.1806878	0.2329601
AGI	Endometrial cancer	rs34359922	1.5076992	1.1221102	0.1790686
AGI	Endometrial cancer	rs111917515	0.8811993	1.0571439	0.4045256
AGI	Endometrial cancer	rs113126535	0.958164	1.147104	0.4035547
AGI	Endometrial cancer	rs112898001	1.3718526	1.1451235	0.2309188
AGI	Endometrial cancer	rs4924660	0.8356494	1.3090172	0.5232268
AGI	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.6393379	0.3545576	0.071357
AGI	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.6393379	0.3440476	0.0631288
AGI	Endometrial cancer	All - MR Egger	0.3122806	1.4432761	0.8330499
DPP-4i	Endometrial cancer	rs4233648	2.4017258	1.3366048	0.0723538
DPP-4i	Endometrial cancer	rs2080714	0.7063636	1.1032857	0.5220189
DPP-4i	Endometrial cancer	rs75850673	-1.781714	1.5105093	0.2381811
DPP-4i	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.6285977	1.0884119	0.563577
DPP-4i	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.6285977	0.7413384	0.396481
DPP-4i	Endometrial cancer	All - MR Egger	-11.00988	7.1982152	0.3686277
Biguanides	Endometrial cancer	rs150243609	0.42517	1.12542	0.7055882
Biguanides	Endometrial cancer	rs17485664	-1.204446	1.175658	0.3056054
Biguanides	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.354077	0.8140317	0.6635866
Biguanides	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.354077	0.8129724	0.6631753
GLP1RA	Endometrial cancer	rs10305525	-0.1132	1.6934114	0.9467033
GLP1RA	Endometrial cancer	rs228817	0.841	1.2548682	0.5027367
GLP1RA	Endometrial cancer	rs12215108	0.0456495	1.1629948	0.9686897
GLP1RA	Endometrial cancer	rs28360624	4.3610479	1.2116527	0.0003191
GLP1RA	Endometrial cancer	rs11963172	3.3386333	0.9843611	0.0006947
GLP1RA	Endometrial cancer	rs880347	1.4801818	0.7653014	0.0530989
GLP1RA	Endometrial cancer	rs9462535	0.2897426	1.016729	0.7756631
GLP1RA	Endometrial cancer	rs142878626	0.6408502	1.383818	0.6432906
GLP1RA	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.5206189	0.5414342	0.0049773
GLP1RA	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.5206189	0.3882727	8.99E-05

GLP1RA	Endometrial cancer	All - MR Egger	1.3495872	2.5822366	0.6199515
Insulin	Endometrial cancer	rs4031066	-1.744733	1.1439863	0.1272256
TZD	Endometrial cancer	rs4684833	0.4932325	0.8078026	0.5414741
TZD	Endometrial cancer	rs2881654	0.7983901	0.2613326	0.0022501
TZD	Endometrial cancer	rs1373641	0.1781595	0.7236712	0.8055364
TZD	Endometrial cancer	rs2120825	0.3388616	0.276946	0.2211161
TZD	Endometrial cancer	rs111327339	-0.08236	0.8945272	0.9266417
TZD	Endometrial cancer	rs4135247	1.3517212	0.4148928	0.001122
TZD	Endometrial cancer	rs1699348	1.922384	1.229024	0.1177812
TZD	Endometrial cancer	rs310752	0.0959115	1.1904308	0.9357849
TZD	Endometrial cancer	rs76763697	-0.313964	1.396067	0.8220635
TZD	Endometrial cancer	rs2920503	1.2592209	0.9807616	0.1991694
TZD	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.6676731	0.1444303	3.79E-06
TZD	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.6676731	0.1559802	1.86E-05
TZD	Endometrial cancer	All - MR Egger	0.55616	0.2479963	0.0551999
Amylin analog	Endometrial cancer	rs4663804	0.505249	1.5832941	0.7496412
Amylin analog	Endometrial cancer	rs11869741	-0.282306	1.0937409	0.7963214
Amylin analog	Endometrial cancer	rs12603201	0.0414895	0.6226437	0.9468728
Amylin analog	Endometrial cancer	rs11654396	-1.193603	1.2942353	0.3564004
Amylin analog	Endometrial cancer	rs12941945	0.0943786	0.9070786	0.9171322
Amylin analog	Endometrial cancer	rs1078523	-0.228836	0.96115	0.8118145
Amylin analog	Endometrial cancer	rs9905939	-0.93489	0.9910844	0.3455276
Amylin analog	Endometrial cancer	rs59795094	-0.453476	1.1876538	0.702591
Amylin analog	Endometrial cancer	rs9892728	-0.238645	1.0130197	0.81376
Amylin analog	Endometrial cancer	rs73111954	-0.108221	0.7859191	0.8904777
Amylin analog	Endometrial cancer	rs11772021	-0.791847	0.4401781	0.0720307
Amylin analog	Endometrial cancer	rs4724382	0.6566288	1.3942703	0.6376779
Amylin analog	Endometrial cancer	rs75390434	-0.595227	1.6563419	0.7193238
Amylin analog	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.37611	0.1283315	0.0033813
Amylin analog	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.37611	0.2420406	0.1202057
Amylin analog	Endometrial cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.70556	0.5458865	0.2226736

SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	rs4561482	2.6649744	1.3478547	0.0480194
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	rs8057326	2.1380286	1.4465619	0.1394059
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	rs34497199	0.9496822	1.1950465	0.4267984
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	rs142133957	-0.514418	1.234863	0.6769866
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	rs11150624	3.1969262	1.2782213	0.0123817
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	rs11865835	1.283713	1.5201043	0.3983956
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	rs8057029	2.7630345	1.3864655	0.0462766
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	rs12448775	-2.015609	1.530391	0.1878202
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	rs8054784	2.6234234	1.4078919	0.0624102
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.4810607	0.5621533	0.0084231
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.4810607	0.4526402	0.0010677
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.088701	1.2882584	0.1489762
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	rs4561482	2.6649744	1.3478547	0.0480194
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	rs8057326	2.1380286	1.4465619	0.1394059
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	rs34497199	0.9496822	1.1950465	0.4267984
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	rs142133957	-0.514418	1.234863	0.6769866
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	rs11150624	3.1969262	1.2782213	0.0123817
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	rs11865835	1.283713	1.5201043	0.3983956
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	rs8057029	2.7630345	1.3864655	0.0462766
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	rs12448775	-2.015609	1.530391	0.1878202
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	rs8054784	2.6234234	1.4078919	0.0624102
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.4810607	0.5621533	0.0084231
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.4810607	0.4526402	0.0010677
SGLT2i	Endometrial cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.088701	1.2882584	0.1489762
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs77023203	-0.971963	0.682243	0.1542562
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs2074312	-0.775676	0.8	0.3322486
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs116842927	-2.673203	2.3137255	0.2479401
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs7110898	0.7531915	3.587234	0.8336954
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs7940894	-2.236957	9.0130435	0.8039866
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs4937311	1.6587302	2.4206349	0.4931888
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs5219	0.1561238	0.3808883	0.6818837

SU	Esophageal cancer	rs4148631	2.8741259	2.2237762	0.1962004
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs10766393	-0.582677	0.7847769	0.4577996
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs5210	-0.933498	0.6871921	0.1743295
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs10766395	-0.924812	0.6992481	0.1859749
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs189603359	3.2723735	2.7684825	0.2372018
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs10766392	-0.554688	0.7786458	0.4762329
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs7110037	2.1894737	0.9078947	0.0158829
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs77902362	-3.551948	2.2922078	0.1212435
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs35271178	0.2914729	0.4263566	0.4942048
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs147673442	-1.274611	1.4559585	0.3813319
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs2355016	2.3833333	0.9555556	0.0126246
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs2285676	-0.929268	0.6804878	0.1720672
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs739688	1.2754491	1.6886228	0.4500575
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs79506407	-0.941606	2.5571776	0.7127086
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs7112030	-0.873449	0.6972705	0.2103262
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs117973841	-3.208609	2.4139073	0.183776
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs12816749	-2.16568	1.9289941	0.2615652
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs74732083	-1.426009	2.029148	0.4822038
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs10841887	1.15	0.9441176	0.2231979
SU	Esophageal cancer	rs59406438	-1.173362	1.5095137	0.4369754
SU	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.16761	0.2044461	0.4123163
SU	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.16761	0.1708578	0.3265976
SU	Esophageal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.218924	0.5467549	0.6922584
AGI	Esophageal cancer	rs72681706	0.9953162	2.0725995	0.6310667
AGI	Esophageal cancer	rs72692396	-1.40519	1.9560878	0.4725308
AGI	Esophageal cancer	rs174587	1.3798883	1.8659218	0.4595907
AGI	Esophageal cancer	rs112968754	-3.630081	2.1626016	0.0932356
AGI	Esophageal cancer	rs8037100	-0.435897	2.6923077	0.8713809
AGI	Esophageal cancer	rs1659215	-2.237838	2.8702703	0.4355904
AGI	Esophageal cancer	rs73402785	-3.594937	2.2194093	0.1052813
AGI	Esophageal cancer	rs34359922	-3.432203	2.1228814	0.1059287

AGI	Esophageal cancer	rs111917515	-1.815498	1.9741697	0.3577681
AGI	Esophageal cancer	rs113126535	-1.924	2.136	0.3677218
AGI	Esophageal cancer	rs112898001	-2.936255	2.1314741	0.1683361
AGI	Esophageal cancer	rs4924660	-3.58046	2.4022989	0.136111
AGI	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.76287	0.5287821	0.0008566
AGI	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.76287	0.6263982	0.0048884
AGI	Esophageal cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.243103	2.3030532	0.6011723
DPP-4i	Esophageal cancer	rs4233648	1.8145161	2.3790323	0.4456353
DPP-4i	Esophageal cancer	rs2080714	-0.032468	1.9155844	0.9864772
DPP-4i	Esophageal cancer	rs75850673	-0.546584	2.7826087	0.8442747
DPP-4i	Esophageal cancer	rs188581353	4.9411765	2.7559449	0.0729864
DPP-4i	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.2559163	1.129036	0.2659751
DPP-4i	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.2559163	1.1867681	0.2899342
DPP-4i	Esophageal cancer	All - MR Egger	4.8571426	3.2397336	0.2725664
Biguanides	Esophageal cancer	rs150243609	-1.248571	2.0885714	0.5499659
Biguanides	Esophageal cancer	rs17485664	2.8141264	2.1635688	0.1933655
Biguanides	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.7111437	2.0300855	0.7261118
Biguanides	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.7111437	1.5026572	0.6360295
GLP1RA	Esophageal cancer	rs10305525	3.0443038	3.1708861	0.337015
GLP1RA	Esophageal cancer	rs228817	-0.713178	2.2093023	0.7468414
GLP1RA	Esophageal cancer	rs12215108	-0.124352	2.0984456	0.9527456
GLP1RA	Esophageal cancer	rs28360624	0.742515	2.2155689	0.7375231
GLP1RA	Esophageal cancer	rs11963172	-1.477778	1.8055556	0.4130937
GLP1RA	Esophageal cancer	rs880347	0.4210526	1.354067	0.7558355
GLP1RA	Esophageal cancer	rs9462535	1.7935484	1.8193548	0.3242236
GLP1RA	Esophageal cancer	rs142878626	2.2096774	2.6520737	0.4047384
GLP1RA	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.4489346	0.4717551	0.3412865
GLP1RA	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.4489346	0.7015889	0.5222489
GLP1RA	Esophageal cancer	All - MR Egger	1.6386958	3.1693848	0.623628
Insulin	Esophageal cancer	rs4031066	2.0821918	2.1917808	0.3421123
Insulin	Esophageal cancer	rs144057856	4.1953385	1.9345172	0.0301074

Insulin	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.270004	1.048391	0.0018142
Insulin	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.270004	1.4503796	0.0241594
TZD	Esophageal cancer	rs4684833	0.3026316	1.4298246	0.8323751
TZD	Esophageal cancer	rs2881654	-0.210823	0.4498309	0.6393043
TZD	Esophageal cancer	rs1373641	2.472973	1.3063063	0.0583441
TZD	Esophageal cancer	rs2120825	-0.035996	0.4825647	0.9405393
TZD	Esophageal cancer	rs111327339	0.6586103	1.6329305	0.6867053
TZD	Esophageal cancer	rs4135247	0.7426273	0.7399464	0.3155603
TZD	Esophageal cancer	rs1699348	8.36	2.2	0.0001447
TZD	Esophageal cancer	rs310752	1.9846154	2.1461538	0.3551058
TZD	Esophageal cancer	rs76763697	-4.138393	2.6116071	0.1130537
TZD	Esophageal cancer	rs2920503	1.5813953	1.8139535	0.3833203
TZD	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.3014928	0.4309218	0.4841482
TZD	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.3014928	0.2733107	0.2699778
TZD	Esophageal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.798823	0.525094	0.1666792
Amylin analog	Esophageal cancer	rs4663804	-6.382353	3.1666667	0.0438544
Amylin analog	Esophageal cancer	rs11869741	-0.342618	2.4874652	0.8904475
Amylin analog	Esophageal cancer	rs12603201	1.291498	1.1295547	0.2528853
Amylin analog	Esophageal cancer	rs11654396	2.125	2.3308824	0.3619414
Amylin analog	Esophageal cancer	rs12941945	2.3886463	1.6026201	0.1361025
Amylin analog	Esophageal cancer	rs1078523	1.35	1.76875	0.4453138
Amylin analog	Esophageal cancer	rs9905939	0.8246753	1.8441558	0.6547429
Amylin analog	Esophageal cancer	rs59795094	1.3538462	2.1846154	0.5354433
Amylin analog	Esophageal cancer	rs9892728	1.4407895	1.8684211	0.4406318
Amylin analog	Esophageal cancer	rs73111954	0.3914894	1.412766	0.7816968
Amylin analog	Esophageal cancer	rs11772021	0.0993789	0.805383	0.9017956
Amylin analog	Esophageal cancer	rs4724382	0.4324324	2.4864865	0.8619338
Amylin analog	Esophageal cancer	rs75390434	1.7692308	3.008547	0.5564865
Amylin analog	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.7191385	0.3649961	0.0488082
Amylin analog	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.7191385	0.445298	0.1063193
Amylin analog	Esophageal cancer	All - MR Egger	0.558451	1.0123434	0.5922235

SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	rs4561482	-0.931624	2.4188034	0.7001196
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	rs8057326	-0.152381	2.6	0.9532643
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	rs34497199	-1.186047	2.1395349	0.5793408
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	rs142133957	2.1533442	2.1044046	0.3061869
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	rs11150624	1.6229508	2.2622951	0.4731327
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	rs11865835	-0.878261	2.6608696	0.7413506
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	rs8057029	-0.422414	2.4568966	0.8634927
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	rs12448775	-2.137821	2.5737179	0.4061798
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	rs8054784	0.5945946	2.5045045	0.8123387
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.037751	0.4799052	0.9372997
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.037751	0.7966175	0.9622027
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	All - MR Egger	0.929228	2.1920579	0.6843562
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	rs4561482	-0.931624	2.4188034	0.7001196
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	rs8057326	-0.152381	2.6	0.9532643
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	rs34497199	-1.186047	2.1395349	0.5793408
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	rs142133957	2.1533442	2.1044046	0.3061869
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	rs11150624	1.6229508	2.2622951	0.4731327
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	rs11865835	-0.878261	2.6608696	0.7413506
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	rs8057029	-0.422414	2.4568966	0.8634927
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	rs12448775	-2.137821	2.5737179	0.4061798
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	rs8054784	0.5945946	2.5045045	0.8123387
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.037751	0.4799052	0.9372997
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.037751	0.7966175	0.9622027
SGLT2i	Esophageal cancer	All - MR Egger	0.929228	2.1920579	0.6843562
SU	Eye cancer	rs77023203	0.5716192	2.5433645	0.8221744
SU	Eye cancer	rs2074312	2.6538703	3.0748649	0.3880906
SU	Eye cancer	rs116842927	3.5791285	9.0011329	0.6909023
SU	Eye cancer	rs7110898	8.2495745	13.059362	0.5275841
SU	Eye cancer	rs4937311	10.747857	9.3651587	0.251116
SU	Eye cancer	rs5219	0.4319515	1.4691117	0.7687409
SU	Eye cancer	rs4148631	2.6396294	8.4328671	0.7542679

SU	Eye cancer	rs10766393	1.3785722	3.0108924	0.6470518
SU	Eye cancer	rs5210	1.2797094	2.6527586	0.6295168
SU	Eye cancer	rs10766395	1.2303985	2.6977694	0.6483325
SU	Eye cancer	rs189603359	9.2347082	8.9747276	0.3034947
SU	Eye cancer	rs10766392	1.3885078	2.9855208	0.6418737
SU	Eye cancer	rs7110037	0.9224474	3.4270263	0.7878001
SU	Eye cancer	rs77902362	-7.553117	7.1776299	0.2926557
SU	Eye cancer	rs35271178	1.1300651	1.6508372	0.4936339
SU	Eye cancer	rs147673442	-6.260078	5.9146891	0.2898754
SU	Eye cancer	rs2355016	0.9556444	3.6136667	0.791431
SU	Eye cancer	rs2285676	1.2764268	2.6272195	0.6270756
SU	Eye cancer	rs739688	5.4576647	6.492515	0.4005672
SU	Eye cancer	rs79506407	-5.438151	10.241533	0.5954258
SU	Eye cancer	rs7112030	1.5323201	2.6777419	0.5671571
SU	Eye cancer	rs117973841	0.117703	7.9925497	0.9882503
SU	Eye cancer	rs12816749	-7.794438	7.2499408	0.2823283
SU	Eye cancer	rs74732083	-12.33437	6.3424888	0.0518085
SU	Eye cancer	rs10841887	5.655	3.6268824	0.1189513
SU	Eye cancer	rs59406438	10.77296	5.6206765	0.0552804
SU	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.1222621	0.542827	0.0386927
SU	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.1222621	0.6532674	0.0858109
SU	Eye cancer	All - MR Egger	0.1692985	1.7191471	0.9223705
AGI	Eye cancer	rs72681706	-4.837658	8.0534426	0.5480435
AGI	Eye cancer	rs72692396	-2.292695	7.1961677	0.7500303
AGI	Eye cancer	rs174587	-2.816508	7.0643575	0.6901196
AGI	Eye cancer	rs112968754	2.7568618	7.9606911	0.7291102
AGI	Eye cancer	rs8037100	3.1926051	10.019436	0.7499986
AGI	Eye cancer	rs1659215	2.9889784	10.551081	0.7769573
AGI	Eye cancer	rs73402785	1.0296203	8.105443	0.898918
AGI	Eye cancer	rs34359922	2.4773559	7.8165678	0.7512918
AGI	Eye cancer	rs111917515	2.7724096	7.2483764	0.7021002

AGI	Eye cancer	rs113126535	2.714004	7.83064	0.728901
AGI	Eye cancer	rs112898001	3.0843625	7.8335458	0.6937747
AGI	Eye cancer	rs4924660	1.9045575	9.0114368	0.832615
AGI	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.8313147	0.8227746	0.3123135
AGI	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.8313147	2.3247593	0.7206489
AGI	Eye cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.961184	8.6365384	0.7387968
DPP-4i	Eye cancer	rs4233648	3.9560726	8.7631452	0.6516693
DPP-4i	Eye cancer	rs2080714	8.6720779	7.1144156	0.2228652
DPP-4i	Eye cancer	rs75850673	11.672857	10.112484	0.2483765
DPP-4i	Eye cancer	rs188581353	-12.75081	7.7709512	0.1008326
DPP-4i	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.1287704	5.5416429	0.7008742
DPP-4i	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.1287704	4.1128403	0.6047434
DPP-4i	Eye cancer	All - MR Egger	-14.90636	9.3029862	0.2502554
Biguanides	Eye cancer	rs150243609	-0.123942	7.1345143	0.9861397
Biguanides	Eye cancer	rs17485664	-3.414743	8.025539	0.6704834
Biguanides	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.576593	1.6340719	0.3346325
Biguanides	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.576593	5.3321709	0.7674778
GLP1RA	Eye cancer	rs10305525	9.6229747	11.462089	0.4011618
GLP1RA	Eye cancer	rs228817	13.749147	8.4986047	0.1057031
GLP1RA	Eye cancer	rs12215108	2.8336062	7.9778238	0.7224507
GLP1RA	Eye cancer	rs28360624	0.7534671	8.4873653	0.9292606
GLP1RA	Eye cancer	rs11963172	4.4218667	6.7257222	0.5108877
GLP1RA	Eye cancer	rs880347	3.5850239	5.0900478	0.4812333
GLP1RA	Eye cancer	rs9462535	3.3699032	7.004	0.6304171
GLP1RA	Eye cancer	rs142878626	10.164608	8.7287788	0.244224
GLP1RA	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	5.2099249	1.4126094	0.0002259
GLP1RA	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	5.2099249	2.6237368	0.0470679
GLP1RA	Eye cancer	All - MR Egger	3.5676694	11.136495	0.7595598
Insulin	Eye cancer	rs4031066	-11.86699	7.5407534	0.1155537
TZD	Eye cancer	rs4684833	2.8710746	5.5293421	0.603591
TZD	Eye cancer	rs2881654	-0.043536	1.7911499	0.9806082

TZD	Eye cancer	rs1373641	2.2205225	5.0168468	0.6580456
TZD	Eye cancer	rs2120825	0.316297	1.9231046	0.8693595
TZD	Eye cancer	rs111327339	5.52929	5.9266918	0.3508473
TZD	Eye cancer	rs4135247	0.1897828	2.8565416	0.9470291
TZD	Eye cancer	rs1699348	0.3524392	8.53176	0.9670495
TZD	Eye cancer	rs310752	12.205077	8.151	0.1342966
TZD	Eye cancer	rs76763697	12.352411	8.6799554	0.1547083
TZD	Eye cancer	rs2920503	10.817849	6.8162209	0.1124958
TZD	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.1736854	0.943177	0.2133539
TZD	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.1736854	1.072644	0.273868
TZD	Eye cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.150892	1.7082544	0.5194739
Amylin analog	Eye cancer	rs4663804	1.345098	10.95049	0.9022382
Amylin analog	Eye cancer	rs11869741	3.3459889	7.1674652	0.6406214
Amylin analog	Eye cancer	rs12603201	-0.079349	4.2889069	0.9852391
Amylin analog	Eye cancer	rs11654396	-6.301125	8.9448529	0.4811579
Amylin analog	Eye cancer	rs12941945	-6.204585	6.2558515	0.3212926
Amylin analog	Eye cancer	rs1078523	2.8469438	6.56375	0.6644792
Amylin analog	Eye cancer	rs9905939	1.0372078	6.8596104	0.879814
Amylin analog	Eye cancer	rs59795094	1.2004077	8.1203846	0.8824797
Amylin analog	Eye cancer	rs9892728	2.8733947	6.9166447	0.6778258
Amylin analog	Eye cancer	rs73111954	2.8928851	5.2985106	0.5850791
Amylin analog	Eye cancer	rs11772021	-1.359642	2.9888613	0.6491791
Amylin analog	Eye cancer	rs4724382	-19.23982	9.6192793	0.0454861
Amylin analog	Eye cancer	rs75390434	-9.133846	11.24265	0.4165459
Amylin analog	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.894249	1.2598589	0.4778277
Amylin analog	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.894249	1.6506285	0.587982
Amylin analog	Eye cancer	All - MR Egger	1.0846845	3.7118536	0.775555
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	rs4561482	-12.22385	9.1138462	0.1798429
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	rs8057326	10.113238	9.9807619	0.3109297
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	rs34497199	5.6522946	8.1771318	0.4894198
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	rs142133957	1.9629038	6.5885318	0.7657586

SGLT2i	Eye cancer	rs11150624	2.4442213	8.735	0.7796162
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	rs11865835	-0.915591	10.093304	0.9277208
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	rs8057029	-7.908198	9.5347414	0.4068731
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	rs12448775	-3.646731	8.5731731	0.6705704
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	rs8054784	-6.019324	9.6893694	0.5344485
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.791235	2.2193487	0.7214536
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.791235	2.9080479	0.785557
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	All - MR Egger	0.747004	7.0297141	0.9183543
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	rs4561482	-12.22385	9.1138462	0.1798429
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	rs8057326	10.113238	9.9807619	0.3109297
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	rs34497199	5.6522946	8.1771318	0.4894198
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	rs142133957	1.9629038	6.5885318	0.7657586
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	rs11150624	2.4442213	8.735	0.7796162
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	rs11865835	-0.915591	10.093304	0.9277208
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	rs8057029	-7.908198	9.5347414	0.4068731
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	rs12448775	-3.646731	8.5731731	0.6705704
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	rs8054784	-6.019324	9.6893694	0.5344485
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.791235	2.2193487	0.7214536
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.791235	2.9080479	0.785557
SGLT2i	Eye cancer	All - MR Egger	0.747004	7.0297141	0.9183543
SU	Gastric cancer	rs77023203	-0.647196	0.3691589	0.0795738
SU	Gastric cancer	rs2074312	-0.456757	0.427027	0.2847903
SU	Gastric cancer	rs116842927	-0.183007	3.7254902	0.9608214
SU	Gastric cancer	rs7110898	-1.148936	0.906383	0.2049388
SU	Gastric cancer	rs4937311	-0.222222	1.3412698	0.8684084
SU	Gastric cancer	rs5219	-0.25572	0.218035	0.2408602
SU	Gastric cancer	rs4148631	1.0839161	1.4895105	0.4667975
SU	Gastric cancer	rs10766393	-0.527559	0.4173228	0.2061759
SU	Gastric cancer	rs5210	-0.416256	0.3866995	0.2817336
SU	Gastric cancer	rs10766395	-0.45614	0.3934837	0.2463601
SU	Gastric cancer	rs189603359	1.9883268	3.3871595	0.557191

SU	Gastric cancer	rs10766392	-0.526042	0.4140625	0.2039279
SU	Gastric cancer	rs7110037	-0.407895	0.5842105	0.4850533
SU	Gastric cancer	rs77902362	-1.402597	3.4025974	0.6801828
SU	Gastric cancer	rs35271178	-0.364341	0.2496124	0.1443925
SU	Gastric cancer	rs147673442	-1.028497	1.126943	0.36143
SU	Gastric cancer	rs2355016	-0.036111	0.6555556	0.9560709
SU	Gastric cancer	rs2285676	-0.421951	0.3829268	0.2705004
SU	Gastric cancer	rs739688	-1.479042	0.9700599	0.1273361
SU	Gastric cancer	rs79506407	0.459854	0.6618005	0.4871475
SU	Gastric cancer	rs7112030	-0.751861	0.3920596	0.0551463
SU	Gastric cancer	rs117973841	3.4437086	3.4271523	0.3149783
SU	Gastric cancer	rs12816749	0.2130178	1.5502959	0.890711
SU	Gastric cancer	rs74732083	1.5224215	2.7533632	0.5803103
SU	Gastric cancer	rs10841887	-0.632353	0.6529412	0.3328105
SU	Gastric cancer	rs59406438	1.627907	2.5010571	0.5151191
SU	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.411093	0.0636871	1.08E-10
SU	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.411093	0.0985563	3.03E-05
SU	Gastric cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.260201	0.2640336	0.3342176
AGI	Gastric cancer	rs72681706	-2.557377	3.1428571	0.4158106
AGI	Gastric cancer	rs72692396	-2.89022	2.9021956	0.3193116
AGI	Gastric cancer	rs174587	-0.709497	1.4301676	0.6198283
AGI	Gastric cancer	rs112968754	-0.426829	3.1869919	0.8934591
AGI	Gastric cancer	rs8037100	0.3589744	1.5487179	0.8167026
AGI	Gastric cancer	rs1659215	0.4162162	1.6324324	0.7987487
AGI	Gastric cancer	rs73402785	-1.219409	3.2700422	0.7092205
AGI	Gastric cancer	rs34359922	0.1864407	3.1737288	0.9531552
AGI	Gastric cancer	rs111917515	-0.398524	2.8523985	0.8888849
AGI	Gastric cancer	rs113126535	-0.48	3.092	0.8766326
AGI	Gastric cancer	rs112898001	-0.358566	3.0836653	0.9074314
AGI	Gastric cancer	rs4924660	1.362069	1.3390805	0.3090738
AGI	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.058868	0.3324603	0.8594547

AGI	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.058868	0.6105447	0.9231877
AGI	Gastric cancer	All - MR Egger	-4.090455	2.9191049	0.1913963
DPP-4i	Gastric cancer	rs4233648	-0.322581	1.4193548	0.8202117
DPP-4i	Gastric cancer	rs2080714	0.7077922	3.1233766	0.8207261
DPP-4i	Gastric cancer	rs75850673	1.9006211	1.1552795	0.0999366
DPP-4i	Gastric cancer	rs188581353	5.8010013	2.59199	0.0252178
DPP-4i	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.4695649	1.0104725	0.1458536
DPP-4i	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.4695649	0.8173187	0.072172
DPP-4i	Gastric cancer	All - MR Egger	7.255209	2.8665088	0.1270296
Biguanides	Gastric cancer	rs150243609	2.38	3.2071429	0.4580307
Biguanides	Gastric cancer	rs17485664	-5.442379	3.464684	0.1162255
Biguanides	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.229685	3.8995511	0.7525034
Biguanides	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.229685	2.3535794	0.6013401
GLP1RA	Gastric cancer	rs10305525	-1.170886	1.164557	0.3146875
GLP1RA	Gastric cancer	rs228817	1.5658915	1.4186047	0.269669
GLP1RA	Gastric cancer	rs12215108	-4.88601	3.3937824	0.1499538
GLP1RA	Gastric cancer	rs28360624	-11.22156	3.7065868	0.0024662
GLP1RA	Gastric cancer	rs11963172	-3.744444	2.9333333	0.2017735
GLP1RA	Gastric cancer	rs880347	-0.411483	0.8899522	0.6438192
GLP1RA	Gastric cancer	rs9462535	-0.954839	1.0451613	0.3609374
GLP1RA	Gastric cancer	rs142878626	2.6682028	1.4815668	0.0717134
GLP1RA	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.468061	0.7982135	0.5576167
GLP1RA	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.468061	0.4912526	0.3406965
GLP1RA	Gastric cancer	All - MR Egger	1.6412839	3.2163672	0.628071
Insulin	Gastric cancer	rs4031066	-2.294521	1.6506849	0.1645163
Insulin	Gastric cancer	rs144057856	14.486127	6.1598224	0.0186873
Insulin	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.17022	4.195526	0.7803055
Insulin	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.17022	1.5944285	0.4629833
TZD	Gastric cancer	rs4684833	-0.157895	0.8859649	0.8585519
TZD	Gastric cancer	rs2881654	-0.128523	0.4351747	0.7677366
TZD	Gastric cancer	rs1373641	0.4189189	0.8558559	0.6245064

TZD	Gastric cancer	rs2120825	-0.570304	0.4758155	0.2306907
TZD	Gastric cancer	rs111327339	3.2583082	2.8338369	0.2502317
TZD	Gastric cancer	rs4135247	-0.053619	0.4209115	0.8986329
TZD	Gastric cancer	rs1699348	0.624	1.592	0.6950879
TZD	Gastric cancer	rs310752	0.8538462	1.2615385	0.4985143
TZD	Gastric cancer	rs76763697	0.0982143	1.21875	0.9357711
TZD	Gastric cancer	rs2920503	0.994186	0.9302326	0.2851823
TZD	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.034646	0.1606635	0.8292672
TZD	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.034646	0.2184399	0.8739799
TZD	Gastric cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.508921	0.3813606	0.2187771
Amylin analog	Gastric cancer	rs4663804	-3.303922	1.7156863	0.0541401
Amylin analog	Gastric cancer	rs11869741	-3.228412	2.6406685	0.2214907
Amylin analog	Gastric cancer	rs12603201	-0.149798	0.6437247	0.815991
Amylin analog	Gastric cancer	rs11654396	-2.948529	1.5220588	0.0527211
Amylin analog	Gastric cancer	rs12941945	2.6157205	2.5414847	0.3033812
Amylin analog	Gastric cancer	rs1078523	0.5125	1.0125	0.6127353
Amylin analog	Gastric cancer	rs9905939	-0.090909	1.0324675	0.9298367
Amylin analog	Gastric cancer	rs59795094	0.6923077	1.2461538	0.5785147
Amylin analog	Gastric cancer	rs9892728	0.5789474	1.0657895	0.5869853
Amylin analog	Gastric cancer	rs73111954	-1.523404	0.8468085	0.0720195
Amylin analog	Gastric cancer	rs11772021	-0.846791	0.9730849	0.3841841
Amylin analog	Gastric cancer	rs4724382	-2.27027	1.7747748	0.2008309
Amylin analog	Gastric cancer	rs75390434	-0.547009	1.5299145	0.7206862
Amylin analog	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.535558	0.337083	0.1121052
Amylin analog	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.535558	0.3144089	0.0884969
Amylin analog	Gastric cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.282175	0.9973591	0.7824894
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	rs4561482	0.4102564	1.3418803	0.7598083
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	rs8057326	1.2666667	4.2380952	0.7650344
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	rs34497199	-0.44186	1.751938	0.8008769
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	rs142133957	2.3376835	3.0799347	0.44785
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	rs11150624	-0.114754	1.2868852	0.9289452

SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	rs11865835	1.7826087	1.6956522	0.2931291
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	rs8057029	0.3793103	1.362069	0.7806431
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	rs12448775	0.1826923	3.3237179	0.9561654
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	rs8054784	-0.234234	1.4144144	0.8684677
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.3379243	0.259839	0.1934248
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.3379243	0.5658402	0.5503686
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	All - MR Egger	1.5151822	3.0160362	0.6308187
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	rs4561482	0.4102564	1.3418803	0.7598083
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	rs8057326	1.2666667	4.2380952	0.7650344
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	rs34497199	-0.44186	1.751938	0.8008769
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	rs142133957	2.3376835	3.0799347	0.44785
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	rs11150624	-0.114754	1.2868852	0.9289452
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	rs11865835	1.7826087	1.6956522	0.2931291
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	rs8057029	0.3793103	1.362069	0.7806431
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	rs12448775	0.1826923	3.3237179	0.9561654
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	rs8054784	-0.234234	1.4144144	0.8684677
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.3379243	0.259839	0.1934248
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.3379243	0.5658402	0.5503686
SGLT2i	Gastric cancer	All - MR Egger	1.5151822	3.0160362	0.6308187
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs77023203	1.0728949	2.3465187	0.6475069
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs2074312	0.5519216	2.8383514	0.8458224
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs116842927	-2.615076	8.2138562	0.7502014
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs7110898	4.822383	12.169617	0.6919102
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4937311	-0.030666	8.6350794	0.9971664
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs5219	0.0202397	1.3556528	0.9880881
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4148631	1.2875804	7.7925175	0.8687607
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs10766393	1.2091129	2.78	0.6636113
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs5210	1.0310394	2.4477241	0.6735917
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs10766395	0.8115764	2.4895038	0.7444249
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs189603359	1.9330467	8.3511089	0.8169482
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs10766392	1.2202682	2.7566146	0.6580051

SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs7110037	1.1369605	3.1617368	0.7191463
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs77902362	1.143513	6.6725974	0.8639293
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs35271178	1.122276	1.5230667	0.4612119
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs147673442	-7.709171	5.4234197	0.1551832
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs2355016	1.1933972	3.3343611	0.7204116
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs2285676	1.0316585	2.4241439	0.6704165
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs739688	-0.869138	5.9967665	0.8847627
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs79506407	13.99146	9.333309	0.1338506
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs7112030	1.1842581	2.4700248	0.6316172
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs117973841	-6.094238	7.3649669	0.4079746
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs12816749	4.9539763	6.6842012	0.4586043
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs74732083	-4.149596	5.9204036	0.4833669
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs10841887	3.8673824	3.3396176	0.2468512
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs59406438	-3.806723	5.230296	0.4667227
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	0.7265752	0.3602797	0.0437271
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.7265752	0.6028731	0.2281309
SU	Hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	0.1633241	1.5866548	0.918869
AGI	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs72681706	-0.358867	7.4044496	0.9613446
AGI	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs72692396	3.4662874	6.586008	0.5986722
AGI	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs174587	-6.890615	6.5283799	0.291203
AGI	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs112968754	-15.16923	7.2990244	0.037686
AGI	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs8037100	-19.2601	9.1882051	0.0360665
AGI	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs1659215	-20.35714	9.6787568	0.0354413
AGI	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs73402785	-14.44886	7.4477637	0.0523764
AGI	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs34359922	-7.629237	7.1861441	0.2883903
AGI	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs111917515	-15.93402	6.6642804	0.0168044
AGI	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs113126535	-17.40696	7.20268	0.0156605
AGI	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs112898001	-17.14618	7.2044223	0.0173149
AGI	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4924660	-10.97724	8.2878736	0.1853389
AGI	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-11.00705	2.2182614	6.98E-07
AGI	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-11.00705	2.1365917	2.58E-07

AGI	Hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	4.0624006	7.9283433	0.6195044
DPP-4i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4233648	-0.601798	8.0866129	0.9406769
DPP-4i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs2080714	0.1981591	6.5737013	0.975952
DPP-4i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs75850673	6.8708696	9.2974534	0.4599036
DPP-4i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs188581353	-0.235966	7.2278974	0.9739564
DPP-4i	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	1.0174705	1.5244641	0.5044986
DPP-4i	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.0174705	3.8030005	0.7890502
DPP-4i	Hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	0.2523041	8.6488144	0.9793766
Biguanides	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs150243609	6.9505857	6.6209143	0.2938136
Biguanides	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs17485664	2.8118773	7.3924164	0.7036684
Biguanides	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	5.108399	2.0568475	0.013006
Biguanides	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	5.108399	4.9319746	0.3003087
GLP1RA	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs10305525	7.9273418	10.564873	0.4530446
GLP1RA	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs228817	0.3482767	7.8426357	0.9645791
GLP1RA	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs12215108	11.359016	7.3681347	0.123161
GLP1RA	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs28360624	-0.924024	7.8242515	0.9059905
GLP1RA	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs11963172	1.1940444	6.2149444	0.8476445
GLP1RA	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs880347	-4.579565	4.6913062	0.3289747
GLP1RA	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs9462535	-2.315697	6.4578065	0.7199028
GLP1RA	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs142878626	3.4470737	8.1288018	0.6715244
GLP1RA	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	0.5298459	1.8777434	0.7778119
GLP1RA	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.5298459	2.4224241	0.8268639
GLP1RA	Hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	1.7507826	10.329623	0.8709802
Insulin	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4031066	-5.864973	6.9596575	0.3993907
TZD	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4684833	6.3209649	5.1167105	0.2166976
TZD	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs2881654	-3.570564	1.6600902	0.03149
TZD	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs1373641	2.3863514	4.6227928	0.6057048
TZD	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs2120825	-3.95973	1.7820697	0.0262844
TZD	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs111327339	-1.544275	5.4964199	0.778741
TZD	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4135247	-0.871145	2.6363217	0.7410679
TZD	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs1699348	5.773144	7.869208	0.4631699

TZD	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs310752	9.2740769	7.5209231	0.2175371
TZD	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs76763697	-1.213661	7.9857589	0.8792042
TZD	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs2920503	5.727936	6.2828488	0.3619382
TZD	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-1.954115	1.0765697	0.0695038
TZD	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.954115	0.9928008	0.0490352
TZD	Hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	-5.743074	1.581468	0.0066707
Amylin analog	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4663804	1.5550686	10.113235	0.8777945
Amylin analog	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs11869741	-1.530657	6.6231755	0.8172322
Amylin analog	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs12603201	2.9582955	3.9587449	0.4548939
Amylin analog	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs11654396	6.5605735	8.2480882	0.4263777
Amylin analog	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs12941945	-1.956533	5.7575109	0.7339901
Amylin analog	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs1078523	-3.565713	6.0550125	0.5559377
Amylin analog	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs9905939	-2.661857	6.3235909	0.6737983
Amylin analog	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs59795094	-5.1366	7.4922	0.4929698
Amylin analog	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs9892728	-3.340151	6.3805789	0.6006353
Amylin analog	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs73111954	-0.550621	4.8965106	0.9104652
Amylin analog	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs11772021	2.3462319	2.756853	0.3947391
Amylin analog	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4724382	5.4136036	8.8652072	0.5414265
Amylin analog	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs75390434	-6.079427	10.375043	0.557898
Amylin analog	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	0.3878872	0.8836032	0.6606735
Amylin analog	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.3878872	1.5228489	0.7989459
Amylin analog	Hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	2.6689458	3.4245118	0.4522066
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4561482	-16.62197	8.4097949	0.0480981
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs8057326	-13.39457	9.2082762	0.1457736
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs34497199	-12.18752	7.5504651	0.1064967
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs142133957	-0.430086	6.1355139	0.9441158
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs11150624	-9.459754	8.0622377	0.2406591
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs11865835	-8.247861	9.3142609	0.3758822
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs8057029	-15.58259	8.7959483	0.0764669
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs12448775	2.0693974	7.9508654	0.794653
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs8054784	-4.686333	8.9416036	0.600206

SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-7.858784	2.2783827	0.0005621
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-7.858784	2.689954	0.0034832
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	3.8920408	6.5373901	0.570347
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4561482	-16.62197	8.4097949	0.0480981
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs8057326	-13.39457	9.2082762	0.1457736
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs34497199	-12.18752	7.5504651	0.1064967
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs142133957	-0.430086	6.1355139	0.9441158
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs11150624	-9.459754	8.0622377	0.2406591
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs11865835	-8.247861	9.3142609	0.3758822
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs8057029	-15.58259	8.7959483	0.0764669
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs12448775	2.0693974	7.9508654	0.794653
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs8054784	-4.686333	8.9416036	0.600206
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-7.858784	2.2783827	0.0005621
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-7.858784	2.689954	0.0034832
SGLT2i	Hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	3.8920408	6.5373901	0.570347
SU	Kidney cancer	rs77023203	0.3754715	0.9563224	0.6946
SU	Kidney cancer	rs2074312	0.1670502	1.1459556	0.8841
SU	Kidney cancer	rs116842927	0.8942477	3.3760169	0.7911
SU	Kidney cancer	rs7110898	3.8851982	4.752101	0.4136
SU	Kidney cancer	rs4937311	1.3456699	3.4607951	0.6974
SU	Kidney cancer	rs5219	-0.364238	0.5488227	0.5069
SU	Kidney cancer	rs4148631	-1.13067	3.1158863	0.7167
SU	Kidney cancer	rs10766393	-0.086757	1.1117717	0.9378
SU	Kidney cancer	rs5210	0.1473417	0.9867415	0.8813
SU	Kidney cancer	rs10766395	-0.00752	1.0169453	0.9941
SU	Kidney cancer	rs189603359	6.000567	2.8413901	0.0347
SU	Kidney cancer	rs10766392	-0.13577	1.1151883	0.9031
SU	Kidney cancer	rs7110037	0.6369655	1.2809297	0.619
SU	Kidney cancer	rs77902362	0.0942926	2.7859361	0.973
SU	Kidney cancer	rs35271178	0.2399933	0.6157165	0.6967
SU	Kidney cancer	rs147673442	-4.702639	1.9813031	0.01762

SU	Kidney cancer	rs2355016	0.6479396	1.3470027	0.6305
SU	Kidney cancer	rs2285676	0.1580236	0.9877956	0.8729
SU	Kidney cancer	rs739688	3.4571887	2.7500249	0.2087
SU	Kidney cancer	rs79506407	4.7943054	4.2393967	0.2581
SU	Kidney cancer	rs7112030	-0.014893	1.0423101	0.9886
SU	Kidney cancer	rs117973841	-2.796992	2.8529755	0.3269
SU	Kidney cancer	rs12816749	-2.360566	2.7247355	0.3863
SU	Kidney cancer	rs74732083	3.1405154	2.2217539	0.1575
SU	Kidney cancer	rs10841887	-0.369964	1.3471335	0.7836
SU	Kidney cancer	rs59406438	1.3351547	2.053144	0.5155
SU	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.0854801	0.2148652	0.6907546
SU	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0854801	0.2440624	0.7261597
SU	Kidney cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.056252	0.6481326	0.9315582
AGI	Kidney cancer	rs72681706	-2.336179	3.0366577	0.4417
AGI	Kidney cancer	rs72692396	0.3138315	2.624009	0.9048
AGI	Kidney cancer	rs174587	3.096911	2.6762636	0.2472
AGI	Kidney cancer	rs112968754	-1.765958	3.0152983	0.5581
AGI	Kidney cancer	rs8037100	-1.535583	3.7640156	0.6833
AGI	Kidney cancer	rs1659215	-2.054781	3.9793237	0.6056
AGI	Kidney cancer	rs73402785	-1.824938	3.0544925	0.5502
AGI	Kidney cancer	rs34359922	-0.614171	2.9323602	0.8341
AGI	Kidney cancer	rs111917515	-1.34422	2.7406662	0.6238
AGI	Kidney cancer	rs113126535	-1.24444	2.9534632	0.6735
AGI	Kidney cancer	rs112898001	-2.065066	2.9743536	0.4875
AGI	Kidney cancer	rs4924660	1.3349498	3.3131091	0.687
AGI	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.692026	0.4963139	0.1632178
AGI	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.692026	0.8729025	0.427902
AGI	Kidney cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.965698	3.2041259	0.376457
DPP-4i	Kidney cancer	rs4233648	-0.426291	6.9370776	0.951
DPP-4i	Kidney cancer	rs2080714	-0.469224	2.6470138	0.8593
DPP-4i	Kidney cancer	rs75850673	6.9946674	4.0266411	0.08237

DPP-4i	Kidney cancer	rs188581353	-5.266751	3.5642615	0.1395
DPP-4i	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.19415	2.3939271	0.9353614
DPP-4i	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.19415	1.814012	0.9147666
DPP-4i	Kidney cancer	All - MR Egger	-6.175861	5.3220063	0.3656644
Biguanides	Kidney cancer	rs150243609	0.589125	2.8887101	0.8384
Biguanides	Kidney cancer	rs17485664	-1.001264	3.0111794	0.7395
Biguanides	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.173071	0.7945095	0.827559
Biguanides	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.173071	2.0845781	0.9338322
GLP1RA	Kidney cancer	rs10305525	-4.423173	4.1473923	0.2862
GLP1RA	Kidney cancer	rs228817	-0.716479	3.1416329	0.8196
GLP1RA	Kidney cancer	rs12215108	0.8938007	2.9461388	0.7616
GLP1RA	Kidney cancer	rs28360624	-0.991742	3.1594595	0.7536
GLP1RA	Kidney cancer	rs11963172	-0.027771	2.3323576	0.9905
GLP1RA	Kidney cancer	rs880347	0.2590733	1.8940056	0.8912
GLP1RA	Kidney cancer	rs9462535	-0.877871	2.5915213	0.7348
GLP1RA	Kidney cancer	rs142878626	-0.62357	3.2533346	0.848
GLP1RA	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.415085	0.4246199	0.3282997
GLP1RA	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.415085	0.9618874	0.6660819
GLP1RA	Kidney cancer	All - MR Egger	0.9877274	4.1385893	0.8193096
Insulin	Kidney cancer	rs4031066	3.7732854	2.8285248	0.1822
Insulin	Kidney cancer	rs144057856	1.4655581	2.19172	0.5037
Insulin	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.3313281	1.1173197	0.0369301
Insulin	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.3313281	1.7324832	0.1784132
TZD	Kidney cancer	rs4684833	-1.040199	2.0393112	0.61
TZD	Kidney cancer	rs2881654	-0.170391	0.6597427	0.7962
TZD	Kidney cancer	rs1373641	-0.229146	1.8609286	0.902
TZD	Kidney cancer	rs2120825	-0.123283	0.7050903	0.8612
TZD	Kidney cancer	rs111327339	-2.213318	2.2436632	0.3239
TZD	Kidney cancer	rs4135247	-0.14786	1.0479949	0.8878
TZD	Kidney cancer	rs1699348	-2.510998	3.1536199	0.4259
TZD	Kidney cancer	rs310752	2.4064838	3.0022017	0.4228

TZD	Kidney cancer	rs76763697	0.4802525	3.3796493	0.887
TZD	Kidney cancer	rs2920503	1.7888682	2.5069666	0.4755
TZD	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.185598	0.2262444	0.4120198
TZD	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.185598	0.3951162	0.6385472
TZD	Kidney cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.320251	0.6289377	0.624361
Amylin analog	Kidney cancer	rs4663804	8.6374949	8.117463	0.2873
Amylin analog	Kidney cancer	rs11869741	-0.40403	6.4690773	0.9502
Amylin analog	Kidney cancer	rs12603201	3.5223904	1.5867806	0.02643
Amylin analog	Kidney cancer	rs11654396	-8.16868	3.4216415	0.01697
Amylin analog	Kidney cancer	rs12941945	-4.014885	2.3748784	0.09092
Amylin analog	Kidney cancer	rs1078523	-0.577661	2.4647715	0.8147
Amylin analog	Kidney cancer	rs9905939	2.1186041	2.5648736	0.4088
Amylin analog	Kidney cancer	rs59795094	-0.486148	3.0078509	0.8716
Amylin analog	Kidney cancer	rs9892728	-0.860871	2.5848457	0.7391
Amylin analog	Kidney cancer	rs73111954	-0.767505	2.0403828	0.7068
Amylin analog	Kidney cancer	rs11772021	-1.182186	1.0961149	0.2808
Amylin analog	Kidney cancer	rs4724382	-0.215957	3.6330691	0.9526
Amylin analog	Kidney cancer	rs75390434	-0.196808	4.1417066	0.9621
Amylin analog	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.419344	0.7413044	0.5716085
Amylin analog	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.419344	0.6347011	0.5088076
Amylin analog	Kidney cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.597797	1.7671655	0.7415206
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	rs4561482	4.9963735	3.3676074	0.1379
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	rs8057326	0.8627471	3.6994769	0.8156
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	rs34497199	3.1744175	3.0388338	0.2962
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	rs142133957	-0.217145	2.6141683	0.9338
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	rs11150624	0.9646708	3.2385291	0.7658
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	rs11865835	4.1431873	3.8097013	0.2768
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	rs8057029	5.2668189	3.490282	0.1313
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	rs12448775	0.4974299	3.1877969	0.876
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	rs8054784	4.7380586	3.5647406	0.1838
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.4391592	0.7423173	0.0010167

SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.4391592	1.0915461	0.0254442
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.026894	2.7361008	0.7185416
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	rs4561482	4.9963735	3.3676074	0.1379
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	rs8057326	0.8627471	3.6994769	0.8156
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	rs34497199	3.1744175	3.0388338	0.2962
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	rs142133957	-0.217145	2.6141683	0.9338
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	rs11150624	0.9646708	3.2385291	0.7658
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	rs11865835	4.1431873	3.8097013	0.2768
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	rs8057029	5.2668189	3.490282	0.1313
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	rs12448775	0.4974299	3.1877969	0.876
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	rs8054784	4.7380586	3.5647406	0.1838
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.4391592	0.7423173	0.0010167
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.4391592	1.0915461	0.0254442
SGLT2i	Kidney cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.026894	2.7361008	0.7185416
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs77023203	-0.167957	2.0999276	0.9362513
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs2074312	-1.3171	2.5393703	0.6039896
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs116842927	-5.650174	7.4252505	0.4466926
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs7110898	0.9355277	10.907362	0.931649
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs4937311	-12.10413	7.730246	0.1173922
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs5219	-0.365841	1.2134293	0.7630381
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs4148631	-2.75549	6.9763497	0.6928607
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs10766393	-2.675748	2.4862441	0.2818284
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs5210	0.2112357	2.1904409	0.9231749
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs10766395	0.1242464	2.2276466	0.9555213
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs189603359	3.6077043	7.5195136	0.6313846
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs10766392	-2.713594	2.4648464	0.2709323
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs7110037	0.0833866	2.8336053	0.9765235
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs77902362	-9.85474	5.9119156	0.0955286
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs35271178	0.004679	1.3640884	0.9972631
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs147673442	-1.380339	4.9198187	0.7790424
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs2355016	-0.172037	2.98725	0.9540748

SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs2285676	0.2155366	2.1694	0.9208579
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs739688	-2.212078	5.3567605	0.6796428
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs79506407	1.425708	8.4282968	0.8656729
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs7112030	-0.060233	2.2108139	0.9782646
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs117973841	3.0240265	6.6360596	0.6486085
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs12816749	10.141065	5.9702959	0.0893971
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs74732083	-4.396256	5.1893049	0.3968969
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs10841887	-0.205171	3.0049706	0.9455648
SU	Laryngeal cancer	rs59406438	7.9348626	4.6673573	0.0891166
SU	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.41613	0.4229667	0.3251964
SU	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.41613	0.5396876	0.4406734
SU	Laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	0.4120452	1.4198246	0.7741495
AGI	Laryngeal cancer	rs72681706	-5.14623	6.605363	0.4359216
AGI	Laryngeal cancer	rs72692396	-8.320599	5.8779242	0.1569022
AGI	Laryngeal cancer	rs174587	11.419777	5.8091061	0.049317
AGI	Laryngeal cancer	rs112968754	3.4787439	6.5543089	0.5955873
AGI	Laryngeal cancer	rs8037100	1.6603641	8.2530256	0.8405559
AGI	Laryngeal cancer	rs1659215	0.6582108	8.6938378	0.9396498
AGI	Laryngeal cancer	rs73402785	2.4517722	6.6660759	0.7130236
AGI	Laryngeal cancer	rs34359922	5.5332627	6.444661	0.3905718
AGI	Laryngeal cancer	rs111917515	1.4861587	5.9684871	0.8033601
AGI	Laryngeal cancer	rs113126535	1.354568	6.45036	0.8336686
AGI	Laryngeal cancer	rs112898001	2.7240797	6.4483267	0.6726984
AGI	Laryngeal cancer	rs4924660	4.9251207	7.4152874	0.5065721
AGI	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.8692665	1.5728279	0.2346464
AGI	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.8692665	1.9117645	0.328188
AGI	Laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	-14.16276	7.0786188	0.0732927
DPP-4i	Laryngeal cancer	rs4233648	-1.7805	7.2358145	0.8056299
DPP-4i	Laryngeal cancer	rs2080714	-0.200455	5.8614675	0.9727187
DPP-4i	Laryngeal cancer	rs75850673	4.9904286	8.324472	0.5488469
DPP-4i	Laryngeal cancer	rs188581353	-3.031727	6.3094994	0.6308705

DPP-4i	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.501179	1.5468643	0.7459406
DPP-4i	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.501179	3.3756809	0.8819739
DPP-4i	Laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.85897	7.560599	0.7416887
Biguanides	Laryngeal cancer	rs150243609	-2.126157	5.9206143	0.7195121
Biguanides	Laryngeal cancer	rs17485664	2.5129219	6.6198141	0.7042378
Biguanides	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.064471	2.3051628	0.9776876
Biguanides	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.064471	4.4130738	0.9883441
GLP1RA	Laryngeal cancer	rs10305525	-8.410253	9.4955063	0.3757745
GLP1RA	Laryngeal cancer	rs228817	10.831318	7.0019147	0.1218854
GLP1RA	Laryngeal cancer	rs12215108	1.0776218	6.5595855	0.8695092
GLP1RA	Laryngeal cancer	rs28360624	-2.788904	7.0120359	0.6908285
GLP1RA	Laryngeal cancer	rs11963172	5.8237778	5.5546556	0.2944314
GLP1RA	Laryngeal cancer	rs880347	1.7918612	4.2006794	0.6696965
GLP1RA	Laryngeal cancer	rs9462535	-9.204	5.784929	0.1116027
GLP1RA	Laryngeal cancer	rs142878626	0.702159	7.253318	0.9228811
GLP1RA	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.5848148	2.1837816	0.7888539
GLP1RA	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.5848148	2.1665674	0.7872165
GLP1RA	Laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	0.2029905	10.041319	0.9845269
Insulin	Laryngeal cancer	rs4031066	0.5719459	6.2201986	0.9267379
TZD	Laryngeal cancer	rs4684833	2.5235	4.5655702	0.5804524
TZD	Laryngeal cancer	rs2881654	-0.336085	1.4785344	0.8201833
TZD	Laryngeal cancer	rs1373641	4.1414459	4.1419144	0.3173652
TZD	Laryngeal cancer	rs2120825	0.7208133	1.5881665	0.649926
TZD	Laryngeal cancer	rs111327339	-1.424893	4.8669033	0.7696965
TZD	Laryngeal cancer	rs4135247	3.382252	2.3560724	0.1511314
TZD	Laryngeal cancer	rs1699348	7.626856	7.039248	0.2785972
TZD	Laryngeal cancer	rs310752	0.7303115	6.7257462	0.9135321
TZD	Laryngeal cancer	rs76763697	-4.276058	7.1875893	0.5518953
TZD	Laryngeal cancer	rs2920503	8.9361047	5.6205756	0.1118593
TZD	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.1081453	0.7354135	0.1318535
TZD	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.1081453	0.885324	0.2106853

TZD	Laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.721998	1.4100051	0.6224462
Amylin analog	Laryngeal cancer	rs4663804	-0.486332	9.039951	0.957096
Amylin analog	Laryngeal cancer	rs11869741	-6.627632	5.9274652	0.2635147
Amylin analog	Laryngeal cancer	rs12603201	-5.054737	3.5408866	0.153426
Amylin analog	Laryngeal cancer	rs11654396	9.4795588	7.4005882	0.2002219
Amylin analog	Laryngeal cancer	rs12941945	-0.18582	5.1816594	0.9713932
Amylin analog	Laryngeal cancer	rs1078523	5.5003438	5.4202	0.3102078
Amylin analog	Laryngeal cancer	rs9905939	2.0376169	5.6666104	0.719159
Amylin analog	Laryngeal cancer	rs59795094	6.6465769	6.7062923	0.3216389
Amylin analog	Laryngeal cancer	rs9892728	5.5635132	5.7109276	0.3299636
Amylin analog	Laryngeal cancer	rs73111954	1.2926723	4.3721277	0.7674882
Amylin analog	Laryngeal cancer	rs11772021	-0.418135	2.4574534	0.8648925
Amylin analog	Laryngeal cancer	rs4724382	5.8311351	7.9247838	0.4618463
Amylin analog	Laryngeal cancer	rs75390434	-0.927872	9.2464957	0.9200677
Amylin analog	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.4037589	1.1527164	0.7261381
Amylin analog	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.4037589	1.3613851	0.7667875
Amylin analog	Laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	-4.247899	3.0566727	0.1921003
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	rs4561482	4.125812	7.5198205	0.58324
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	rs8057326	-1.554371	8.2446762	0.850461
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	rs34497199	-3.792961	6.7472791	0.574016
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	rs142133957	-0.691013	5.3809299	0.8978175
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	rs11150624	3.2231475	7.2178443	0.6551981
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	rs11865835	-4.287609	8.3209478	0.6063582
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	rs8057029	8.5413103	7.8715259	0.277882
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	rs12448775	8.1212179	7.1629167	0.2568841
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	rs8054784	8.4309369	7.9971171	0.2917698
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.1335848	1.6784659	0.2036747
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.1335848	2.3986831	0.3737442
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	1.5725339	5.7746584	0.7932364
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	rs4561482	4.125812	7.5198205	0.58324
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	rs8057326	-1.554371	8.2446762	0.850461

SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	rs34497199	-3.792961	6.7472791	0.574016
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	rs142133957	-0.691013	5.3809299	0.8978175
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	rs11150624	3.2231475	7.2178443	0.6551981
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	rs11865835	-4.287609	8.3209478	0.6063582
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	rs8057029	8.5413103	7.8715259	0.277882
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	rs12448775	8.1212179	7.1629167	0.2568841
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	rs8054784	8.4309369	7.9971171	0.2917698
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.1335848	1.6784659	0.2036747
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.1335848	2.3986831	0.3737442
SGLT2i	Laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	1.5725339	5.7746584	0.7932364
SU	Liver cancer	rs77023203	-1.154194	1.6968142	0.49637
SU	Liver cancer	rs2074312	-2.368028	2.0985402	0.259144
SU	Liver cancer	rs116842927	2.2189546	4.7804503	0.642524
SU	Liver cancer	rs4937311	-1.948116	6.0566859	0.74772
SU	Liver cancer	rs5219	0.6451232	0.9668355	0.504611
SU	Liver cancer	rs4148631	7.2777942	5.7716772	0.207327
SU	Liver cancer	rs10766393	-1.491952	2.0791844	0.473025
SU	Liver cancer	rs5210	-0.881571	1.7868131	0.621747
SU	Liver cancer	rs10766395	-0.456716	1.8187954	0.80173
SU	Liver cancer	rs10766392	-1.427593	2.0681736	0.490026
SU	Liver cancer	rs7110037	5.4629307	2.3281877	0.0189542
SU	Liver cancer	rs77902362	0.013309	5.0303181	0.997889
SU	Liver cancer	rs35271178	0.802437	1.0876248	0.460643
SU	Liver cancer	rs147673442	-2.114426	3.3941704	0.533312
SU	Liver cancer	rs2355016	4.7071406	2.4406164	0.053772
SU	Liver cancer	rs2285676	-0.884498	1.7693477	0.617145
SU	Liver cancer	rs739688	4.3693141	4.3731122	0.317731
SU	Liver cancer	rs79506407	-3.030657	6.5805676	0.645124
SU	Liver cancer	rs7112030	-1.113829	1.8001543	0.536087
SU	Liver cancer	rs117973841	-6.115412	5.50345	0.266484
SU	Liver cancer	rs12816749	2.2945744	5.0817823	0.651608

SU	Liver cancer	rs74732083	-0.293891	5.8360147	0.959837
SU	Liver cancer	rs10841887	-4.858599	2.3787819	0.0411046
SU	Liver cancer	rs59406438	-5.213942	4.4618528	0.242581
SU	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.095652	0.4517489	0.8323116
SU	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.095652	0.4393181	0.8276403
SU	Liver cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.102569	1.2082485	0.9331164
AGI	Liver cancer	rs72681706	-0.318218	4.8748409	0.947953
AGI	Liver cancer	rs72692396	0.569638	5.3608538	0.915377
AGI	Liver cancer	rs174587	-7.038014	5.0577313	0.164063
AGI	Liver cancer	rs112968754	-1.134046	5.3223369	0.83127
AGI	Liver cancer	rs8037100	-3.474692	6.485303	0.592111
AGI	Liver cancer	rs1659215	-4.064513	6.9626824	0.559384
AGI	Liver cancer	rs73402785	1.013469	5.4519066	0.852529
AGI	Liver cancer	rs34359922	0.6496553	5.2247189	0.901044
AGI	Liver cancer	rs111917515	-2.822277	4.8074961	0.557165
AGI	Liver cancer	rs113126535	-2.970153	5.2224393	0.56954
AGI	Liver cancer	rs112898001	-1.088521	5.2533585	0.83585
AGI	Liver cancer	rs4924660	-7.481831	6.1095861	0.220724
AGI	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.172099	0.8107526	0.0073817
AGI	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.172099	1.563821	0.1648421
AGI	Liver cancer	All - MR Egger	4.9963297	5.8994249	0.4168485
DPP-4i	Liver cancer	rs4233648	-2.870987	5.9957919	0.632057
DPP-4i	Liver cancer	rs2080714	-6.835683	4.8452924	0.158307
DPP-4i	Liver cancer	rs75850673	-6.446166	6.6132261	0.32969
DPP-4i	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	-5.557861	1.2433782	7.82E-06
DPP-4i	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-5.557861	3.2742561	0.0896131
DPP-4i	Liver cancer	All - MR Egger	-20.8239	29.413586	0.6078078
Biguanides	Liver cancer	rs17485664	-3.318896	6.3847726	0.603193
GLP1RA	Liver cancer	rs10305525	1.6563594	7.7335531	0.830408
GLP1RA	Liver cancer	rs228817	-1.77767	5.7663564	0.757867
GLP1RA	Liver cancer	rs12215108	2.4814362	5.3976431	0.645713

GLP1RA	Liver cancer	rs11963172	-2.691199	4.6393972	0.561864
GLP1RA	Liver cancer	rs880347	3.5270353	3.4690284	0.309286
GLP1RA	Liver cancer	rs9462535	2.6506039	4.6334688	0.567284
GLP1RA	Liver cancer	rs142878626	3.2561002	6.242371	0.60194
GLP1RA	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.5357159	0.9872722	0.1198237
GLP1RA	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.5357159	1.880058	0.414017
GLP1RA	Liver cancer	All - MR Egger	6.3340903	7.7954378	0.4534171
TZD	Liver cancer	rs4684833	-5.674849	3.828617	0.138282
TZD	Liver cancer	rs2881654	-0.250742	1.2459071	0.840501
TZD	Liver cancer	rs1373641	-0.859319	3.2988739	0.794487
TZD	Liver cancer	rs2120825	-0.028872	1.3300165	0.982681
TZD	Liver cancer	rs111327339	4.7755034	3.848086	0.214603
TZD	Liver cancer	rs4135247	-0.857648	1.8999487	0.651697
TZD	Liver cancer	rs1699348	1.5355679	5.5825824	0.783267
TZD	Liver cancer	rs310752	-4.992568	5.4137558	0.356424
TZD	Liver cancer	rs76763697	-10.66567	6.0757666	0.0791834
TZD	Liver cancer	rs2920503	1.2606518	4.4402739	0.776477
TZD	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.487085	0.6784159	0.472773
TZD	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.487085	0.73359	0.5067065
TZD	Liver cancer	All - MR Egger	0.4572882	1.169672	0.7060367
Amylin analog	Liver cancer	rs4663804	2.1430569	7.278523	0.768425
Amylin analog	Liver cancer	rs11869741	3.7367015	4.8165564	0.437865
Amylin analog	Liver cancer	rs12603201	1.5294479	2.9838799	0.608252
Amylin analog	Liver cancer	rs11654396	8.1884168	5.9518114	0.168888
Amylin analog	Liver cancer	rs12941945	6.2047889	4.1913078	0.138768
Amylin analog	Liver cancer	rs1078523	-1.506692	4.5086295	0.738244
Amylin analog	Liver cancer	rs9905939	-1.067889	4.560716	0.814869
Amylin analog	Liver cancer	rs59795094	-0.128354	5.5665859	0.981604
Amylin analog	Liver cancer	rs9892728	-1.355673	4.7559811	0.775609
Amylin analog	Liver cancer	rs73111954	5.5409421	3.8247177	0.147416
Amylin analog	Liver cancer	rs11772021	0.6119363	2.1820887	0.779143

Amylin analog	Liver cancer	rs4724382	4.2417971	6.5960455	0.520171
Amylin analog	Liver cancer	rs75390434	-3.192614	7.4056292	0.666391
Amylin analog	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.7464227	0.7988408	0.0288013
Amylin analog	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.7464227	1.152553	0.1297054
Amylin analog	Liver cancer	All - MR Egger	2.0265146	2.6334391	0.4577844
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	rs4561482	11.537208	6.0260847	0.0555506
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	rs8057326	13.24959	6.7948424	0.0511823
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	rs34497199	5.9996291	5.6259203	0.286231
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	rs11865835	3.0196547	6.9267611	0.66288
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	rs8057029	12.390343	6.303315	0.0493348
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	rs12448775	12.496728	7.0720357	0.0772178
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	rs8054784	10.414674	6.4483699	0.106292
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	9.7711132	1.4239776	6.80E-12
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	9.7711132	2.4193436	5.37E-05
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	All - MR Egger	11.636004	10.910321	0.3349582
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	rs4561482	11.537208	6.0260847	0.0555506
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	rs8057326	13.24959	6.7948424	0.0511823
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	rs34497199	5.9996291	5.6259203	0.286231
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	rs11865835	3.0196547	6.9267611	0.66288
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	rs8057029	12.390343	6.303315	0.0493348
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	rs12448775	12.496728	7.0720357	0.0772178
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	rs8054784	10.414674	6.4483699	0.106292
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	9.7711132	1.4239776	6.80E-12
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	9.7711132	2.4193436	5.37E-05
SGLT2i	Liver cancer	All - MR Egger	11.636004	10.910321	0.3349582
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs77023203	0.012243	0.3999065	0.9755769
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs2074312	0.2326216	0.4826486	0.6298281
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs116842927	-1.983094	1.3228976	0.1338599
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs7110898	1.8466809	2.174766	0.3958034
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs4937311	1.8403175	1.4098413	0.1917782
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs5219	0.058035	0.2244684	0.7959869

SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs4148631	1.793007	1.3146154	0.1725983
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs10766393	0.191811	0.4733596	0.6853216
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs5210	0.1508374	0.4110099	0.7136248
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs10766395	0.1092231	0.4192231	0.7944497
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs189603359	-2.344047	1.4427626	0.1042279
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs10766392	0.1954167	0.4686719	0.6767088
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs7110037	-0.031711	0.5351316	0.9527471
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs77902362	-2.591169	1.3112987	0.0481511
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs35271178	0.0347287	0.2531938	0.8909024
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs147673442	-0.021036	0.8254922	0.9796695
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs2355016	-0.146917	0.561	0.7934112
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs2285676	0.1461463	0.4069268	0.7194855
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs739688	0.4222754	1.0149701	0.6773755
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs79506407	-2.232749	1.4513139	0.1239427
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs7112030	0.1139702	0.415062	0.7836343
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs117973841	0.989702	1.3884106	0.4759504
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs12816749	1.3619527	1.1383432	0.2315272
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs74732083	0.8164574	1.1305157	0.4701721
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs10841887	0.0203824	0.5506471	0.9704728
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs59406438	1.2484989	0.9477801	0.1877423
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.087861	0.0910527	0.3345715
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.087861	0.1012982	0.3857502
SU	Lung adenocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.31964	0.2647434	0.2390587
AGI	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs72681706	1.4582436	1.2534426	0.244671
AGI	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs72692396	1.0728942	1.2359481	0.3853539
AGI	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs174587	0.307095	1.1469274	0.7888883
AGI	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs112968754	0.1799593	1.2086179	0.8816351
AGI	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs8037100	-0.262103	1.5223077	0.8633003
AGI	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs1659215	-0.196	1.6122703	0.9032414
AGI	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs73402785	0.4267932	1.2309705	0.7288071
AGI	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs34359922	0.4813559	1.1861017	0.6848673

AGI	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs111917515	-0.133616	1.1108487	0.904259
AGI	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs113126535	-0.316	1.20248	0.7927123
AGI	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs112898001	-0.03494	1.1990438	0.9767529
AGI	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs4924660	-1.998391	1.3658621	0.1434404
AGI	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.1306299	0.2343302	0.5772126
AGI	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.1306299	0.3613992	0.7177586
AGI	Lung adenocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	2.1764821	1.3987202	0.1507501
DPP-4i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs4233648	0.5249194	1.4134677	0.7103621
DPP-4i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs2080714	2.3569481	1.1261688	0.0363589
DPP-4i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs75850673	-0.338261	1.6298137	0.8355837
DPP-4i	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.1971407	0.8079352	0.1384125
DPP-4i	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.1971407	0.7748734	0.1223583
DPP-4i	Lung adenocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	3.75055	9.978548	0.7711189
Biguanides	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs17485664	-1.059814	1.252119	0.3973204
GLP1RA	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs10305525	-1.927595	1.8367089	0.2939558
GLP1RA	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs228817	-0.878682	1.3186822	0.5051979
GLP1RA	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs12215108	-1.762228	1.2122798	0.1460439
GLP1RA	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs880347	0.2733493	0.800622	0.7327866
GLP1RA	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs9462535	-0.762774	1.067871	0.4750452
GLP1RA	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs142878626	-1.307327	1.457765	0.3698243
GLP1RA	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.702642	0.3598815	0.0508877
GLP1RA	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.702642	0.4735396	0.13786
GLP1RA	Lung adenocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.40326	1.8102342	0.8346299
Insulin	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs4031066	-0.493151	1.2493151	0.6930371
TZD	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs2881654	0.4296167	0.2783202	0.1226838
TZD	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs1373641	-0.591712	0.7621171	0.4375098
TZD	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs2120825	0.590225	0.2972778	0.0470964
TZD	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs111327339	-0.675861	0.9282175	0.4665353
TZD	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs4135247	0.1716622	0.4432172	0.6985271
TZD	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs1699348	-2.26536	1.30576	0.0827589
TZD	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs310752	1.3737692	1.2647692	0.2773986

TZD	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs76763697	-0.307455	1.4702679	0.8343583
TZD	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs2920503	0.5262209	1.0406395	0.6130878
TZD	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.3209992	0.1748608	0.0663959
TZD	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.3209992	0.1695265	0.0582907
TZD	Lung adenocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.6052634	0.2658449	0.056908
Amylin analog	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs4663804	0.8294118	1.672549	0.6199672
Amylin analog	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs11869741	-2.142396	1.1852646	0.0706804
Amylin analog	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs12603201	1.0610121	0.6675709	0.1119786
Amylin analog	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs11654396	-1.675147	1.37	0.2214298
Amylin analog	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs12941945	-1.852751	0.9651528	0.0549027
Amylin analog	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs1078523	-1.599188	1.0138125	0.1147036
Amylin analog	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs9905939	-0.850844	1.0740909	0.4282716
Amylin analog	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs59795094	-2.105077	1.253	0.0929516
Amylin analog	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs9892728	-1.700395	1.07125	0.1124448
Amylin analog	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs73111954	0.0897872	0.8574468	0.9166022
Amylin analog	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs11772021	0.1661698	0.4647205	0.7206657
Amylin analog	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs4724382	-1.156577	1.4836937	0.4356704
Amylin analog	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.440374	0.3294972	0.181385
Amylin analog	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.440374	0.2607106	0.0911946
Amylin analog	Lung adenocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.5367854	0.6992754	0.4604476
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs4561482	-0.953675	1.4183761	0.5013474
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs8057326	-0.510667	1.5348571	0.7393511
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs34497199	0.2546512	1.2674419	0.8407631
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs11150624	-0.953115	1.3370492	0.4759389
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs11865835	1.3326087	1.5986087	0.4045034
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs8057029	-0.216552	1.444569	0.8808376
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs12448775	-2.176923	1.5843269	0.1694303
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs8054784	-0.686486	1.4855856	0.6440109
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.47735	0.3379589	0.1578172
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.47735	0.5112795	0.3504903
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	-2.91102	2.4449856	0.2787712

SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs4561482	-0.953675	1.4183761	0.5013474
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs8057326	-0.510667	1.5348571	0.7393511
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs34497199	0.2546512	1.2674419	0.8407631
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs11150624	-0.953115	1.3370492	0.4759389
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs11865835	1.3326087	1.5986087	0.4045034
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs8057029	-0.216552	1.444569	0.8808376
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs12448775	-2.176923	1.5843269	0.1694303
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs8054784	-0.686486	1.4855856	0.6440109
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.47735	0.3379589	0.1578172
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.47735	0.5112795	0.3504903
SGLT2i	Lung adenocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	-2.91102	2.4449856	0.2787712
SU	Melanoma	rs77023203	-0.002737	0.0024064	0.2554184
SU	Melanoma	rs5219	-7.19E-04	0.0013944	0.606275
SU	Melanoma	rs5210	-0.002465	0.0025158	0.3271159
SU	Melanoma	rs10766395	-0.002071	0.002557	0.4178993
SU	Melanoma	rs35271178	-0.001135	0.0015639	0.467826
SU	Melanoma	rs2285676	-0.002429	0.0024914	0.3296724
SU	Melanoma	rs739688	0.0066966	0.0061151	0.273472
SU	Melanoma	rs7112030	-0.002312	0.0025376	0.3622058
SU	Melanoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.001477	0.0004838	0.00227
SU	Melanoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.001477	0.0007559	0.0507759
SU	Melanoma	All - MR Egger	-0.001993	0.0022217	0.404255
DPP-4i	Melanoma	rs4233648	-0.001054	0.0082071	0.8978115
DPP-4i	Melanoma	rs2080714	0.0045662	0.0067619	0.4994914
DPP-4i	Melanoma	IVW(random effects)	0.0022937	0.0027582	0.4056373
DPP-4i	Melanoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0022937	0.0052187	0.6602873
GLP1RA	Melanoma	rs228817	-0.004726	0.0080391	0.5566116
GLP1RA	Melanoma	rs880347	-0.008779	0.0048172	0.0684037
GLP1RA	Melanoma	rs9462535	0.0110149	0.0066131	0.0957892
GLP1RA	Melanoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.002451	0.0060452	0.685199
GLP1RA	Melanoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.002451	0.0035043	0.4843586

GLP1RA	Melanoma	All - MR Egger	-0.02348	0.037332	0.6425782
Insulin	Melanoma	rs4031066	-0.006774	0.0071437	0.3430089
TZD	Melanoma	rs1373641	-0.00645	0.0047299	0.1726709
TZD	Melanoma	rs4135247	-0.003849	0.0026962	0.1534435
TZD	Melanoma	rs1699348	0.0048345	0.0080518	0.5482242
TZD	Melanoma	rs310752	-0.011712	0.0077072	0.1285897
TZD	Melanoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.004384	0.0019492	0.0245195
TZD	Melanoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.004384	0.0021591	0.0423265
TZD	Melanoma	All - MR Egger	-0.004222	0.0055347	0.525295
Amylin analog	Melanoma	rs4663804	-0.002319	0.0101511	0.8193125
Amylin analog	Melanoma	rs12603201	-0.001604	0.004065	0.6931845
Amylin analog	Melanoma	rs1078523	0.0032467	0.006224	0.601916
Amylin analog	Melanoma	rs9905939	0.0054598	0.0064759	0.3991788
Amylin analog	Melanoma	rs59795094	0.0039792	0.0076769	0.6042278
Amylin analog	Melanoma	rs9892728	0.0039579	0.006557	0.5460977
Amylin analog	Melanoma	rs4724382	0.0022157	0.0091023	0.8076799
Amylin analog	Melanoma	IVW(random effects)	0.0016306	0.0011746	0.1650514
Amylin analog	Melanoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0016306	0.00241	0.4986493
Amylin analog	Melanoma	All - MR Egger	-0.002991	0.0086122	0.7425454
SGLT2i	Melanoma	rs4561482	-0.002983	0.0086316	0.72964
SGLT2i	Melanoma	rs8057326	0.0021823	0.0094637	0.8176244
SGLT2i	Melanoma	rs34497199	8.56E-05	0.0077376	0.9911704
SGLT2i	Melanoma	rs11150624	-0.007845	0.0082807	0.3434621
SGLT2i	Melanoma	rs8057029	0.0022572	0.0090103	0.8021919
SGLT2i	Melanoma	rs8054784	-0.002244	0.0091563	0.8064341
SGLT2i	Melanoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.001593	0.0015719	0.3109451
SGLT2i	Melanoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.001593	0.0035329	0.6521252
SGLT2i	Melanoma	All - MR Egger	-0.018504	0.0534528	0.7466597
SGLT2i	Melanoma	rs4561482	-0.002983	0.0086316	0.72964
SGLT2i	Melanoma	rs8057326	0.0021823	0.0094637	0.8176244
SGLT2i	Melanoma	rs34497199	8.56E-05	0.0077376	0.9911704

SGLT2i	Melanoma	rs11150624	-0.007845	0.0082807	0.3434621
SGLT2i	Melanoma	rs8057029	0.0022572	0.0090103	0.8021919
SGLT2i	Melanoma	rs8054784	-0.002244	0.0091563	0.8064341
SGLT2i	Melanoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.001593	0.0015719	0.3109451
SGLT2i	Melanoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.001593	0.0035329	0.6521252
SGLT2i	Melanoma	All - MR Egger	-0.018504	0.0534528	0.7466597
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs77023203	-0.990794	1.5601519	0.5253875
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs2074312	-0.884411	1.8895622	0.6397484
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs116842927	3.1727233	5.4449673	0.5601026
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs7110898	-6.01366	8.0194894	0.4533266
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs4937311	0.6029302	5.7293254	0.9161887
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs5219	-1.219591	0.9008156	0.1757766
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs4148631	5.7956643	5.1657483	0.2618876
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs10766393	-0.246372	1.851315	0.8941303
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs5210	-1.53818	1.6264138	0.3442764
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs10766395	-2.068682	1.6539825	0.2110338
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs189603359	-2.669416	5.5006615	0.6274706
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs10766392	-0.220862	1.8357682	0.9042372
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs7110037	-0.165889	2.0985816	0.9369941
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs77902362	2.6752013	4.4479545	0.5475434
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs35271178	-0.713367	1.0107876	0.4803411
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs147673442	-4.237461	3.5809067	0.236671
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs2355016	0.4084583	2.2141306	0.8536385
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs2285676	-1.512354	1.6107415	0.347773
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs739688	0.6410898	3.9763114	0.8719144
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs79506407	-13.70005	6.0994404	0.0246966
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs7112030	-0.751628	1.6417593	0.6470828
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs117973841	-5.216921	4.8713576	0.2841974
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs12816749	-7.04645	4.4408462	0.1125725
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs74732083	-6.830897	3.9289462	0.0821038
SU	Multiple myeloma	rs10841887	-3.2735	2.2211059	0.1405313

SU	Multiple myeloma	rs59406438	-1.019321	3.4652854	0.7686416
SU	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	-1.167342	0.3230697	0.0003023
SU	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.167342	0.4005093	0.0035609
SU	Multiple myeloma	All - MR Egger	-1.355012	1.0532187	0.2105257
AGI	Multiple myeloma	rs72681706	-1.544511	4.9005855	0.7526337
AGI	Multiple myeloma	rs72692396	-2.322754	4.367505	0.5948462
AGI	Multiple myeloma	rs174587	-1.730402	4.3370447	0.6899066
AGI	Multiple myeloma	rs112968754	-3.7555	4.874878	0.4410756
AGI	Multiple myeloma	rs8037100	-4.931082	6.1389744	0.4218349
AGI	Multiple myeloma	rs1659215	-5.539946	6.4656757	0.3915422
AGI	Multiple myeloma	rs73402785	-1.499262	4.9706329	0.7629388
AGI	Multiple myeloma	rs34359922	-2.754004	4.7793644	0.564461
AGI	Multiple myeloma	rs111917515	-4.092768	4.4426568	0.3569235
AGI	Multiple myeloma	rs113126535	-4.15156	4.80152	0.3872394
AGI	Multiple myeloma	rs112898001	-4.249084	4.8082072	0.3768502
AGI	Multiple myeloma	rs4924660	-7.497644	5.5076494	0.1734143
AGI	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	-3.437581	0.4939885	3.43E-12
AGI	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.437581	1.4223787	0.0156583
AGI	Multiple myeloma	All - MR Egger	-0.800932	5.2611637	0.8820295
DPP-4i	Multiple myeloma	rs4233648	-1.103113	5.3661048	0.8371264
DPP-4i	Multiple myeloma	rs2080714	-5.014825	4.3812273	0.2523681
DPP-4i	Multiple myeloma	rs75850673	-4.03982	6.1931491	0.5142047
DPP-4i	Multiple myeloma	rs188581353	6.3960576	4.8884981	0.1907414
DPP-4i	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	-0.886921	2.6935498	0.7419472
DPP-4i	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.886921	2.5421164	0.7271713
DPP-4i	Multiple myeloma	All - MR Egger	7.2719045	5.8430732	0.3393642
Biguanides	Multiple myeloma	rs150243609	6.6835286	4.3444714	0.1239512
Biguanides	Multiple myeloma	rs17485664	-4.847844	4.9144238	0.3239113
Biguanides	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	1.6250026	5.7221554	0.7764224
Biguanides	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.6250026	3.2549483	0.6176098
GLP1RA	Multiple myeloma	rs10305525	-4.708456	7.0201266	0.5024065

GLP1RA	Multiple myeloma	rs228817	-4.010829	5.2039147	0.4408651
GLP1RA	Multiple myeloma	rs12215108	-3.470591	4.9117306	0.4798199
GLP1RA	Multiple myeloma	rs28360624	-5.893497	5.1958922	0.2566852
GLP1RA	Multiple myeloma	rs11963172	-3.608789	4.1256889	0.3817307
GLP1RA	Multiple myeloma	rs880347	-3.231909	3.1235646	0.3008155
GLP1RA	Multiple myeloma	rs9462535	4.3474258	4.2908645	0.3109733
GLP1RA	Multiple myeloma	rs142878626	3.0853226	5.4224885	0.5693653
GLP1RA	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	-2.097235	1.2657869	0.0975472
GLP1RA	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.097235	1.6110668	0.1929957
GLP1RA	Multiple myeloma	All - MR Egger	1.2356217	6.8796032	0.8633735
Insulin	Multiple myeloma	rs4031066	-4.833966	4.6235548	0.295788
TZD	Multiple myeloma	rs4684833	3.0435614	3.3878684	0.368988
TZD	Multiple myeloma	rs2881654	-1.489628	1.1020879	0.17649
TZD	Multiple myeloma	rs1373641	-4.529009	3.0731216	0.1405493
TZD	Multiple myeloma	rs2120825	-0.95591	1.1858605	0.4201911
TZD	Multiple myeloma	rs111327339	-0.269171	3.6699094	0.9415313
TZD	Multiple myeloma	rs4135247	-3.377239	1.7502842	0.0536642
TZD	Multiple myeloma	rs1699348	-1.945688	5.2252	0.7096202
TZD	Multiple myeloma	rs310752	-6.837177	4.9955154	0.1711047
TZD	Multiple myeloma	rs76763697	-2.835951	5.3120089	0.5934277
TZD	Multiple myeloma	rs2920503	-4.038959	4.1723605	0.3330307
TZD	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	-1.706381	0.5262994	0.001186
TZD	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.706381	0.6597123	0.0096941
TZD	Multiple myeloma	All - MR Egger	-0.836558	1.0509754	0.4490145
Amylin analog	Multiple myeloma	rs4663804	1.375951	6.7093824	0.8375107
Amylin analog	Multiple myeloma	rs11869741	1.2517354	4.3994708	0.7760123
Amylin analog	Multiple myeloma	rs12603201	-0.684879	2.6294534	0.7945057
Amylin analog	Multiple myeloma	rs11654396	-5.579426	5.4689926	0.3076371
Amylin analog	Multiple myeloma	rs12941945	-2.437555	3.8172882	0.5231114
Amylin analog	Multiple myeloma	rs1078523	-0.40931	4.0204563	0.91891
Amylin analog	Multiple myeloma	rs9905939	-0.896539	4.2008636	0.8310011

Amylin analog	Multiple myeloma	rs59795094	-0.588289	4.9752846	0.9058757
Amylin analog	Multiple myeloma	rs9892728	-0.397225	4.2366908	0.9253011
Amylin analog	Multiple myeloma	rs73111954	4.0350298	3.2501787	0.2144287
Amylin analog	Multiple myeloma	rs11772021	0.9056087	1.8316025	0.6209989
Amylin analog	Multiple myeloma	rs4724382	-2.238676	5.8897387	0.703873
Amylin analog	Multiple myeloma	rs75390434	-3.650821	6.9100769	0.5972683
Amylin analog	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	0.0319754	0.5784931	0.9559205
Amylin analog	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0319754	1.0113231	0.9747772
Amylin analog	Multiple myeloma	All - MR Egger	1.9125929	2.2748077	0.4183775
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	rs4561482	4.5477265	5.5809915	0.4151525
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	rs8057326	0.1979524	6.1141143	0.974172
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	rs34497199	-4.905798	5.010876	0.3275651
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	rs142133957	0.0252289	4.11323	0.9951061
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	rs11150624	2.7065738	5.3503852	0.6129513
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	rs11865835	-4.649122	6.2052609	0.453723
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	rs8057029	3.4408621	5.8375345	0.5555678
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	rs12448775	-2.195558	5.2769551	0.6773623
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	rs8054784	1.6400631	5.9310901	0.782149
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	-9.79E-05	1.1025489	0.9999291
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-9.79E-05	1.7892102	0.9999563
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	All - MR Egger	-1.317326	4.370225	0.7718425
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	rs4561482	4.5477265	5.5809915	0.4151525
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	rs8057326	0.1979524	6.1141143	0.974172
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	rs34497199	-4.905798	5.010876	0.3275651
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	rs142133957	0.0252289	4.11323	0.9951061
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	rs11150624	2.7065738	5.3503852	0.6129513
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	rs11865835	-4.649122	6.2052609	0.453723
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	rs8057029	3.4408621	5.8375345	0.5555678
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	rs12448775	-2.195558	5.2769551	0.6773623
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	rs8054784	1.6400631	5.9310901	0.782149
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	-9.79E-05	1.1025489	0.9999291

SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-9.79E-05	1.7892102	0.9999563
SGLT2i	Multiple myeloma	All - MR Egger	-1.317326	4.370225	0.7718425
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs77023203	1.3303832	0.9241682	0.1499957
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs2074312	0.6711649	1.1187027	0.54854
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs116842927	1.9518649	3.2108279	0.5432533
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs7110898	17.069149	4.8175319	0.0003954
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4937311	1.6825556	3.3961905	0.6203006
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs5219	-0.021951	0.5336931	0.9671925
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4148631	-2.936846	3.062951	0.3376449
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs10766393	0.5067192	1.0959396	0.6438228
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs5210	1.2103695	0.963665	0.2091136
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs10766395	1.2638321	0.9800727	0.1972143
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs189603359	2.0959922	3.2642412	0.5208037
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs10766392	0.5258958	1.0866927	0.6284273
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs7110037	-2.319971	1.2431842	0.0620201
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs77902362	-5.021234	2.6295812	0.0561952
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs35271178	-0.22431	0.599245	0.7081654
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs147673442	1.3028964	2.1316788	0.5410627
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs2355016	-2.502753	1.3113639	0.0563252
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs2285676	1.1812098	0.9543829	0.215839
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs739688	-1.646096	2.3580659	0.4851332
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs79506407	1.8556472	3.6522628	0.6113962
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs7112030	1.1213424	0.9726154	0.2489455
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs117973841	-2.112126	2.8901358	0.4648982
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs12816749	7.5874556	2.634645	0.0039783
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs74732083	-3.977668	2.3260987	0.0872627
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs10841887	-0.18848	1.316	0.8861148
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs59406438	-2.670888	2.0529873	0.1932665
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	0.2323007	0.3289031	0.4800084
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.2323007	0.2373137	0.3276413
SU	Non hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	-0.308701	0.8750555	0.7273338

AGI	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs72681706	2.9609133	2.9040281	0.3079237
AGI	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs72692396	1.2525968	2.5873852	0.6283029
AGI	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs174587	-0.803095	2.5688994	0.7545677
AGI	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs112968754	0.3833866	2.8854715	0.8942978
AGI	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs8037100	-0.469196	3.6323128	0.8972209
AGI	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs1659215	0.4862616	3.8255838	0.8988551
AGI	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs73402785	2.2841772	2.940097	0.4372146
AGI	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs34359922	3.0010297	2.831839	0.2892602
AGI	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs111917515	-0.260557	2.6285683	0.921039
AGI	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs113126535	-0.553208	2.840544	0.8455853
AGI	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs112898001	-0.725088	2.8429044	0.7986832
AGI	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4924660	-0.429011	3.2641264	0.8954334
AGI	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	0.6115027	0.4211386	0.1464953
AGI	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.6115027	0.8420472	0.4677103
AGI	Non hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	3.0770001	3.1165882	0.3467826
DPP-4i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4233648	3.5070726	3.1831774	0.2705694
DPP-4i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs2080714	0.4528909	2.5929286	0.8613438
DPP-4i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs75850673	4.1965901	3.6694348	0.2527642
DPP-4i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs188581353	0.6325294	2.8822153	0.8262922
DPP-4i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	1.8125776	0.9304182	0.0513992
DPP-4i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.8125776	1.504016	0.2281421
DPP-4i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	0.0983056	3.446247	0.9798336
Biguanides	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs150243609	1.7497286	2.5799143	0.4976373
Biguanides	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs17485664	-2.381952	2.9128996	0.4135141
Biguanides	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.066558	2.0507117	0.9741084
Biguanides	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.066558	1.9313205	0.9725084
GLP1RA	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs10305525	-3.330968	4.1592278	0.4232114
GLP1RA	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs228817	-3.896938	3.0852016	0.2065509
GLP1RA	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs12215108	3.8946788	2.9066684	0.1802741
GLP1RA	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs28360624	5.9280299	3.0780419	0.0541157
GLP1RA	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs11963172	2.9409944	2.4438444	0.2288102

GLP1RA	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs880347	-0.537947	1.8489569	0.7710923
GLP1RA	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs9462535	3.9262581	2.5415742	0.1223914
GLP1RA	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs142878626	1.3283779	3.2041244	0.6784467
GLP1RA	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	1.416818	1.1186634	0.2053243
GLP1RA	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.416818	0.9539227	0.1374764
GLP1RA	Non hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	2.9283555	5.1155602	0.5878153
Insulin	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4031066	-1.76389	2.7397123	0.5196901
TZD	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4684833	-1.646412	2.009	0.4124908
TZD	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs2881654	-0.041195	0.6526133	0.9496679
TZD	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs1373641	-0.552441	1.8206486	0.7615613
TZD	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs2120825	0.0292593	0.7013555	0.9667234
TZD	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs111327339	2.5343353	2.1679003	0.2423925
TZD	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4135247	-0.889255	1.0375362	0.391399
TZD	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs1699348	1.610264	3.096184	0.6030077
TZD	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs310752	-0.243783	2.9596077	0.9343524
TZD	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs76763697	-0.665866	3.1443884	0.8322917
TZD	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs2920503	0.1920244	2.4728081	0.938103
TZD	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.121195	0.2293189	0.597153
TZD	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.121195	0.3905769	0.7563351
TZD	Non hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	0.0356664	0.622136	0.9556892
Amylin analog	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4663804	-0.217138	3.9771275	0.9564597
Amylin analog	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs11869741	-1.256747	2.6050279	0.6294997
Amylin analog	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs12603201	-2.008113	1.5581498	0.1974743
Amylin analog	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs11654396	-2.72475	3.2427794	0.4007674
Amylin analog	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs12941945	0.1406349	2.2648996	0.9504886
Amylin analog	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs1078523	1.0955	2.382825	0.6456968
Amylin analog	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs9905939	0.7898831	2.4894091	0.7510179
Amylin analog	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs59795094	1.6108	2.9485	0.5848517
Amylin analog	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs9892728	1.4835197	2.5109276	0.5546374
Amylin analog	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs73111954	-2.81303	1.9265617	0.1442545
Amylin analog	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs11772021	-1.467499	1.0851905	0.1762806

Amylin analog	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4724382	-0.078441	3.490036	0.9820685
Amylin analog	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs75390434	-1.361462	4.0891709	0.7391772
Amylin analog	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.936975	0.3942885	0.017484
Amylin analog	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.936975	0.5993169	0.1179573
Amylin analog	Non hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	-2.353609	1.3478282	0.1085993
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4561482	-5.477795	3.3082051	0.0977581
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs8057326	-4.291171	3.623181	0.2362683
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs34497199	-4.493884	2.9696434	0.1302101
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs142133957	1.2604519	2.4203752	0.602529
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs11150624	-5.591943	3.1700328	0.0777317
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs11865835	-4.401313	3.670887	0.2305365
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs8057029	-6.665784	3.4595086	0.0540044
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs12448775	-2.655705	3.1173558	0.3942643
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs8054784	-5.12327	3.5151622	0.1449846
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-3.640172	0.9156326	7.02E-05
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.640172	1.0583631	0.0005829
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	1.618465	2.5748009	0.5495771
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4561482	-5.477795	3.3082051	0.0977581
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs8057326	-4.291171	3.623181	0.2362683
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs34497199	-4.493884	2.9696434	0.1302101
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs142133957	1.2604519	2.4203752	0.602529
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs11150624	-5.591943	3.1700328	0.0777317
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs11865835	-4.401313	3.670887	0.2305365
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs8057029	-6.665784	3.4595086	0.0540044
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs12448775	-2.655705	3.1173558	0.3942643
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs8054784	-5.12327	3.5151622	0.1449846
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-3.640172	0.9156326	7.02E-05
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.640172	1.0583631	0.0005829
SGLT2i	Non hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	1.618465	2.5748009	0.5495771
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs2074312	-4.405405	1.5675676	0.0049488
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs116842927	3.7908497	4.8366013	0.433167

SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs7110898	-1.276596	6.7659574	0.8503442
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs4937311	-3.650794	4.7619048	0.4432797
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs5219	-0.336474	0.7402423	0.6494363
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs4148631	5.2447552	4.2657343	0.2188813
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs10766393	-4.278215	1.5485564	0.0057323
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs5210	-2.216749	1.3300493	0.0955807
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs10766395	-2.255639	1.3533835	0.0955807
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs189603359	9.4163424	4.2217899	0.0257199
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs10766392	-4.296875	1.5364583	0.0051642
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs7110037	2.5789474	1.7631579	0.1435532
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs77902362	2.4675325	3.9935065	0.5366504
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs35271178	-0.341085	0.8217054	0.6780728
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs147673442	0.2590674	2.7202073	0.9241257
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs2355016	2.8055556	1.8333333	0.1259417
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs2285676	-2.195122	1.3170732	0.0955807
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs739688	7.9640719	3.2934132	0.0155983
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs79506407	4.0875912	5.2068127	0.4324262
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs7112030	-2.059553	1.3399504	0.1242842
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs117973841	-8.576159	4.2384106	0.0430281
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs12816749	-0.473373	3.9053254	0.903523
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs74732083	-2.511211	3.7892377	0.5075087
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs10841887	-1.088235	1.8235294	0.5506581
SU	Oral cavity cancer	rs59406438	-1.41649	2.9386892	0.6297957
SU	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.056895	0.4882911	0.0304277
SU	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.056895	0.3415632	0.0019729
SU	Oral cavity cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.305126	1.2758813	0.3169846
AGI	Oral cavity cancer	rs72681706	-4.449649	4.2154567	0.2911713
AGI	Oral cavity cancer	rs72692396	-8.762475	4.7105788	0.0628615
AGI	Oral cavity cancer	rs174587	3.4636872	3.6312849	0.3401615
AGI	Oral cavity cancer	rs112968754	2.9674797	3.9430894	0.451704
AGI	Oral cavity cancer	rs1659215	3.2972973	5.2432432	0.5294368

AGI	Oral cavity cancer	rs73402785	2.3206751	4.0084388	0.5626247
AGI	Oral cavity cancer	rs34359922	3.3898305	3.8559322	0.3793357
AGI	Oral cavity cancer	rs111917515	2.0295203	3.6162362	0.5746445
AGI	Oral cavity cancer	rs113126535	2	3.92	0.6099085
AGI	Oral cavity cancer	rs112898001	3.7848606	3.8645418	0.3273915
AGI	Oral cavity cancer	rs4924660	-2.298851	4.5402299	0.6126256
AGI	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.0955485	1.1342607	0.3341092
AGI	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.0955485	1.2268509	0.37187
AGI	Oral cavity cancer	All - MR Egger	-7.434751	4.9133604	0.1645307
DPP-4i	Oral cavity cancer	rs4233648	-1.451613	4.5967742	0.7521623
DPP-4i	Oral cavity cancer	rs2080714	5	3.6363636	0.1691314
DPP-4i	Oral cavity cancer	rs75850673	-7.950311	5.4037267	0.1412196
DPP-4i	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.2363822	3.6315136	0.9481008
DPP-4i	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.2363822	2.5221936	0.9253309
DPP-4i	Oral cavity cancer	All - MR Egger	3.6804301	46.280206	0.9494792
Biguanides	Oral cavity cancer	rs17485664	-3.605948	4.0520446	0.3735151
GLP1RA	Oral cavity cancer	rs10305525	-3.481013	5.8860759	0.5542539
GLP1RA	Oral cavity cancer	rs228817	-6.124031	4.2635659	0.1508989
GLP1RA	Oral cavity cancer	rs12215108	2.7979275	4.3005181	0.5153032
GLP1RA	Oral cavity cancer	rs28360624	0.1197605	4.3113772	0.9778394
GLP1RA	Oral cavity cancer	rs11963172	-2.277778	3.5555556	0.5217664
GLP1RA	Oral cavity cancer	rs880347	0.8133971	2.6315789	0.7572524
GLP1RA	Oral cavity cancer	rs9462535	-5.935484	3.483871	0.0884365
GLP1RA	Oral cavity cancer	rs142878626	-0.023041	5.1382488	0.9964221
GLP1RA	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.554138	1.1493695	0.1763224
GLP1RA	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.554138	1.3665184	0.255414
GLP1RA	Oral cavity cancer	All - MR Egger	7.6562333	6.1425033	0.2590601
TZD	Oral cavity cancer	rs4684833	2.0175439	2.8070175	0.472295
TZD	Oral cavity cancer	rs2881654	0.8680947	0.9131905	0.3417987
TZD	Oral cavity cancer	rs2120825	0.9223847	0.9786277	0.345922
TZD	Oral cavity cancer	rs111327339	-1.163142	3.429003	0.7344538

TZD	Oral cavity cancer	rs4135247	-0.214477	1.4477212	0.8822259
TZD	Oral cavity cancer	rs310752	9.3846154	4.1538462	0.0238673
TZD	Oral cavity cancer	rs76763697	5.4017857	4.5089286	0.2309093
TZD	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.9437247	0.5867237	0.1077333
TZD	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.9437247	0.5735824	0.0999045
TZD	Oral cavity cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.33978	0.9788869	0.7426425
Amylin analog	Oral cavity cancer	rs4663804	15.098039	5.5882353	0.0068975
Amylin analog	Oral cavity cancer	rs11869741	-1.253482	4.3175487	0.7715695
Amylin analog	Oral cavity cancer	rs12603201	2.8340081	2.1862348	0.1948734
Amylin analog	Oral cavity cancer	rs11654396	-2.720588	4.4852941	0.5441447
Amylin analog	Oral cavity cancer	rs1078523	0.8125	3.3125	0.8062373
Amylin analog	Oral cavity cancer	rs9905939	-0.584416	3.5064935	0.8676323
Amylin analog	Oral cavity cancer	rs59795094	-0.923077	4.1538462	0.8241409
Amylin analog	Oral cavity cancer	rs9892728	0.5921053	3.4868421	0.8651585
Amylin analog	Oral cavity cancer	rs73111954	3.1914894	2.7234043	0.2412472
Amylin analog	Oral cavity cancer	rs4724382	6.3063063	4.8648649	0.1948734
Amylin analog	Oral cavity cancer	rs75390434	4.8717949	5.6410256	0.3877877
Amylin analog	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.016129	1.0681826	0.0591014
Amylin analog	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.016129	1.0747266	0.0606627
Amylin analog	Oral cavity cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.823729	3.4818054	0.8182786
SGLT2i	Oral cavity cancer	rs8057326	1.1428571	5.1428571	0.8241409
SGLT2i	Oral cavity cancer	rs34497199	1.9379845	4.2635659	0.6494363
SGLT2i	Oral cavity cancer	rs11150624	8.1147541	4.5081967	0.0718606
SGLT2i	Oral cavity cancer	rs8057029	-0.344828	4.8275862	0.9430567
SGLT2i	Oral cavity cancer	rs12448775	13.75	6.4423077	0.0328159
SGLT2i	Oral cavity cancer	rs8054784	3.3333333	5.045045	0.5087956
SGLT2i	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	4.013289	1.9024206	0.0348954
SGLT2i	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	4.013289	2.0067741	0.0455142
SGLT2i	Oral cavity cancer	All - MR Egger	19.573293	9.7675783	0.1156001
SGLT2i	Oral cavity cancer	rs8057326	1.1428571	5.1428571	0.8241409
SGLT2i	Oral cavity cancer	rs34497199	1.9379845	4.2635659	0.6494363

SGLT2i	Oral cavity cancer	rs11150624	8.1147541	4.5081967	0.0718606
SGLT2i	Oral cavity cancer	rs8057029	-0.344828	4.8275862	0.9430567
SGLT2i	Oral cavity cancer	rs12448775	13.75	6.4423077	0.0328159
SGLT2i	Oral cavity cancer	rs8054784	3.3333333	5.045045	0.5087956
SGLT2i	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	4.013289	1.9024206	0.0348954
SGLT2i	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	4.013289	2.0067741	0.0455142
SGLT2i	Oral cavity cancer	All - MR Egger	19.573293	9.7675783	0.1156001
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs77023203	-0.673156	0.9908455	0.4969
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs2074312	-1.363555	1.1865919	0.2505
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs116842927	-2.312388	3.3290466	0.4873
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs7110898	10.28136	4.5955345	0.02527
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs4937311	-1.239792	3.6034022	0.7308
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs5219	0.1778241	0.5679355	0.7542
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs4148631	-2.371903	3.2456162	0.4649
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs10766393	-0.664509	1.1691985	0.5698
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs5210	-0.364757	1.0325694	0.7239
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs10766395	-0.363526	1.0508846	0.7294
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs189603359	3.5806038	3.1449409	0.2549
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs10766392	-0.699413	1.1581309	0.5459
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs7110037	-0.706775	1.3176905	0.5917
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs77902362	-2.759231	2.9769714	0.354
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs35271178	-0.381397	0.6435204	0.5534
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs147673442	4.8160229	2.4536556	0.04967
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs2355016	-0.740334	1.3899983	0.5943
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs2285676	-0.368625	1.0260661	0.7194
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs739688	1.59593	2.8695407	0.5781
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs79506407	7.9210639	4.6611841	0.08925
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs7112030	-0.640962	1.0413047	0.5382
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs117973841	1.1615075	3.1750863	0.7145
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs12816749	6.922092	2.7401077	0.01153
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs74732083	0.2094959	2.4881702	0.9329

SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs10841887	0.0440846	1.4296277	0.9754
SU	Oropharynx cancer	rs59406438	-5.149544	2.4566824	0.03607
SU	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.248008	0.2767505	0.3701755
SU	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.248008	0.2545276	0.3298642
SU	Oropharynx cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.6383	0.7410832	0.3975929
AGI	Oropharynx cancer	rs72681706	1.1987831	2.9611765	0.6856
AGI	Oropharynx cancer	rs72692396	-2.167371	2.8888391	0.4531
AGI	Oropharynx cancer	rs174587	5.8352012	2.8349422	0.03956
AGI	Oropharynx cancer	rs112968754	0.9084497	3.0619062	0.7667
AGI	Oropharynx cancer	rs8037100	1.6302217	3.8403188	0.6712
AGI	Oropharynx cancer	rs1659215	1.9065197	4.0257672	0.6358
AGI	Oropharynx cancer	rs73402785	0.4709732	3.1222855	0.8801
AGI	Oropharynx cancer	rs34359922	1.2426199	3.0116847	0.6799
AGI	Oropharynx cancer	rs111917515	1.4065433	2.7714824	0.6118
AGI	Oropharynx cancer	rs113126535	1.4624102	3.0006494	0.626
AGI	Oropharynx cancer	rs112898001	1.8219064	2.9818467	0.5412
AGI	Oropharynx cancer	rs4924660	3.6516104	3.4069188	0.2838
AGI	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.5863782	0.574474	0.0057546
AGI	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.5863782	0.8954408	0.0764581
AGI	Oropharynx cancer	All - MR Egger	-3.837481	3.3487487	0.2785002
DPP-4i	Oropharynx cancer	rs4233648	-19.55447	7.3951834	0.008188
DPP-4i	Oropharynx cancer	rs2080714	-2.004653	2.7591301	0.4675
DPP-4i	Oropharynx cancer	rs75850673	6.5826288	4.2029092	0.1173
DPP-4i	Oropharynx cancer	rs188581353	2.3154588	2.7900733	0.4066
DPP-4i	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.1470112	3.2573463	0.9640019
DPP-4i	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.1470112	1.7284744	0.9322196
DPP-4i	Oropharynx cancer	All - MR Egger	4.3757189	7.1987779	0.6051202
Biguanides	Oropharynx cancer	rs150243609	2.6171706	2.8490576	0.3583
Biguanides	Oropharynx cancer	rs17485664	1.0060565	3.0671012	0.7429
Biguanides	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.8709116	0.8033716	0.0198684
Biguanides	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.8709116	2.0874196	0.3701034

GLP1RA	Oropharynx cancer	rs10305525	2.9129391	4.5463023	0.5217
GLP1RA	Oropharynx cancer	rs228817	-3.447635	3.3154459	0.2984
GLP1RA	Oropharynx cancer	rs12215108	0.387151	3.0593779	0.8993
GLP1RA	Oropharynx cancer	rs28360624	1.1242608	3.2663529	0.7307
GLP1RA	Oropharynx cancer	rs11963172	0.418237	2.6185296	0.8731
GLP1RA	Oropharynx cancer	rs880347	-1.802922	1.9782527	0.3621
GLP1RA	Oropharynx cancer	rs9462535	1.0012782	2.6994732	0.7107
GLP1RA	Oropharynx cancer	rs142878626	-1.024758	3.3589052	0.7603
GLP1RA	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.391969	0.6154677	0.5242135
GLP1RA	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.391969	1.0168375	0.6998828
GLP1RA	Oropharynx cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.956295	4.3046185	0.8315614
Insulin	Oropharynx cancer	rs4031066	-4.094329	2.9062925	0.1589
Insulin	Oropharynx cancer	rs144057856	-0.389318	2.4239832	0.8724
Insulin	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.909298	1.8224172	0.294789
Insulin	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.909298	1.8615024	0.3050443
TZD	Oropharynx cancer	rs4684833	1.0789525	2.1635872	0.618
TZD	Oropharynx cancer	rs2881654	-1.717426	0.6579678	0.009049
TZD	Oropharynx cancer	rs1373641	-1.493	1.9250234	0.438
TZD	Oropharynx cancer	rs2120825	-2.250141	0.6877018	0.001068
TZD	Oropharynx cancer	rs111327339	0.3948438	2.1591497	0.8549
TZD	Oropharynx cancer	rs4135247	-1.698817	1.1079425	0.1252
TZD	Oropharynx cancer	rs1699348	0.5103686	3.2760419	0.8762
TZD	Oropharynx cancer	rs310752	-4.016375	3.1591126	0.2036
TZD	Oropharynx cancer	rs76763697	-4.5018	3.6998612	0.2237
TZD	Oropharynx cancer	rs2920503	-3.101813	2.6669119	0.2448
TZD	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.783795	0.2971463	1.94E-09
TZD	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.783795	0.3970256	7.03E-06
TZD	Oropharynx cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.908681	0.6292231	0.0162255
Amylin analog	Oropharynx cancer	rs4663804	-10.42755	8.2946077	0.2087
Amylin analog	Oropharynx cancer	rs11869741	1.4411754	6.9019957	0.8346
Amylin analog	Oropharynx cancer	rs12603201	0.5349122	1.6656373	0.7481

Amylin analog	Oropharynx cancer	rs11654396	-5.098491	3.5443782	0.1503
Amylin analog	Oropharynx cancer	rs12941945	-1.796591	2.4501431	0.4634
Amylin analog	Oropharynx cancer	rs1078523	1.9868327	2.5746622	0.4403
Amylin analog	Oropharynx cancer	rs9905939	2.2058779	2.6768101	0.4099
Amylin analog	Oropharynx cancer	rs59795094	2.8170141	3.1667354	0.3737
Amylin analog	Oropharynx cancer	rs9892728	2.2441796	2.7163209	0.4087
Amylin analog	Oropharynx cancer	rs73111954	1.9994379	2.0928821	0.3394
Amylin analog	Oropharynx cancer	rs11772021	-2.018687	1.1283696	0.07361
Amylin analog	Oropharynx cancer	rs4724382	-1.713334	3.7233282	0.6454
Amylin analog	Oropharynx cancer	rs75390434	-3.729783	4.302466	0.386
Amylin analog	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.387869	0.6531028	0.5525884
Amylin analog	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.387869	0.6582816	0.555718
Amylin analog	Oropharynx cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.573246	1.4986188	0.3163285
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	rs4561482	-2.506481	3.5455055	0.4796
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	rs8057326	-2.391686	3.8778888	0.5374
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	rs34497199	-0.732129	3.1833144	0.8181
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	rs142133957	5.6193163	2.3163733	0.01527
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	rs11150624	-4.139589	3.419093	0.226
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	rs11865835	-3.134067	3.9107391	0.4229
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	rs8057029	-3.026653	3.7059556	0.4141
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	rs12448775	-1.287878	3.4152244	0.7061
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	rs8054784	-5.144107	3.7725032	0.1727
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.782727	1.3080013	0.5495635
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.782727	1.1105326	0.4809216
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	All - MR Egger	5.9750426	2.550047	0.0516081
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	rs4561482	-2.506481	3.5455055	0.4796
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	rs8057326	-2.391686	3.8778888	0.5374
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	rs34497199	-0.732129	3.1833144	0.8181
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	rs142133957	5.6193163	2.3163733	0.01527
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	rs11150624	-4.139589	3.419093	0.226
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	rs11865835	-3.134067	3.9107391	0.4229

SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	rs8057029	-3.026653	3.7059556	0.4141
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	rs12448775	-1.287878	3.4152244	0.7061
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	rs8054784	-5.144107	3.7725032	0.1727
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.782727	1.3080013	0.5495635
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.782727	1.1105326	0.4809216
SGLT2i	Oropharynx cancer	All - MR Egger	5.9750426	2.550047	0.0516081
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs77023203	0.3156542	0.3224299	0.3275871
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs2074312	0.6745946	0.3913514	0.0847517
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs116842927	0.1736601	1.0851852	0.8728589
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs7110898	-1.805532	1.806383	0.3175386
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4937311	0.8515873	1.1619048	0.4636051
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs5219	0.2716016	0.184253	0.1404631
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4148631	-0.207273	1.0762238	0.847278
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs10766393	0.9152231	0.3834646	0.0169994
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs5210	0.3305419	0.3369458	0.3265956
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs10766395	0.3285714	0.343609	0.3389529
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs189603359	1.4733463	1.2420233	0.2355248
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs10766392	0.8783854	0.3804688	0.0209606
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs7110037	0.0418947	0.4368421	0.9235971
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs77902362	0.3847403	1.0152597	0.7047194
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs35271178	0.2232558	0.207907	0.2829009
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs147673442	0.6626943	0.7085492	0.3496423
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs2355016	0.0626111	0.4613889	0.8920574
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs2285676	0.3334146	0.3334146	0.3173105
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs739688	-0.021515	0.8287425	0.9792885
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs79506407	0.2208759	1.2472019	0.8594321
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	rs7112030	0.3573201	0.3409429	0.2946225
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.3535277	0.0587752	1.80E-09
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.3535277	0.0858345	3.81E-05
SU	Ovarian carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.2944642	0.2286101	0.2131908
AGI	Ovarian carcinoma	rs72681706	1.3276347	0.9941452	0.181728

AGI	Ovarian carcinoma	rs72692396	0.2576846	0.996008	0.7958533
AGI	Ovarian carcinoma	rs174587	0.749162	0.9536313	0.4321085
AGI	Ovarian carcinoma	rs112968754	-0.525203	1.0158537	0.6051514
AGI	Ovarian carcinoma	rs8037100	-1.194872	1.2738462	0.3482428
AGI	Ovarian carcinoma	rs1659215	-1.130811	1.3448649	0.4004398
AGI	Ovarian carcinoma	rs73402785	-0.440506	1.0320675	0.669511
AGI	Ovarian carcinoma	rs34359922	-0.084534	0.9898305	0.9319415
AGI	Ovarian carcinoma	rs111917515	-0.599262	0.9254613	0.5172903
AGI	Ovarian carcinoma	rs113126535	-0.6436	1.0036	0.5213334
AGI	Ovarian carcinoma	rs112898001	-0.836653	1.0027888	0.404097
AGI	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4924660	-0.282874	1.1304598	0.8024104
AGI	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.209379	0.2138524	0.3275384
AGI	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.209379	0.2994161	0.4843692
AGI	Ovarian carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.7375649	1.1341469	0.5301384
DPP-4i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4233648	-1.474194	1.1798387	0.2114869
DPP-4i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs2080714	0.0232987	0.9519481	0.9804739
DPP-4i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs75850673	2.036646	1.315528	0.1215841
DPP-4i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs188581353	-0.609637	1.2214018	0.6176885
DPP-4i	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.086364	0.6740737	0.8980521
DPP-4i	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.086364	0.5707269	0.8797212
DPP-4i	Ovarian carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.063254	2.09392	0.9786445
Biguanides	Ovarian carcinoma	rs150243609	-0.010439	0.9188571	0.9909359
GLP1RA	Ovarian carcinoma	rs10305525	1.8310127	1.4993671	0.2220139
GLP1RA	Ovarian carcinoma	rs228817	-0.265891	1.0984496	0.8087331
GLP1RA	Ovarian carcinoma	rs12215108	0.3281347	1.0139896	0.7462352
GLP1RA	Ovarian carcinoma	rs28360624	-0.641916	1.0479042	0.5401598
GLP1RA	Ovarian carcinoma	rs11963172	-0.127611	0.8638889	0.8825661
GLP1RA	Ovarian carcinoma	rs880347	-1.261244	0.669378	0.0595375
GLP1RA	Ovarian carcinoma	rs9462535	-1.783226	0.88	0.0427245
GLP1RA	Ovarian carcinoma	rs142878626	-1.512903	1.2225806	0.2159138
GLP1RA	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.687317	0.3424981	0.0447736

GLP1RA	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.687317	0.3392471	0.0427642
GLP1RA	Ovarian carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-1.786954	1.5787281	0.3008784
Insulin	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4031066	0.0703425	1.0013699	0.9439977
Insulin	Ovarian carcinoma	rs144057856	0.3369589	0.9390677	0.7197276
Insulin	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.2122022	0.1330337	0.1106895
Insulin	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.2122022	0.6849881	0.7567209
TZD	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4684833	0.2599123	0.7026316	0.7114476
TZD	Ovarian carcinoma	rs2881654	-0.072559	0.2234498	0.7453911
TZD	Ovarian carcinoma	rs1373641	0.3025676	0.6292793	0.6306473
TZD	Ovarian carcinoma	rs2120825	-0.193588	0.2374578	0.4149273
TZD	Ovarian carcinoma	rs111327339	0.1759819	0.7589124	0.8166258
TZD	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4135247	-0.007587	0.361126	0.983238
TZD	Ovarian carcinoma	rs1699348	-0.022672	1.0632	0.982987
TZD	Ovarian carcinoma	rs310752	1.7261538	1.0415385	0.0974565
TZD	Ovarian carcinoma	rs76763697	-0.371741	1.1674107	0.7501572
TZD	Ovarian carcinoma	rs2920503	0.0549302	0.8517442	0.9485789
TZD	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.035488	0.089097	0.6904006
TZD	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.035488	0.1340662	0.7912345
TZD	Ovarian carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.251807	0.213006	0.2710857
Amylin analog	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4663804	0.5846078	1.377451	0.6712648
Amylin analog	Ovarian carcinoma	rs11869741	2.9498607	1.1091922	0.0078264
Amylin analog	Ovarian carcinoma	rs12603201	1.2072874	0.5453441	0.026842
Amylin analog	Ovarian carcinoma	rs11654396	0.7275	1.1191176	0.5156498
Amylin analog	Ovarian carcinoma	rs12941945	0.5572052	0.7917031	0.4815537
Amylin analog	Ovarian carcinoma	rs1078523	1.98	0.825	0.0163951
Amylin analog	Ovarian carcinoma	rs9905939	1.8201299	0.8590909	0.0341184
Amylin analog	Ovarian carcinoma	rs59795094	2.5261538	1.0230769	0.0135426
Amylin analog	Ovarian carcinoma	rs9892728	2.1052632	0.8697368	0.015496
Amylin analog	Ovarian carcinoma	rs73111954	-0.276255	0.6902128	0.6889749
Amylin analog	Ovarian carcinoma	rs11772021	-0.314493	0.3850932	0.4141189
Amylin analog	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4724382	-1.588288	1.2144144	0.1909196

Amylin analog	Ovarian carcinoma	rs75390434	-3.501709	1.4478632	0.0155831
Amylin analog	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.6018874	0.3657165	0.0998099
Amylin analog	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.6018874	0.2122612	0.004574
Amylin analog	Ovarian carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.0399798	0.8443842	0.9630847
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4561482	0.6257265	1.1709402	0.593079
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs8057326	0.1600952	1.2542857	0.898435
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs34497199	0.4667442	1.0379845	0.6529528
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs142133957	-1.87602	1.0636215	0.077765
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs11150624	-0.295738	1.107377	0.7894219
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs11865835	2.4182609	1.3234783	0.0676695
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs8057029	0.6984483	1.2051724	0.5622234
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs12448775	-0.621474	1.2762821	0.6263
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs8054784	-0.093243	1.2234234	0.939248
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.0779816	0.3804039	0.8375745
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0779816	0.3912114	0.8420017
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-2.046016	1.1004296	0.1053215
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4561482	0.6257265	1.1709402	0.593079
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs8057326	0.1600952	1.2542857	0.898435
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs34497199	0.4667442	1.0379845	0.6529528
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs142133957	-1.87602	1.0636215	0.077765
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs11150624	-0.295738	1.107377	0.7894219
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs11865835	2.4182609	1.3234783	0.0676695
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs8057029	0.6984483	1.2051724	0.5622234
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs12448775	-0.621474	1.2762821	0.6263
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	rs8054784	-0.093243	1.2234234	0.939248
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.0779816	0.3804039	0.8375745
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.0779816	0.3912114	0.8420017
SGLT2i	Ovarian carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-2.046016	1.1004296	0.1053215
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs77023203	1.5173993	1.366172	0.2667
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs2074312	1.9495837	1.6578274	0.2396
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs116842927	2.1989263	5.1951203	0.6721

SU	Pancreas cancer	rs7110898	-5.078585	7.3688562	0.4907
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs4937311	3.5693147	4.9392588	0.4699
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs5219	1.2091616	0.7663348	0.1146
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs4148631	-1.158188	4.4332616	0.7939
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs10766393	2.3340212	1.635694	0.1536
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs5210	2.1745213	1.4226939	0.1264
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs10766395	2.0029981	1.4467118	0.1662
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs189603359	2.2148019	4.4858966	0.6215
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs10766392	2.0571877	1.6152355	0.2028
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs7110037	-0.964842	1.7862784	0.5891
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs77902362	1.352457	3.8932196	0.7283
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs35271178	1.0475223	0.8689332	0.228
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs147673442	2.7525938	3.1301839	0.3792
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs2355016	-1.136838	1.881509	0.5457
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs2285676	2.1800869	1.409374	0.1219
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs739688	0.6683871	4.0246738	0.8681
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs79506407	-0.778754	5.1888613	0.8807
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs7112030	2.0517461	1.4350776	0.1528
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs117973841	-3.944418	3.9820045	0.3219
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs12816749	-4.361837	3.887861	0.2619
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs74732083	0.4987805	3.389208	0.883
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs10841887	1.4237982	1.9378352	0.4625
SU	Pancreas cancer	rs59406438	2.1875985	2.8692235	0.4458
SU	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.3058749	0.232318	1.90E-08
SU	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.3058749	0.3469246	0.0001671
SU	Pancreas cancer	All - MR Egger	1.8475577	0.9186248	0.0556626
AGI	Pancreas cancer	rs72681706	-0.067817	4.0682671	0.9867
AGI	Pancreas cancer	rs72692396	0.6223776	3.6416998	0.8643
AGI	Pancreas cancer	rs174587	-0.798982	3.7572656	0.8316
AGI	Pancreas cancer	rs112968754	1.0208415	4.1436207	0.8054
AGI	Pancreas cancer	rs8037100	0.3577238	5.2620403	0.9458

AGI	Pancreas cancer	rs1659215	0.1673084	5.5153842	0.9758
AGI	Pancreas cancer	rs73402785	0.8395203	4.2142891	0.8421
AGI	Pancreas cancer	rs34359922	2.811589	4.0319689	0.4856
AGI	Pancreas cancer	rs111917515	0.9266679	3.7972001	0.8072
AGI	Pancreas cancer	rs113126535	0.8366899	4.1129403	0.8388
AGI	Pancreas cancer	rs112898001	0.6304602	4.1104928	0.8781
AGI	Pancreas cancer	rs4924660	-0.693827	4.7554799	0.884
AGI	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.592015	0.2760616	0.0319926
AGI	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.592015	1.2094958	0.6245072
AGI	Pancreas cancer	All - MR Egger	1.4580792	4.4258646	0.7486158
DPP-4i	Pancreas cancer	rs4233648	-19.61141	9.1288064	0.03169
DPP-4i	Pancreas cancer	rs2080714	3.844926	3.8202918	0.3142
DPP-4i	Pancreas cancer	rs75850673	6.8001249	5.7358391	0.2358
DPP-4i	Pancreas cancer	rs188581353	2.3985593	3.950018	0.5437
DPP-4i	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.2201387	3.5293568	0.5293169
DPP-4i	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.2201387	2.3904225	0.3530113
DPP-4i	Pancreas cancer	All - MR Egger	4.2136248	8.6709134	0.6750318
Biguanides	Pancreas cancer	rs150243609	5.2657563	3.660658	0.1503
Biguanides	Pancreas cancer	rs17485664	-3.097755	4.4139745	0.4828
Biguanides	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.8575353	4.1095893	0.6512688
Biguanides	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.8575353	2.81773	0.5097474
GLP1RA	Pancreas cancer	rs10305525	1.6677073	6.1571204	0.7865
GLP1RA	Pancreas cancer	rs228817	-3.853922	4.4994148	0.3917
GLP1RA	Pancreas cancer	rs12215108	0.6641194	4.1845718	0.8739
GLP1RA	Pancreas cancer	rs28360624	-5.815971	4.5806724	0.2042
GLP1RA	Pancreas cancer	rs11963172	-4.337308	3.6312019	0.2323
GLP1RA	Pancreas cancer	rs880347	-1.68297	2.6909737	0.5317
GLP1RA	Pancreas cancer	rs9462535	3.383991	3.6670031	0.3561
GLP1RA	Pancreas cancer	rs142878626	-3.596064	4.4325343	0.4172
GLP1RA	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.689994	1.0855774	0.1195252
GLP1RA	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.689994	1.3870965	0.2230842

GLP1RA	Pancreas cancer	All - MR Egger	-3.711508	5.7487081	0.5424094
Insulin	Pancreas cancer	rs4031066	-1.093957	3.9814876	0.7835
Insulin	Pancreas cancer	rs144057856	3.2686493	2.8939696	0.2587
Insulin	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.7605537	2.0748192	0.3961409
Insulin	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.7605537	2.3409212	0.4520046
TZD	Pancreas cancer	rs4684833	3.6284933	2.9879219	0.2246
TZD	Pancreas cancer	rs2881654	0.6633009	0.9673287	0.4929
TZD	Pancreas cancer	rs1373641	-1.68433	2.6124439	0.5191
TZD	Pancreas cancer	rs2120825	0.5691569	1.031495	0.5811
TZD	Pancreas cancer	rs111327339	2.1106034	2.7555001	0.4437
TZD	Pancreas cancer	rs4135247	-2.27626	1.5111984	0.132
TZD	Pancreas cancer	rs1699348	0.9779976	4.4565974	0.8263
TZD	Pancreas cancer	rs310752	-2.831844	4.2891149	0.5091
TZD	Pancreas cancer	rs76763697	-1.401864	4.9541135	0.7772
TZD	Pancreas cancer	rs2920503	-0.50939	3.5783194	0.8868
TZD	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.1578581	0.4678592	0.7358114
TZD	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.1578581	0.5716408	0.7824335
TZD	Pancreas cancer	All - MR Egger	0.759849	0.9108162	0.4283458
Amylin analog	Pancreas cancer	rs4663804	-10.27501	10.215511	0.3145
Amylin analog	Pancreas cancer	rs11869741	11.82222	9.5034014	0.2135
Amylin analog	Pancreas cancer	rs12603201	-1.665366	2.2793299	0.465
Amylin analog	Pancreas cancer	rs11654396	-12.45626	4.9343695	0.01159
Amylin analog	Pancreas cancer	rs12941945	-5.162768	3.4106769	0.1301
Amylin analog	Pancreas cancer	rs1078523	0.9859324	3.50686	0.7786
Amylin analog	Pancreas cancer	rs9905939	0.1755618	3.5995508	0.9611
Amylin analog	Pancreas cancer	rs59795094	0.8567496	4.3174008	0.8427
Amylin analog	Pancreas cancer	rs9892728	1.0507743	3.689561	0.7758
Amylin analog	Pancreas cancer	rs73111954	-0.212236	2.9020385	0.9417
Amylin analog	Pancreas cancer	rs11772021	2.2796941	1.650449	0.1672
Amylin analog	Pancreas cancer	rs4724382	-4.472697	5.0766517	0.3783
Amylin analog	Pancreas cancer	rs75390434	-1.787799	5.8954791	0.7617

Amylin analog	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.373078	1.0149324	0.7131796
Amylin analog	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.373078	0.9208894	0.6853833
Amylin analog	Pancreas cancer	All - MR Egger	3.3421546	2.1370656	0.1461354
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	rs4561482	0.111039	4.9769054	0.9822
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	rs8057326	8.5736669	5.2614222	0.1032
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	rs34497199	11.612276	4.3452554	0.007531
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	rs142133957	0.9920414	3.7196876	0.7897
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	rs11150624	1.8317921	4.6209124	0.6918
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	rs11865835	2.6462789	5.3938184	0.6237
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	rs8057029	1.9855775	4.9900757	0.6907
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	rs12448775	3.1781273	4.3880422	0.4689
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	rs8054784	3.5507209	5.0686628	0.4836
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.7701148	1.2953089	0.0036075
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.7701148	1.5542584	0.0152802
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	All - MR Egger	1.1374288	3.8588739	0.7767296
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	rs4561482	0.111039	4.9769054	0.9822
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	rs8057326	8.5736669	5.2614222	0.1032
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	rs34497199	11.612276	4.3452554	0.007531
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	rs142133957	0.9920414	3.7196876	0.7897
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	rs11150624	1.8317921	4.6209124	0.6918
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	rs11865835	2.6462789	5.3938184	0.6237
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	rs8057029	1.9855775	4.9900757	0.6907
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	rs12448775	3.1781273	4.3880422	0.4689
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	rs8054784	3.5507209	5.0686628	0.4836
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.7701148	1.2953089	0.0036075
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.7701148	1.5542584	0.0152802
SGLT2i	Pancreas cancer	All - MR Egger	1.1374288	3.8588739	0.7767296
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs77023203	-1.570093	1.3481308	0.2441628
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs2074312	-2.732432	1.5945946	0.0866097
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs116842927	-8.810458	6.7189542	0.1897618
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs7110898	3.2595745	4.0808511	0.4244361

SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	4937311	-7.095238	4.9444444	0.1512894
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	5219	-1.273217	0.7900404	0.1070524
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	4148631	-2.594406	4.958042	0.6007848
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	10766393	-2.152231	1.5564304	0.1667264
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	5210	-1.704433	1.4137931	0.2279814
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	10766395	-1.348371	1.4385965	0.3486134
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	189603359	-4.653696	6.5544747	0.4777023
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	10766392	-2.252604	1.5442708	0.1446519
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	7110037	0.0842105	1.9736842	0.9659673
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	77902362	-7.37987	5.3506494	0.1678184
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	35271178	-1.20155	0.896124	0.1799755
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	147673442	-0.124352	3.5932642	0.9723931
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	2355016	-0.077778	2.1416667	0.97103
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	2285676	-1.680488	1.4	0.230004
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	739688	0.3473054	3.491018	0.9207529
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	79506407	2.0681265	3.0097324	0.4919905
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	7112030	-1.851117	1.426799	0.1944966
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	117973841	-4.135762	6.0066225	0.4911168
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	12816749	4.7514793	4.6094675	0.3026305
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	74732083	-7.522422	4.5762332	0.1002171
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	10841887	-2.447059	2.1558824	0.2563496
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	59406438	0.448203	4.1818182	0.914647
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.485565	0.2623956	1.50E-08
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.485565	0.3542306	2.74E-05
SU	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.366472	0.9413463	0.1595565
AGI	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	72681706	-4.641686	5.8079625	0.4241782
AGI	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	72692396	-6.251497	5.3253493	0.2404299
AGI	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	174587	6.2793296	4.3743017	0.1511434
AGI	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	112968754	1.0569106	5.8943089	0.857694
AGI	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	8037100	-5.953846	5.4974359	0.2787985
AGI	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancers	1659215	-6.491892	5.7891892	0.2621253

AGI	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs73402785	-0.299578	5.9915612	0.9601224
AGI	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs34359922	0.970339	5.7923729	0.8669608
AGI	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs111917515	0.099631	5.3579336	0.9851642
AGI	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs113126535	0.188	5.8	0.9741421
AGI	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs112898001	0.2111554	5.7848606	0.9708826
AGI	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs4924660	-4.33908	4.8333333	0.3693238
AGI	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.337227	1.2242606	0.2747132
AGI	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.337227	1.5737055	0.3954745
AGI	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	-5.501349	5.9736854	0.378768
DPP-4i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs4233648	-3.403226	4.9032258	0.4876327
DPP-4i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs2080714	2.1233766	5.3116883	0.6893366
DPP-4i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs75850673	-4.279503	4.6273292	0.3550532
DPP-4i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs188581353	-8.018773	5.0663329	0.1134769
DPP-4i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-3.556035	1.9959943	0.0748168
DPP-4i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.556035	2.4791717	0.1514684
DPP-4i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	-8.556948	6.0007266	0.2899686
Biguanides	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs150243609	-8.377143	5.2371429	0.1096954
Biguanides	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs17485664	0.4758364	5.9888476	0.9366717
Biguanides	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-4.540812	4.3869719	0.3006374
Biguanides	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-4.540812	3.9423624	0.2494033
GLP1RA	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs10305525	2.3544304	4.8291139	0.6258692
GLP1RA	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs228817	0.379845	4.8527132	0.9376095
GLP1RA	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs12215108	2.8186528	5.9067358	0.6332247
GLP1RA	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs28360624	4.005988	6.3473054	0.5279542
GLP1RA	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs11963172	8.4166667	5.0277778	0.0941241
GLP1RA	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs880347	-4.177033	2.9330144	0.1544049
GLP1RA	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs9462535	-7.709677	3.7741935	0.0410787
GLP1RA	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs142878626	-5.237327	5.0529954	0.2999784
GLP1RA	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.489225	1.8852801	0.4295731
GLP1RA	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.489225	1.5732915	0.3438597
GLP1RA	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	-6.020557	8.0897164	0.4848566

Insulin	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs4031066	-2.30137	4.8287671	0.63365
TZD	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs4684833	0.3421053	3.0964912	0.9120275
TZD	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs2881654	0.3720406	1.1972943	0.7560025
TZD	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs1373641	-0.846847	2.8873874	0.7692992
TZD	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs2120825	0.7244094	1.2935883	0.5754794
TZD	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs111327339	-2.149547	4.2643505	0.6142096
TZD	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs4135247	-0.605898	1.5281501	0.6917427
TZD	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs1699348	-0.52	5.136	0.9193551
TZD	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs310752	-4.946154	4.4769231	0.2692415
TZD	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs76763697	-0.120536	4.53125	0.978778
TZD	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs2920503	-2.02907	3.494186	0.5614434
TZD	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.085401	0.351679	0.8081309
TZD	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.085401	0.6709977	0.898723
TZD	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	0.9193735	1.1007453	0.4278267
Amylin analog	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs4663804	-5.696078	6	0.3424445
Amylin analog	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs11869741	3.1169916	4.913649	0.52585
Amylin analog	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs12603201	-1.643725	2.3157895	0.4778342
Amylin analog	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs11654396	6.3602941	5.1029412	0.2126184
Amylin analog	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs12941945	-3.240175	4.6724891	0.4880222
Amylin analog	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs1078523	2.1375	3.60625	0.5533679
Amylin analog	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs9905939	2.1558442	3.7077922	0.5609466
Amylin analog	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs59795094	4.1923077	4.4461538	0.3457287
Amylin analog	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs9892728	1.9144737	3.7960526	0.6140276
Amylin analog	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs73111954	1.093617	2.9659574	0.7123341
Amylin analog	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs11772021	0.6666667	2.1449275	0.7559445
Amylin analog	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs4724382	4.8378378	5.7567568	0.4006978
Amylin analog	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs75390434	2.6410256	5.7350427	0.6451526
Amylin analog	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.9208084	0.7053462	0.1917328
Amylin analog	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.9208084	0.9994521	0.3568869
Amylin analog	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.685634	2.4327124	0.7832986
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs4561482	13.128205	4.8888889	0.0072462

SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs8057326	3.6571429	7.4857143	0.6251606
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs34497199	-1.356589	5.2015504	0.7942431
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs142133957	-2.926591	4.8499184	0.5462221
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs11150624	7.557377	4.6803279	0.1063733
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs11865835	2.7565217	5.7826087	0.6335817
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs8057029	13.086207	5.0172414	0.0091007
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs12448775	12.00641	6.4679487	0.0634118
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs8054784	11.783784	5.1531532	0.0222126
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	6.7025314	2.1785399	0.0020936
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	6.7025314	1.7789145	0.0001647
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.202127	5.9777694	0.8463393
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs4561482	13.128205	4.8888889	0.0072462
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs8057326	3.6571429	7.4857143	0.6251606
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs34497199	-1.356589	5.2015504	0.7942431
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs142133957	-2.926591	4.8499184	0.5462221
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs11150624	7.557377	4.6803279	0.1063733
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs11865835	2.7565217	5.7826087	0.6335817
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs8057029	13.086207	5.0172414	0.0091007
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs12448775	12.00641	6.4679487	0.0634118
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs8054784	11.783784	5.1531532	0.0222126
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	6.7025314	2.1785399	0.0020936
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	6.7025314	1.7789145	0.0001647
SGLT2i	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.202127	5.9777694	0.8463393
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs77023203	1.1405117	2.3771028	0.6313763
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs2074312	3.8521081	2.8794324	0.1809613
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs116842927	12.713856	8.326427	0.1267789
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs7110898	12.487617	12.223957	0.3069849
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4937311	-16.0481	8.7442857	0.0664662
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs5219	1.2979879	1.3745222	0.3450065
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4148631	-6.40114	7.8811888	0.4166741
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs10766393	4.8350656	2.8195276	0.0863728

SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs5210	1.4934089	2.4774138	0.5466353
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs10766395	1.4412531	2.5190226	0.5672219
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs189603359	-12.27453	8.3536576	0.1417351
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs10766392	4.8174219	2.7959896	0.0848929
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs7110037	-1.284563	3.2009474	0.688194
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs77902362	-0.746503	6.7562013	0.9120195
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs35271178	0.9483333	1.5428682	0.5387819
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs147673442	5.299171	5.5066839	0.3358908
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs2355016	-0.813561	3.3772222	0.8096353
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs2285676	1.4895073	2.4535122	0.5437899
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs739688	-1.713425	6.0522754	0.7770969
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs79506407	2.7530657	9.4485158	0.7707642
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs7112030	1.8551117	2.5013648	0.4583056
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs117973841	-4.889007	7.4157285	0.509719
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs12816749	-3.316349	6.7651479	0.6239847
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs74732083	-2.965695	5.9383184	0.6174859
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs10841887	1.7979618	3.3930882	0.5961886
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	rs59406438	1.7649239	5.285518	0.7384423
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	1.3755232	0.5172518	0.0078305
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.3755232	0.6106794	0.024294
SU	Pleural mesothelioma	All - MR Egger	3.3538479	1.6064284	0.0476076
AGI	Pleural mesothelioma	rs72681706	4.3389696	7.4495785	0.560267
AGI	Pleural mesothelioma	rs72692396	10.491257	6.6384032	0.1140179
AGI	Pleural mesothelioma	rs174587	6.5278771	6.5926257	0.3220868
AGI	Pleural mesothelioma	rs112968754	-4.655447	7.4328049	0.5310934
AGI	Pleural mesothelioma	rs8037100	-6.149538	9.3580513	0.5110917
AGI	Pleural mesothelioma	rs1659215	-6.563892	9.8542703	0.5053496
AGI	Pleural mesothelioma	rs73402785	-2.477658	7.5713924	0.7434868
AGI	Pleural mesothelioma	rs34359922	-0.272061	7.2819068	0.970197
AGI	Pleural mesothelioma	rs111917515	-4.012214	6.7694096	0.5533834
AGI	Pleural mesothelioma	rs113126535	-4.5544	7.31692	0.5336475

AGI	Pleural mesothelioma	rs112898001	-2.827514	7.3247809	0.6994817
AGI	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4924660	-4.82346	8.3981034	0.5657303
AGI	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	-0.45836	1.6477907	0.7808847
AGI	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.45836	2.1659547	0.8324033
AGI	Pleural mesothelioma	All - MR Egger	8.9097127	8.0017941	0.2915568
DPP-4i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4233648	9.5334677	8.1766935	0.243642
DPP-4i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs2080714	3.7579286	6.672987	0.5733291
DPP-4i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs75850673	9.2629814	9.4454037	0.3267473
DPP-4i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs188581353	4.6412641	7.3630288	0.5284675
DPP-4i	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	6.2089015	1.4956681	3.31E-05
DPP-4i	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	6.2089015	3.8613622	0.1078448
DPP-4i	Pleural mesothelioma	All - MR Egger	3.6347031	8.8068482	0.7198534
Biguanides	Pleural mesothelioma	rs150243609	13.306686	6.509	0.0409188
Biguanides	Pleural mesothelioma	rs17485664	12.643123	7.4758364	0.0907989
Biguanides	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	13.020561	0.328625	0
Biguanides	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	13.020561	4.9090365	0.007993
GLP1RA	Pleural mesothelioma	rs10305525	19.423671	10.695633	0.0693646
GLP1RA	Pleural mesothelioma	rs228817	-9.871783	7.9265116	0.2129799
GLP1RA	Pleural mesothelioma	rs12215108	5.8639896	7.4675648	0.4323004
GLP1RA	Pleural mesothelioma	rs28360624	3.629982	7.965509	0.6485967
GLP1RA	Pleural mesothelioma	rs11963172	-0.371625	6.2983333	0.9529492
GLP1RA	Pleural mesothelioma	rs880347	-1.139866	4.7611005	0.8107859
GLP1RA	Pleural mesothelioma	rs9462535	4.8134774	6.5495484	0.4623805
GLP1RA	Pleural mesothelioma	rs142878626	-3.145599	8.2482258	0.7029311
GLP1RA	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	1.0946158	2.3160437	0.6364821
GLP1RA	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.0946158	2.4567368	0.6559174
GLP1RA	Pleural mesothelioma	All - MR Egger	-0.470736	10.643405	0.9661579
Insulin	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4031066	-1.763774	7.0356849	0.802054
TZD	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4684833	-0.258969	5.1519298	0.9599101
TZD	Pleural mesothelioma	rs2881654	-1.759278	1.6713191	0.2925112
TZD	Pleural mesothelioma	rs1373641	4.4355495	4.6901802	0.3442966

TZD	Pleural mesothelioma	rs2120825	-2.15955	1.7992801	0.23005
TZD	Pleural mesothelioma	rs111327339	0.8394819	5.5614048	0.8800169
TZD	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4135247	0.0733769	2.6650161	0.9780343
TZD	Pleural mesothelioma	rs1699348	-9.58248	7.956544	0.2284535
TZD	Pleural mesothelioma	rs310752	-0.727325	7.6117538	0.9238757
TZD	Pleural mesothelioma	rs76763697	11.006071	8.12375	0.1754807
TZD	Pleural mesothelioma	rs2920503	-1.197663	6.3518605	0.8504431
TZD	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	-1.098594	0.7901505	0.1644195
TZD	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.098594	1.001932	0.2728707
TZD	Pleural mesothelioma	All - MR Egger	-1.825921	1.5956728	0.2855818
Amylin analog	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4663804	7.5357059	10.220882	0.4609489
Amylin analog	Pleural mesothelioma	rs11869741	7.5191643	6.7034819	0.2619983
Amylin analog	Pleural mesothelioma	rs12603201	-1.409	4.0079109	0.7251722
Amylin analog	Pleural mesothelioma	rs11654396	3.3162132	8.3380147	0.690835
Amylin analog	Pleural mesothelioma	rs12941945	-3.200188	5.8353712	0.583409
Amylin analog	Pleural mesothelioma	rs1078523	5.75535	6.1265625	0.3475206
Amylin analog	Pleural mesothelioma	rs9905939	7.0486364	6.4037078	0.2710221
Amylin analog	Pleural mesothelioma	rs59795094	7.79	7.5815231	0.304186
Amylin analog	Pleural mesothelioma	rs9892728	5.8225987	6.4558355	0.3671034
Amylin analog	Pleural mesothelioma	rs73111954	2.735017	4.949234	0.5805276
Amylin analog	Pleural mesothelioma	rs11772021	-2.000081	2.7796273	0.4718021
Amylin analog	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4724382	-0.927468	8.961964	0.9175745
Amylin analog	Pleural mesothelioma	rs75390434	-11.23436	10.530855	0.2860603
Amylin analog	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	1.0566157	1.2449675	0.396043
Amylin analog	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.0566157	1.5394279	0.4924804
Amylin analog	Pleural mesothelioma	All - MR Egger	-2.727408	3.4575829	0.4468857
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4561482	-0.060206	8.503453	0.9943509
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs8057326	-7.666695	9.3277714	0.4111216
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs34497199	-3.344512	7.6358217	0.6613842
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs142133957	-6.811387	6.2090212	0.272635
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs11150624	1.0069672	8.163959	0.9018355

SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs11865835	2.6784957	9.4501739	0.7768446
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs8057029	-0.511727	8.9017241	0.9541579
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs12448775	-7.417788	8.0166346	0.3548101
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs8054784	-1.783667	9.0496396	0.8437508
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	-3.122483	1.2723663	0.0141247
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.122483	2.7216083	0.2512603
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	All - MR Egger	-8.442764	6.6100303	0.2422388
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4561482	-0.060206	8.503453	0.9943509
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs8057326	-7.666695	9.3277714	0.4111216
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs34497199	-3.344512	7.6358217	0.6613842
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs142133957	-6.811387	6.2090212	0.272635
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs11150624	1.0069672	8.163959	0.9018355
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs11865835	2.6784957	9.4501739	0.7768446
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs8057029	-0.511727	8.9017241	0.9541579
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs12448775	-7.417788	8.0166346	0.3548101
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	rs8054784	-1.783667	9.0496396	0.8437508
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	-3.122483	1.2723663	0.0141247
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.122483	2.7216083	0.2512603
SGLT2i	Pleural mesothelioma	All - MR Egger	-8.442764	6.6100303	0.2422388
SU	Prostate cancer	rs77023203	0.2217278	0.4041145	0.583228
SU	Prostate cancer	rs2074312	0.6789135	0.4896054	0.1655472
SU	Prostate cancer	rs116842927	0.3430153	1.4090109	0.8076615
SU	Prostate cancer	rs7110898	2.8876894	2.0793702	0.1649141
SU	Prostate cancer	rs4937311	0.2665278	1.4833571	0.8574048
SU	Prostate cancer	rs5219	0.1590323	0.2332194	0.4953022
SU	Prostate cancer	rs4148631	0.4705287	1.3396434	0.7254126
SU	Prostate cancer	rs10766393	0.5873858	0.4797507	0.2208178
SU	Prostate cancer	rs5210	0.2838005	0.4210837	0.5003263
SU	Prostate cancer	rs10766395	0.2610627	0.4282381	0.5421133
SU	Prostate cancer	rs189603359	0.6574436	1.439179	0.6478015
SU	Prostate cancer	rs10766392	0.4743568	0.4756406	0.3186185

SU	Prostate cancer	rs7110037	0.3509316	0.5430421	0.5181286
SU	Prostate cancer	rs77902362	-1.030968	1.1516104	0.3706589
SU	Prostate cancer	rs35271178	0.2352946	0.2618264	0.3688303
SU	Prostate cancer	rs147673442	-0.540611	0.9343264	0.5628518
SU	Prostate cancer	rs2355016	0.3988361	0.5729778	0.4863812
SU	Prostate cancer	rs2285676	0.2861512	0.4170317	0.4926111
SU	Prostate cancer	rs739688	0.5978437	1.0289461	0.5612234
SU	Prostate cancer	rs79506407	1.5599319	1.5976472	0.3288696
SU	Prostate cancer	rs7112030	0.2328521	0.4251538	0.5839054
SU	Prostate cancer	rs117973841	1.359457	1.2612748	0.2811036
SU	Prostate cancer	rs12816749	0.7709172	1.1492367	0.5023429
SU	Prostate cancer	rs74732083	-0.990067	1.0158184	0.329734
SU	Prostate cancer	rs10841887	-1.154694	0.5774588	0.0455421
SU	Prostate cancer	rs59406438	1.9949641	0.8959915	0.0259778
SU	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.2623958	0.0889772	0.0031878
SU	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.2623958	0.1037458	0.0114317
SU	Prostate cancer	All - MR Egger	0.1337359	0.2727423	0.6283477
AGI	Prostate cancer	rs72681706	0.7455246	1.2640375	0.5553272
AGI	Prostate cancer	rs72692396	-0.276054	1.1217585	0.8056123
AGI	Prostate cancer	rs174587	1.3730559	1.1197821	0.2201305
AGI	Prostate cancer	rs112968754	0.4242805	1.2621341	0.7367493
AGI	Prostate cancer	rs8037100	0.6022872	1.5885333	0.7045789
AGI	Prostate cancer	rs1659215	0.3665703	1.6729514	0.8265598
AGI	Prostate cancer	rs73402785	0.4241013	1.2849325	0.7413567
AGI	Prostate cancer	rs34359922	1.1559746	1.2373814	0.3501954
AGI	Prostate cancer	rs111917515	-0.07285	1.1491476	0.9494522
AGI	Prostate cancer	rs113126535	0.442076	1.24254	0.7220022
AGI	Prostate cancer	rs112898001	0.523502	1.243259	0.6737022
AGI	Prostate cancer	rs4924660	1.7952011	1.4246494	0.2076332
AGI	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.6003705	0.172598	0.0005044
AGI	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.6003705	0.367537	0.1023646

AGI	Prostate cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.799951	1.3555143	0.5681881
DPP-4i	Prostate cancer	rs4233648	1.3650565	1.389121	0.3257667
DPP-4i	Prostate cancer	rs2080714	-0.519441	1.1337662	0.6468409
DPP-4i	Prostate cancer	rs75850673	-0.122203	1.6010435	0.9391588
DPP-4i	Prostate cancer	rs188581353	-0.973741	1.2633417	0.4408456
DPP-4i	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.153259	0.4980511	0.7582967
DPP-4i	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.153259	0.6575464	0.815701
DPP-4i	Prostate cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.503056	1.5101776	0.4244691
Biguanides	Prostate cancer	rs150243609	-0.715094	1.1243586	0.5247751
Biguanides	Prostate cancer	rs17485664	-0.970513	1.274658	0.4464236
Biguanides	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.826864	0.1267107	6.77E-11
Biguanides	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.826864	0.8431981	0.3267759
GLP1RA	Prostate cancer	rs10305525	-2.907196	1.817943	0.1097833
GLP1RA	Prostate cancer	rs228817	-1.66062	1.3462481	0.2173829
GLP1RA	Prostate cancer	rs12215108	1.6974922	1.2685959	0.1808679
GLP1RA	Prostate cancer	rs28360624	1.8448743	1.3485928	0.1713122
GLP1RA	Prostate cancer	rs11963172	0.7330889	1.0685667	0.4926823
GLP1RA	Prostate cancer	rs880347	1.6693828	0.8091866	0.039109
GLP1RA	Prostate cancer	rs9462535	3.0969613	1.1130774	0.0053968
GLP1RA	Prostate cancer	rs142878626	-1.025	1.409947	0.4672396
GLP1RA	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.9494904	0.6224458	0.1271548
GLP1RA	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.9494904	0.417438	0.022932
GLP1RA	Prostate cancer	All - MR Egger	1.0003233	2.8756141	0.7398211
Insulin	Prostate cancer	rs4031066	2.2892192	1.1967808	0.0557719
TZD	Prostate cancer	rs4684833	1.667114	0.8743728	0.0565672
TZD	Prostate cancer	rs2881654	-0.087844	0.2848343	0.7577757
TZD	Prostate cancer	rs1373641	-2.361707	0.7967342	0.0030344
TZD	Prostate cancer	rs2120825	0.099572	0.3068054	0.7455259
TZD	Prostate cancer	rs111327339	-0.144313	0.9477976	0.8789811
TZD	Prostate cancer	rs4135247	-1.076745	0.453866	0.0176736
TZD	Prostate cancer	rs1699348	0.4799232	1.351208	0.7224541

TZD	Prostate cancer	rs310752	-1.493962	1.2918769	0.2475065
TZD	Prostate cancer	rs76763697	-0.356281	1.3755759	0.7956315
TZD	Prostate cancer	rs2920503	-0.632291	1.0790291	0.5578882
TZD	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.242209	0.2422437	0.3173801
TZD	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.242209	0.1706605	0.155828
TZD	Prostate cancer	All - MR Egger	0.0524778	0.3866447	0.8953909
Amylin analog	Prostate cancer	rs4663804	1.5461863	1.7378627	0.373624
Amylin analog	Prostate cancer	rs11869741	-0.349989	1.1367242	0.7581641
Amylin analog	Prostate cancer	rs12603201	0.6301336	0.6812834	0.3550068
Amylin analog	Prostate cancer	rs11654396	0.7066007	1.4167426	0.6179553
Amylin analog	Prostate cancer	rs12941945	-1.80741	0.9915022	0.0683184
Amylin analog	Prostate cancer	rs1078523	-0.677475	1.0411688	0.5152485
Amylin analog	Prostate cancer	rs9905939	-0.896766	1.0881688	0.4098795
Amylin analog	Prostate cancer	rs59795094	-0.991654	1.2883615	0.441477
Amylin analog	Prostate cancer	rs9892728	-0.771724	1.0970263	0.4817637
Amylin analog	Prostate cancer	rs73111954	0.2250017	0.8409277	0.7890352
Amylin analog	Prostate cancer	rs11772021	0.3925611	0.4732443	0.4068157
Amylin analog	Prostate cancer	rs4724382	-1.404991	1.5220631	0.3559638
Amylin analog	Prostate cancer	rs75390434	-0.452895	1.7880855	0.8000481
Amylin analog	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.08123	0.2277004	0.7212865
Amylin analog	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.08123	0.2617215	0.7562816
Amylin analog	Prostate cancer	All - MR Egger	0.5191535	0.5881484	0.3962834
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	rs4561482	1.7525726	1.4450513	0.2252025
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	rs8057326	0.8359048	1.5834095	0.5975587
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	rs34497199	0.4903698	1.2960078	0.7051561
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	rs142133957	0.0969299	1.050584	0.9264892
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	rs11150624	0.3340303	1.386418	0.809609
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	rs11865835	-1.996983	1.6051652	0.2134635
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	rs8057029	0.8676293	1.5121034	0.5661102
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	rs12448775	-0.589936	1.3703429	0.6668302
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	rs8054784	0.442264	1.535955	0.7733921

SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.257186	0.318329	0.4191338
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.257186	0.462188	0.5779011
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.286573	1.1213424	0.8056357
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	rs4561482	1.7525726	1.4450513	0.2252025
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	rs8057326	0.8359048	1.5834095	0.5975587
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	rs34497199	0.4903698	1.2960078	0.7051561
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	rs142133957	0.0969299	1.050584	0.9264892
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	rs11150624	0.3340303	1.386418	0.809609
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	rs11865835	-1.996983	1.6051652	0.2134635
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	rs8057029	0.8676293	1.5121034	0.5661102
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	rs12448775	-0.589936	1.3703429	0.6668302
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	rs8054784	0.442264	1.535955	0.7733921
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.257186	0.318329	0.4191338
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.257186	0.462188	0.5779011
SGLT2i	Prostate cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.286573	1.1213424	0.8056357
SU	Rectal cancer	rs77023203	-0.702325	0.8996402	0.4349949
SU	Rectal cancer	rs2074312	-1.376811	1.0889784	0.2061173
SU	Rectal cancer	rs116842927	1.8151264	3.1502397	0.564489
SU	Rectal cancer	rs7110898	-9.681277	4.6357021	0.0367603
SU	Rectal cancer	rs4937311	-0.254844	3.3078175	0.9385895
SU	Rectal cancer	rs5219	0.4533943	0.5196164	0.3829052
SU	Rectal cancer	rs4148631	5.0685524	2.980986	0.0890757
SU	Rectal cancer	rs10766393	-1.065066	1.0666955	0.3180505
SU	Rectal cancer	rs5210	-0.712047	0.9379187	0.4477464
SU	Rectal cancer	rs10766395	-0.932416	0.9538195	0.3282919
SU	Rectal cancer	rs189603359	0.7037821	3.1926654	0.8255307
SU	Rectal cancer	rs10766392	-1.130104	1.0576406	0.2852886
SU	Rectal cancer	rs7110037	2.3993632	1.2103342	0.0474348
SU	Rectal cancer	rs77902362	-1.205594	2.5581753	0.6374471
SU	Rectal cancer	rs35271178	0.3553163	0.5836016	0.5426347
SU	Rectal cancer	rs147673442	0.6124637	2.085215	0.7689739

SU	Rectal cancer	rs2355016	2.2662639	1.276625	0.075865
SU	Rectal cancer	rs2285676	-0.7305	0.9288854	0.4316177
SU	Rectal cancer	rs739688	1.7315928	2.294503	0.4504469
SU	Rectal cancer	rs79506407	1.3221436	3.5689294	0.7110402
SU	Rectal cancer	rs7112030	-0.849777	0.9468089	0.3694434
SU	Rectal cancer	rs117973841	-8.381126	2.8252119	0.0030116
SU	Rectal cancer	rs12816749	0.5855036	2.5628343	0.8192891
SU	Rectal cancer	rs74732083	1.1615247	2.2505381	0.6057778
SU	Rectal cancer	rs10841887	-0.827256	1.28315	0.519117
SU	Rectal cancer	rs59406438	1.0179175	1.9965814	0.6101704
SU	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.111781	0.2683807	0.6770429
SU	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.111781	0.2310521	0.628534
SU	Rectal cancer	All - MR Egger	0.0806202	0.7193023	0.9116913
AGI	Rectal cancer	rs72681706	-2.159316	2.8369789	0.4465781
AGI	Rectal cancer	rs72692396	0.2274251	2.5261277	0.928264
AGI	Rectal cancer	rs174587	1.0654022	2.4978101	0.6697184
AGI	Rectal cancer	rs112968754	1.8303008	2.8117439	0.5150797
AGI	Rectal cancer	rs8037100	0.834841	3.5389846	0.8135115
AGI	Rectal cancer	rs1659215	0.5018292	3.7271784	0.8928961
AGI	Rectal cancer	rs73402785	3.8197089	2.8626034	0.1820899
AGI	Rectal cancer	rs34359922	1.9194195	2.7583178	0.4865128
AGI	Rectal cancer	rs111917515	0.9185572	2.5603137	0.7197691
AGI	Rectal cancer	rs113126535	0.702348	2.767248	0.7996444
AGI	Rectal cancer	rs112898001	0.4127371	2.7688765	0.8815039
AGI	Rectal cancer	rs4924660	-0.741862	3.1766437	0.8153449
AGI	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.8097093	0.4159432	0.0515728
AGI	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.8097093	0.8204191	0.3236692
AGI	Rectal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.622164	3.040251	0.8419567
DPP-4i	Rectal cancer	rs4233648	-4.602831	3.0973952	0.1372705
DPP-4i	Rectal cancer	rs2080714	-0.277548	2.5229221	0.912401
DPP-4i	Rectal cancer	rs75850673	-6.119087	3.5737205	0.0868514

DPP-4i	Rectal cancer	rs188581353	-1.396158	2.7994243	0.6179694
DPP-4i	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.526846	1.3132885	0.0543471
DPP-4i	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.526846	1.4629483	0.0841267
DPP-4i	Rectal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.808502	3.4236878	0.8352977
Biguanides	Rectal cancer	rs150243609	-1.733714	2.5117143	0.4900361
Biguanides	Rectal cancer	rs17485664	6.3366543	2.8412119	0.0257299
Biguanides	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.8065763	4.0047213	0.6519091
Biguanides	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.8065763	1.8818127	0.3370456
GLP1RA	Rectal cancer	rs10305525	2.9886076	4.0543797	0.4610429
GLP1RA	Rectal cancer	rs228817	4.2537054	3.0005969	0.1563018
GLP1RA	Rectal cancer	rs12215108	-3.792358	2.8252591	0.1794973
GLP1RA	Rectal cancer	rs28360624	-1.972515	3.002982	0.511276
GLP1RA	Rectal cancer	rs11963172	2.1338167	2.3797222	0.369897
GLP1RA	Rectal cancer	rs880347	3.2445646	1.8002392	0.0714988
GLP1RA	Rectal cancer	rs9462535	-0.127608	2.4756903	0.9588918
GLP1RA	Rectal cancer	rs142878626	5.0334332	3.1181567	0.1064768
GLP1RA	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.5831478	1.0259704	0.1228129
GLP1RA	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.5831478	0.928788	0.088282
GLP1RA	Rectal cancer	All - MR Egger	4.3076722	4.5845924	0.3836927
Insulin	Rectal cancer	rs4031066	-0.029897	2.6669932	0.991056
TZD	Rectal cancer	rs4684833	0.1614491	1.9525789	0.934102
TZD	Rectal cancer	rs2881654	0.9628591	0.6348151	0.1293285
TZD	Rectal cancer	rs1373641	2.646964	1.7727973	0.135411
TZD	Rectal cancer	rs2120825	0.5870304	0.6824826	0.389712
TZD	Rectal cancer	rs111327339	-1.660257	2.1093958	0.4312368
TZD	Rectal cancer	rs4135247	1.4597855	1.0097131	0.1482493
TZD	Rectal cancer	rs1699348	-2.472552	3.01404	0.4120196
TZD	Rectal cancer	rs310752	2.7567385	2.8806538	0.3385755
TZD	Rectal cancer	rs76763697	5.2689732	3.0682768	0.085935
TZD	Rectal cancer	rs2920503	0.5525459	2.4061221	0.8183702
TZD	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.9110406	0.3310585	0.005925

TZD	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.9110406	0.3800336	0.016518
TZD	Rectal cancer	All - MR Egger	0.6926776	0.6053377	0.2855867
Amylin analog	Rectal cancer	rs4663804	4.4226471	3.8699314	0.253112
Amylin analog	Rectal cancer	rs11869741	-3.390585	2.5347827	0.1810192
Amylin analog	Rectal cancer	rs12603201	0.3828838	1.5167368	0.8007016
Amylin analog	Rectal cancer	rs11654396	-3.202603	3.1584485	0.3105924
Amylin analog	Rectal cancer	rs12941945	-2.461537	2.2077948	0.2648803
Amylin analog	Rectal cancer	rs1078523	-1.351269	2.3201438	0.5602923
Amylin analog	Rectal cancer	rs9905939	-0.613429	2.4245065	0.8002589
Amylin analog	Rectal cancer	rs59795094	-1.593877	2.8707769	0.5787527
Amylin analog	Rectal cancer	rs9892728	-1.403197	2.4448289	0.566005
Amylin analog	Rectal cancer	rs73111954	-1.818689	1.8732851	0.3316202
Amylin analog	Rectal cancer	rs11772021	-0.123887	1.0558095	0.9065919
Amylin analog	Rectal cancer	rs4724382	-1.965171	3.3972432	0.5629532
Amylin analog	Rectal cancer	rs75390434	3.5684017	3.9809145	0.3700512
Amylin analog	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.765628	0.4404961	0.0821925
Amylin analog	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.765628	0.5833295	0.1893468
Amylin analog	Rectal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.855974	1.3115545	0.5273916
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	rs4561482	2.2215556	3.2217009	0.490471
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	rs8057326	-6.479743	3.5283143	0.066284
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	rs34497199	-4.841574	2.8901938	0.0939004
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	rs142133957	-0.738478	2.3516313	0.7534998
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	rs11150624	-1.241574	3.0878934	0.6876267
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	rs11865835	-6.368878	3.5724696	0.0746244
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	rs8057029	2.1260431	3.3704397	0.5281772
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	rs12448775	-1.88026	3.0408013	0.536349
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	rs8054784	0.8038441	3.4238468	0.814381
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.694901	1.0445937	0.1046865
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.694901	1.0303659	0.0999799
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.817919	2.6897111	0.7698986
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	rs4561482	2.2215556	3.2217009	0.490471

SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	rs8057326	-6.479743	3.5283143	0.066284
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	rs34497199	-4.841574	2.8901938	0.0939004
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	rs142133957	-0.738478	2.3516313	0.7534998
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	rs11150624	-1.241574	3.0878934	0.6876267
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	rs11865835	-6.368878	3.5724696	0.0746244
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	rs8057029	2.1260431	3.3704397	0.5281772
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	rs12448775	-1.88026	3.0408013	0.536349
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	rs8054784	0.8038441	3.4238468	0.814381
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.694901	1.0445937	0.1046865
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.694901	1.0303659	0.0999799
SGLT2i	Rectal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.817919	2.6897111	0.7698986
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs77023203	4.6149766	3.3567757	0.1691859
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs2074312	1.8921162	4.0573243	0.640968
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs116842927	-16.04706	11.774336	0.1729189
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs7110898	18.309191	17.150638	0.2857228
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4937311	-3.425714	12.362381	0.7816972
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs5219	0.5029919	1.9380215	0.7952195
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4148631	-16.72427	11.139161	0.1332538
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs10766393	3.8631759	3.9735958	0.3309453
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs5210	4.3738916	3.5015271	0.2116145
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs10766395	3.8649875	3.5616792	0.2778513
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs189603359	1.699893	11.769844	0.8851626
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs10766392	3.8509375	3.9400781	0.3283831
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs7110037	-5.862711	4.5238684	0.1949925
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs77902362	1.7321851	9.5171104	0.8555769
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs35271178	0.5654543	2.1778295	0.7951405
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs147673442	1.6698627	7.7932902	0.8303371
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs2355016	-6.830444	4.7699722	0.1521532
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs2285676	4.3435854	3.4677805	0.2103677
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs739688	-15.67048	8.57	0.0674705
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs79506407	17.14219	13.589854	0.2071661

SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs7112030	3.8000993	3.5334739	0.2821702
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs117973841	-2.26696	10.569669	0.8301744
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs12816749	8.2324852	9.5839053	0.3903457
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs74732083	-6.606637	8.4812556	0.4359979
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs10841887	1.92695	4.7787353	0.6867759
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs59406438	1.4010085	7.4356448	0.8505491
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.3568963	0.8235266	0.0994213
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.3568963	0.8621426	0.1155186
SU	Salivary gland carcinoma	All - MR Egger	3.2613345	2.2689763	0.1635267
AGI	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs72681706	4.7335129	10.583091	0.6546792
AGI	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs72692396	6.2688623	9.4182834	0.5056632
AGI	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs174587	-2.14362	9.3255307	0.8181961
AGI	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs112968754	26.189959	10.518496	0.0127781
AGI	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs8037100	29.049846	13.159128	0.0272735
AGI	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs1659215	30.720216	13.859784	0.0266573
AGI	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs73402785	24.366962	10.681519	0.0225351
AGI	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs34359922	20.928559	10.274915	0.0416641
AGI	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs111917515	19.542325	9.5098155	0.0398825
AGI	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs113126535	22.99732	10.29056	0.0254306
AGI	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs112898001	23.560359	10.310717	0.0223107
AGI	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4924660	27.268851	11.879828	0.0217107
AGI	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	17.883082	3.1318517	1.13E-08
AGI	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	17.883082	3.0578145	4.97E-09
AGI	Salivary gland carcinoma	All - MR Egger	6.416147	11.582465	0.5917813
DPP-4i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4233648	2.1183145	11.588871	0.8549638
DPP-4i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs2080714	16.212792	9.4118182	0.084961
DPP-4i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs75850673	5.0346522	13.337453	0.7058152
DPP-4i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs188581353	-4.169274	10.323354	0.6863097
DPP-4i	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	5.5714305	4.7242386	0.2382673
DPP-4i	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	5.5714305	5.4441391	0.3061276
DPP-4i	Salivary gland carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-4.563601	12.355255	0.7472963

Biguanides	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs150243609	-8.190771	9.4027429	0.3836971
Biguanides	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs17485664	-9.506543	10.607398	0.3701362
Biguanides	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-8.769731	0.6531341	4.19E-41
Biguanides	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-8.769731	7.0362731	0.2126322
GLP1RA	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs10305525	5.2247785	15.062342	0.7286838
GLP1RA	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs228817	19.721395	11.230155	0.0790695
GLP1RA	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs12215108	-6.957927	10.563005	0.5100838
GLP1RA	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs28360624	0.1068874	11.228862	0.9924051
GLP1RA	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs11963172	7.357	8.9000556	0.4084502
GLP1RA	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs880347	3.8983493	6.7104306	0.5612817
GLP1RA	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs9462535	10.574258	9.2374839	0.2523285
GLP1RA	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs142878626	-5.576221	11.571959	0.6298957
GLP1RA	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	4.5600718	2.769741	0.0996836
GLP1RA	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	4.5600718	3.4658543	0.1882702
GLP1RA	Salivary gland carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-18.4785	14.73811	0.256556
Insulin	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4031066	5.4238151	9.9565068	0.5859249
TZD	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4684833	-4.733377	7.2992105	0.5166759
TZD	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs2881654	-0.200054	2.3658625	0.9326123
TZD	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs1373641	3.2468964	6.6122523	0.6233964
TZD	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs2120825	0.057437	2.5398988	0.9819583
TZD	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs111327339	-3.346511	7.8424773	0.6695862
TZD	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4135247	0.5496729	3.7727882	0.8841629
TZD	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs1699348	2.616368	11.2656	0.8163485
TZD	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs310752	-2.364146	10.755231	0.8260163
TZD	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs76763697	-10.38929	11.410714	0.3625667
TZD	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs2920503	8.987907	8.9804651	0.3169096
TZD	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.050921	0.7906488	0.948648
TZD	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.050921	1.4164408	0.971322
TZD	Salivary gland carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.48718	2.2558334	0.8344202
Amylin analog	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4663804	-5.626422	14.469118	0.6973817
Amylin analog	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs11869741	4.2827855	9.4698607	0.6510858

Amylin analog	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs12603201	-4.438826	5.6652227	0.4333207
Amylin analog	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs11654396	3.4003971	11.796397	0.7731498
Amylin analog	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs12941945	4.1451834	8.2409607	0.614966
Amylin analog	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs1078523	-0.099946	8.670375	0.9908028
Amylin analog	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs9905939	-0.52021	9.0538961	0.9541812
Amylin analog	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs59795094	-3.105885	10.728769	0.7722055
Amylin analog	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs9892728	-0.356399	9.1359868	0.9688821
Amylin analog	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs73111954	0.4867234	7.0108936	0.9446522
Amylin analog	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs11772021	-4.321822	3.9431677	0.2730666
Amylin analog	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4724382	7.6668829	12.685315	0.5455841
Amylin analog	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs75390434	-16.83342	14.851624	0.2570297
Amylin analog	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-1.745729	1.1950652	0.1440755
Amylin analog	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.745729	2.1792055	0.4230825
Amylin analog	Salivary gland carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-3.29912	4.8989585	0.5145724
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4561482	-19.95436	12.028803	0.0971397
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs8057326	-12.85571	13.170476	0.3290144
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs34497199	-22.41884	10.802093	0.037948
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs142133957	-11.76958	8.6884992	0.1755401
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs11150624	-7.190189	11.529426	0.5328653
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs11865835	7.8395913	13.320522	0.5561733
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs8057029	-8.949483	12.578879	0.4767937
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs12448775	-1.684904	11.277949	0.8812395
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs8054784	-8.628171	12.783243	0.4997015
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-10.19196	2.8795476	0.000401
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-10.19196	3.8361397	0.007888
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-8.763592	9.2650724	0.3757102
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4561482	-19.95436	12.028803	0.0971397
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs8057326	-12.85571	13.170476	0.3290144
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs34497199	-22.41884	10.802093	0.037948
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs142133957	-11.76958	8.6884992	0.1755401
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs11150624	-7.190189	11.529426	0.5328653

SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs11865835	7.8395913	13.320522	0.5561733
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs8057029	-8.949483	12.578879	0.4767937
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs12448775	-1.684904	11.277949	0.8812395
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs8054784	-8.628171	12.783243	0.4997015
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-10.19196	2.8795476	0.000401
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-10.19196	3.8361397	0.007888
SGLT2i	Salivary gland carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-8.763592	9.2650724	0.3757102
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs77023203	-0.257664	0.7280607	0.7234109
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs2074312	-0.839838	0.8711892	0.3350393
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs116842927	-1.859956	2.5639651	0.4681933
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs7110898	0.3938298	4.0215745	0.9219885
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs4937311	0.3834127	2.587619	0.882207
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs5219	-0.112221	0.4104172	0.784522
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs4148631	0.4398601	2.409021	0.8551207
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs10766393	-0.36979	0.8549081	0.6653421
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs5210	-0.313744	0.746133	0.6741252
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs10766395	-0.475489	0.7630075	0.5331682
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs189603359	2.4415564	2.2910895	0.2865707
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs10766392	-0.362188	0.8460417	0.6685808
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs77902362	-0.425195	2.4618182	0.8628749
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs35271178	-0.289287	0.4632093	0.5322814
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs147673442	1.1736269	1.5664508	0.4537205
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs2285676	-0.287805	0.7387561	0.6968469
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs739688	0.9341916	1.8706587	0.6175034
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs79506407	1.8646472	2.6983455	0.4895445
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs7112030	-0.51134	0.7535484	0.4974065
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs117973841	0.390894	2.4909934	0.8753056
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs12816749	-0.767633	2.1243195	0.7178342
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs74732083	2.6521076	2.2024888	0.228535
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs10841887	1.8326471	1.0041765	0.0679973
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs59406438	1.7271459	1.7816279	0.3323356

SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.122942	0.1357956	0.3652831
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.122942	0.1914195	0.5207021
SU	Small cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.328625	0.4857713	0.5057728
AGI	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs72681706	5.9711944	2.2735363	0.0086296
AGI	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs72692396	2.2722156	2.2046507	0.3027066
AGI	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs174587	0.6397765	2.133352	0.7642591
AGI	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs112968754	0.5489024	2.2240244	0.8050584
AGI	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs8037100	0.442	2.7715897	0.8732944
AGI	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs1659215	0.8696757	2.9358378	0.7670564
AGI	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs73402785	0.2094515	2.266962	0.9263858
AGI	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs34359922	0.4770339	2.1941525	0.8278877
AGI	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs111917515	0.6102583	2.0205535	0.7626328
AGI	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs113126535	0.80664	2.186	0.7121257
AGI	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs112898001	0.2822311	2.188247	0.8973767
AGI	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs4924660	0.2267816	2.5031609	0.9278119
AGI	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.1281248	0.4718974	0.0168202
AGI	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.1281248	0.660496	0.087637
AGI	Small cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	4.9531427	2.5313422	0.0788636
DPP-4i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs4233648	0.4912903	2.6124194	0.85083
DPP-4i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs2080714	0.0248701	2.0777273	0.9904497
DPP-4i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs75850673	0.0952795	2.9773913	0.9744713
DPP-4i	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.1802447	0.1447797	0.213147
DPP-4i	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.1802447	1.4271511	0.899497
DPP-4i	Small cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-1.584059	12.876632	0.9220758
Biguanides	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs17485664	-3.648513	2.3566543	0.1215802
GLP1RA	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs10305525	-3.283608	3.4158861	0.3364137
GLP1RA	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs228817	1.7921705	2.4052713	0.4562105
GLP1RA	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs12215108	4.2251813	2.2818653	0.0640783
GLP1RA	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs28360624	-3.037126	2.3638922	0.1988626
GLP1RA	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs11963172	-1.2755	1.9701111	0.5173567
GLP1RA	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs880347	-0.999091	1.4714354	0.4971438

GLP1RA	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs9462535	1.911871	1.9568387	0.3285591
GLP1RA	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs142878626	0.7154147	2.7797696	0.7968972
GLP1RA	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.056397	0.8332042	0.9460348
GLP1RA	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.056397	0.7581773	0.940704
GLP1RA	Small cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.793247	3.9950767	0.8491669
Insulin	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs4031066	-0.564932	2.2984247	0.8058442
TZD	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs2881654	-0.440282	0.498106	0.3767437
TZD	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs2120825	-0.248335	0.5243532	0.6357831
TZD	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs111327339	-1.599184	1.8794864	0.3948458
TZD	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs4135247	-0.787828	0.8148257	0.3336103
TZD	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs1699348	3.724	2.38368	0.1182196
TZD	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs310752	1.7999231	2.3046154	0.4347978
TZD	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs76763697	3.6145982	2.6668304	0.175293
TZD	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs2920503	2.9113953	1.8966279	0.1247746
TZD	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.195824	0.3643616	0.5909612
TZD	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.195824	0.312505	0.5309042
TZD	Small cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-1.068128	0.4820827	0.0686071
Amylin analog	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs4663804	-4.187745	3.0366667	0.1678763
Amylin analog	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs12603201	1.6497166	1.2223077	0.1771207
Amylin analog	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs11654396	2.5436765	2.4820588	0.3054457
Amylin analog	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs1078523	-0.751313	1.857125	0.6858033
Amylin analog	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs9905939	-0.712468	1.9644805	0.7168478
Amylin analog	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs59795094	-1.57	2.2954615	0.4940015
Amylin analog	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs9892728	-1.203092	1.9636184	0.5400804
Amylin analog	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs73111954	0.0248511	1.5545532	0.9872456
Amylin analog	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs11772021	1.0986335	0.846087	0.1941198
Amylin analog	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs4724382	-4.520991	2.7275676	0.0974149
Amylin analog	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs75390434	1.6966667	3.1721368	0.5927428
Amylin analog	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.290354	0.5084421	0.5679548
Amylin analog	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.290354	0.5010782	0.5622798
Amylin analog	Small cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	2.3746907	1.1009111	0.0593544

SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs4561482	2.4781197	2.5835043	0.3374536
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs8057326	1.0612381	2.822381	0.7069109
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs34497199	-0.065581	2.3320155	0.9775647
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs142133957	0.5200489	2.5310604	0.8372074
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs11150624	1.6746721	2.4529508	0.4947855
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs11865835	0.6289565	2.9367826	0.8304183
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs8057029	2.0010345	2.6443966	0.4492252
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs12448775	0.1692628	2.9288141	0.9539141
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs8054784	0.4053153	2.73	0.8819741
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.9952812	0.3009112	0.0009411
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.9952812	0.8800285	0.2580699
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.0814629	2.5853336	0.9757427
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs4561482	2.4781197	2.5835043	0.3374536
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs8057326	1.0612381	2.822381	0.7069109
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs34497199	-0.065581	2.3320155	0.9775647
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs142133957	0.5200489	2.5310604	0.8372074
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs11150624	1.6746721	2.4529508	0.4947855
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs11865835	0.6289565	2.9367826	0.8304183
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs8057029	2.0010345	2.6443966	0.4492252
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs12448775	0.1692628	2.9288141	0.9539141
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs8054784	0.4053153	2.73	0.8819741
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.9952812	0.3009112	0.0009411
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.9952812	0.8800285	0.2580699
SGLT2i	Small cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.0814629	2.5853336	0.9757427
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs77023203	3.3610047	2.6241355	0.2002623
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs2074312	5.1236216	3.175027	0.106587
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs116842927	-1.097867	9.192244	0.9049315
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs7110898	16.498979	13.488298	0.2212516
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs4937311	7.8300556	9.6531746	0.4172865
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs5219	0.1478022	1.5163122	0.9223494
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs4148631	-10.36769	8.7072028	0.2337702

SU	Small intestine cancer	rs10766393	4.5464829	3.1093701	0.1436898
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs5210	2.4894581	2.7363793	0.3629472
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs10766395	1.8018697	2.7830827	0.5173494
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs189603359	-2.088891	9.2917121	0.8221253
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs10766392	4.5297917	3.0832292	0.1417863
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs7110037	0.8451316	3.5353421	0.811065
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs77902362	-5.17763	7.4799026	0.4888083
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs35271178	1.4502155	1.7034729	0.3945867
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs147673442	-8.034301	6.0693264	0.1855845
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs2355016	-1.057944	3.7291111	0.7766412
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs2285676	2.477	2.7100488	0.3607139
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs739688	-11.21401	6.7005389	0.0942095
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs79506407	-2.639513	10.536983	0.8022008
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs7112030	3.0117866	2.7618362	0.2754923
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs117973841	-1.974328	8.231457	0.8104453
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs12816749	8.1393491	7.4797041	0.2765107
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs74732083	-5.410404	6.6222646	0.4139273
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs10841887	5.1900882	3.7388235	0.1650881
SU	Small intestine cancer	rs59406438	10.278689	5.8419239	0.0784977
SU	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.7628251	0.6254266	0.0048234
SU	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.7628251	0.6742253	0.0089334
SU	Small intestine cancer	All - MR Egger	1.739508	1.7740844	0.3366157
AGI	Small intestine cancer	rs72681706	2.6501874	8.2779625	0.7488548
AGI	Small intestine cancer	rs72692396	6.77501	7.3747705	0.3582661
AGI	Small intestine cancer	rs174587	-9.03838	7.3026257	0.2158314
AGI	Small intestine cancer	rs112968754	15.392602	8.1917886	0.0602406
AGI	Small intestine cancer	rs8037100	12.828103	10.310872	0.2134504
AGI	Small intestine cancer	rs1659215	13.447297	10.858324	0.2155559
AGI	Small intestine cancer	rs73402785	15.135865	8.3466245	0.0697684
AGI	Small intestine cancer	rs34359922	16.043898	8.0430932	0.046071
AGI	Small intestine cancer	rs111917515	11.315351	7.460738	0.1293543

AGI	Small intestine cancer	rs113126535	10.32836	8.06312	0.2002153
AGI	Small intestine cancer	rs112898001	12.872669	8.0679283	0.1105924
AGI	Small intestine cancer	rs4924660	1.4338678	9.2807471	0.8772162
AGI	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	8.5866331	2.2805075	0.0001664
AGI	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	8.5866331	2.3928293	0.0003326
AGI	Small intestine cancer	All - MR Egger	14.278432	8.8743635	0.1387053
DPP-4i	Small intestine cancer	rs4233648	-12.23798	9.0479839	0.1761947
DPP-4i	Small intestine cancer	rs2080714	-0.225212	7.362987	0.9755988
DPP-4i	Small intestine cancer	rs75850673	1.9328882	10.448323	0.8532329
DPP-4i	Small intestine cancer	rs188581353	-7.187272	8.1630038	0.3786053
DPP-4i	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	-4.446577	3.0754453	0.1482244
DPP-4i	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-4.446577	4.2706936	0.2977903
DPP-4i	Small intestine cancer	All - MR Egger	-5.159353	9.7625784	0.6499496
Biguanides	Small intestine cancer	rs150243609	15.881571	7.2056	0.0275202
Biguanides	Small intestine cancer	rs17485664	-2.912424	8.2811524	0.7250685
Biguanides	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	7.7835484	9.306784	0.4029689
Biguanides	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	7.7835484	5.4358908	0.1521779
GLP1RA	Small intestine cancer	rs10305525	-26.97468	11.806646	0.0223302
GLP1RA	Small intestine cancer	rs228817	-8.905581	8.7668992	0.3097157
GLP1RA	Small intestine cancer	rs12215108	9.0002591	8.2504663	0.2753262
GLP1RA	Small intestine cancer	rs28360624	9.5392216	8.7569461	0.2760075
GLP1RA	Small intestine cancer	rs11963172	10.287389	6.9477222	0.1386905
GLP1RA	Small intestine cancer	rs880347	3.646134	5.2562201	0.487883
GLP1RA	Small intestine cancer	rs9462535	-6.724516	7.2236129	0.3519014
GLP1RA	Small intestine cancer	rs142878626	5.5231106	9.0967281	0.543749
GLP1RA	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.6917117	3.5711558	0.6357028
GLP1RA	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.6917117	2.7108689	0.5325962
GLP1RA	Small intestine cancer	All - MR Egger	20.431734	14.44153	0.2068701
Insulin	Small intestine cancer	rs4031066	-15.47884	7.7804795	0.0466521
TZD	Small intestine cancer	rs4684833	-0.716447	5.710307	0.9001549
TZD	Small intestine cancer	rs2881654	1.5978579	1.8508343	0.3879628

TZD	Small intestine cancer	rs1373641	-2.279653	5.1728378	0.6594325
TZD	Small intestine cancer	rs2120825	2.1115073	1.9898425	0.288625
TZD	Small intestine cancer	rs111327339	-0.442438	6.1484743	0.9426345
TZD	Small intestine cancer	rs4135247	2.6580107	2.9490349	0.3674206
TZD	Small intestine cancer	rs1699348	-6.147424	8.79744	0.4846932
TZD	Small intestine cancer	rs310752	4.5491308	8.4080769	0.588478
TZD	Small intestine cancer	rs76763697	-1.767411	8.9375893	0.8432405
TZD	Small intestine cancer	rs2920503	6.3664535	7.0272674	0.3649547
TZD	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.5706777	0.5879791	0.0075555
TZD	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.5706777	1.1085203	0.1565081
TZD	Small intestine cancer	All - MR Egger	2.1610553	1.7654014	0.2557328
Amylin analog	Small intestine cancer	rs4663804	0.2743843	11.300196	0.9806282
Amylin analog	Small intestine cancer	rs11869741	-0.80332	7.3879387	0.9134135
Amylin analog	Small intestine cancer	rs12603201	0.7921579	4.4267206	0.8579776
Amylin analog	Small intestine cancer	rs11654396	-0.642234	9.2221324	0.9444798
Amylin analog	Small intestine cancer	rs12941945	5.0939301	6.4431878	0.4291824
Amylin analog	Small intestine cancer	rs1078523	-3.534163	6.7735625	0.6018386
Amylin analog	Small intestine cancer	rs9905939	-1.186169	7.0772727	0.866896
Amylin analog	Small intestine cancer	rs59795094	-6.276485	8.3800769	0.4538711
Amylin analog	Small intestine cancer	rs9892728	-2.376763	7.1382895	0.7391647
Amylin analog	Small intestine cancer	rs73111954	-0.870345	5.476	0.8737177
Amylin analog	Small intestine cancer	rs11772021	-3.506998	3.0773292	0.254443
Amylin analog	Small intestine cancer	rs4724382	-1.658613	9.9178378	0.8671849
Amylin analog	Small intestine cancer	rs75390434	-5.004145	11.624103	0.6668339
Amylin analog	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.584665	0.747924	0.0341115
Amylin analog	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.584665	1.7021001	0.3518507
Amylin analog	Small intestine cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.808818	3.8248563	0.6455213
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	rs4561482	0.1441803	9.4062393	0.9877704
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	rs8057326	-10.68381	10.294476	0.299354
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	rs34497199	-2.561326	8.4355814	0.7614071
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	rs142133957	0.6067308	6.8404078	0.9293219

SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	rs11150624	-1.849344	9.0081967	0.8373411
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	rs11865835	-18.06504	10.414696	0.0828166
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	rs8057029	-2.98306	9.8382759	0.7617301
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	rs12448775	0.8427276	8.8608333	0.9242298
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	rs8054784	-2.181739	9.9917117	0.8271526
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	-3.190634	1.9146197	0.0956222
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.190634	3.0043406	0.2882321
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	All - MR Egger	3.0407916	7.2885852	0.6890303
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	rs4561482	0.1441803	9.4062393	0.9877704
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	rs8057326	-10.68381	10.294476	0.299354
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	rs34497199	-2.561326	8.4355814	0.7614071
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	rs142133957	0.6067308	6.8404078	0.9293219
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	rs11150624	-1.849344	9.0081967	0.8373411
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	rs11865835	-18.06504	10.414696	0.0828166
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	rs8057029	-2.98306	9.8382759	0.7617301
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	rs12448775	0.8427276	8.8608333	0.9242298
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	rs8054784	-2.181739	9.9917117	0.8271526
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	-3.190634	1.9146197	0.0956222
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.190634	3.0043406	0.2882321
SGLT2i	Small intestine cancer	All - MR Egger	3.0407916	7.2885852	0.6890303
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs77023203	0.265979	1.4593738	0.8553822
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs2074312	0.9694378	1.7662784	0.5831022
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs116842927	-3.598606	5.1755556	0.4868622
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs7110898	8.7596596	7.4877021	0.2420521
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4937311	-4.682992	5.3645556	0.38269
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs5219	-0.528332	0.843245	0.5309563
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4148631	2.096035	4.8429301	0.6651578
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs10766393	1.6413806	1.7292283	0.3425198
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs5210	-0.124518	1.5217389	0.9347847
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs10766395	0.0408045	1.5476241	0.9789655
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs189603359	2.523716	5.1933852	0.6270039

SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs10766392	1.106974	1.7146536	0.5185409
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs7110037	-2.18425	1.9671316	0.2668383
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs77902362	-4.370942	4.1423701	0.2913435
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs35271178	-1.023242	0.946445	0.2796337
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs147673442	1.8160544	3.3588083	0.5887253
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs2355016	-2.112258	2.0745667	0.3085979
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs2285676	-0.206252	1.5070927	0.8911458
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs739688	3.7008743	3.7244311	0.3203811
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs79506407	-8.732214	5.8290024	0.1341168
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs7112030	-0.100567	1.5358437	0.9477919
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs117973841	-1.251934	4.5837748	0.7847588
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs12816749	-3.443964	4.1551775	0.4071967
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs74732083	2.9711883	3.6692152	0.4180774
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs10841887	4.5946471	2.0806912	0.0272282
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs59406438	2.6616279	3.2331501	0.4103769
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.072229	0.3363174	0.8299502
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.072229	0.3748661	0.8472093
SU	Squamous cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.771711	0.9861903	0.4415639
AGI	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs72681706	-3.102646	4.6080094	0.5007463
AGI	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs72692396	1.4911537	4.1079441	0.7166103
AGI	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs174587	-6.244246	4.0597207	0.1240248
AGI	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs112968754	1.0868659	4.5435366	0.8109416
AGI	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs8037100	1.2013282	5.7234872	0.8337501
AGI	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs1659215	0.2152951	6.0274054	0.9715061
AGI	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs73402785	0.8236582	4.6318987	0.858862
AGI	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs34359922	2.2562712	4.4623729	0.6131225
AGI	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs111917515	0.8873875	4.1418081	0.8303512
AGI	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs113126535	1.1999	4.47512	0.7886016
AGI	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs112898001	0.6823267	4.4801594	0.8789506
AGI	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4924660	9.3220115	5.1523621	0.0704091
AGI	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.5425407	1.0286394	0.5978914

AGI	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.5425407	1.3291248	0.6831313
AGI	Squamous cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.151351	4.9378385	0.9761508
DPP-4i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4233648	-1.205492	5.0272177	0.8104907
DPP-4i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs2080714	7.444026	4.0884805	0.0686477
DPP-4i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs75850673	5.1989814	5.7898075	0.36921
DPP-4i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs188581353	-1.427009	4.4701752	0.749553
DPP-4i	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	2.6848866	2.3573129	0.2547196
DPP-4i	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	2.6848866	2.3618346	0.2556302
DPP-4i	Squamous cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.842601	5.9204585	0.8998701
Biguanides	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs150243609	0.7982271	4.1002286	0.8456445
Biguanides	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs17485664	0.1473807	4.6117844	0.974506
Biguanides	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.5108893	0.3231869	0.113927
Biguanides	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.5108893	3.0642637	0.8675865
GLP1RA	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs10305525	-1.86543	6.579557	0.7767789
GLP1RA	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs228817	0.7020667	4.8736512	0.8854582
GLP1RA	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs12215108	4.3007513	4.5814352	0.3478671
GLP1RA	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs28360624	-0.474425	4.8651617	0.9223177
GLP1RA	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs11963172	1.9534722	3.8610444	0.612896
GLP1RA	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs880347	-0.839033	2.9213493	0.7739534
GLP1RA	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs9462535	-4.442845	4.0169548	0.2687165
GLP1RA	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs142878626	7.9973963	5.0522811	0.1134379
GLP1RA	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.5494236	1.263983	0.6637973
GLP1RA	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.5494236	1.5067089	0.7153716
GLP1RA	Squamous cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	9.2564827	6.4219972	0.1995627
Insulin	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4031066	3.7185822	4.3268014	0.3901034
TZD	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4684833	6.3348246	3.1767763	0.0461406
TZD	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs2881654	-0.4927	1.0305434	0.6325809
TZD	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs1373641	-1.23745	2.8762477	0.6670277
TZD	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs2120825	-0.333816	1.1079651	0.7631956
TZD	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs111327339	6.164426	3.4187009	0.0713649
TZD	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4135247	-0.201875	1.6398606	0.9020238

TZD	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs1699348	-6.150512	4.892488	0.2087052
TZD	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs310752	1.3797538	4.6778077	0.7680264
TZD	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs76763697	7.12375	4.9533929	0.1503899
TZD	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs2920503	-7.133895	3.9121977	0.0682276
TZD	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.06662	0.7910701	0.9328852
TZD	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.06662	0.6169581	0.9140101
TZD	Squamous cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.1592583	1.3325525	0.9078152
Amylin analog	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4663804	1.7895196	6.2797353	0.7756691
Amylin analog	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs11869741	-2.180749	4.1172981	0.5963508
Amylin analog	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs12603201	-1.804126	2.462081	0.4637021
Amylin analog	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs11654396	-1.692801	5.124375	0.7411408
Amylin analog	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs12941945	-2.103022	3.5788559	0.5567847
Amylin analog	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs1078523	1.5566125	3.7653313	0.6793088
Amylin analog	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs9905939	2.0826364	3.9352013	0.5966442
Amylin analog	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs59795094	1.4803385	4.6586769	0.7506674
Amylin analog	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs9892728	1.6363026	3.9678487	0.6800533
Amylin analog	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs73111954	2.4155702	3.0428255	0.4272783
Amylin analog	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs11772021	1.4231284	1.7146046	0.4065366
Amylin analog	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4724382	1.4881532	5.5151441	0.7872908
Amylin analog	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs75390434	2.8343162	6.4536325	0.66053
Amylin analog	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.5997322	0.4934699	0.2242376
Amylin analog	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.5997322	0.9469359	0.5265117
Amylin analog	Squamous cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.1168373	2.1294823	0.9572287
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4561482	8.5275385	5.2282821	0.1028818
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs8057326	12.338095	5.7234476	0.0311063
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs34497199	11.857519	4.6925891	0.0115087
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs142133957	3.8653507	3.8129364	0.3107038
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs11150624	8.9195902	5.010123	0.0750246
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs11865835	12.656696	5.7867304	0.0287284
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs8057029	11.556121	5.4711552	0.0346701
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs12448775	11.423045	4.9380128	0.0207068

SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs8054784	13.855045	5.5575946	0.0126671
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	9.8640457	1.1653434	2.57E-17
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	9.8640457	1.6717796	3.63E-09
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	4.4662017	4.0621051	0.3079281
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4561482	8.5275385	5.2282821	0.1028818
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs8057326	12.338095	5.7234476	0.0311063
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs34497199	11.857519	4.6925891	0.0115087
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs142133957	3.8653507	3.8129364	0.3107038
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs11150624	8.9195902	5.010123	0.0750246
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs11865835	12.656696	5.7867304	0.0287284
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs8057029	11.556121	5.4711552	0.0346701
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs12448775	11.423045	4.9380128	0.0207068
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs8054784	13.855045	5.5575946	0.0126671
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	9.8640457	1.1653434	2.57E-17
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	9.8640457	1.6717796	3.63E-09
SGLT2i	Squamous cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	4.4662017	4.0621051	0.3079281
SU	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs116842927	-2.358214	1.5746405	0.1342319
SU	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs7110898	0.5154894	2.5884255	0.8421441
SU	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs5219	0.4152355	0.2596904	0.1098287
SU	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs4148631	-1.104545	1.5158741	0.4662143
SU	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs7110037	1.0034737	0.6277105	0.109904
SU	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs77902362	0.1638961	1.5405519	0.9152746
SU	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs147673442	-0.328549	0.9735233	0.7357515
SU	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs2355016	1.0597778	0.6567222	0.1065842
SU	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs739688	-0.272994	1.1782036	0.8167682
SU	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs79506407	0.6180292	1.7381265	0.7221611
SU	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs117973841	1.0462583	1.6308609	0.5211736
SU	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs12816749	1.0933136	1.3290533	0.4107208
SU	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs74732083	-0.539081	1.3591928	0.691649
SU	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs10841887	-0.324324	0.6351765	0.6096285
SU	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs59406438	1.2291966	1.0954123	0.2618065

SU	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.3742604	0.1571491	0.0172393
SU	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.3742604	0.1889963	0.0476752
SU	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.558984	0.3845588	0.169777
AGI	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs72681706	1.7964169	1.4425293	0.2130125
AGI	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs72692396	1.3473852	1.4086627	0.3388199
AGI	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs174587	-0.941173	1.3389385	0.4821026
AGI	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs112968754	-0.552561	1.4131301	0.6957831
AGI	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs8037100	-1.147846	1.7716923	0.5170618
AGI	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs1659215	-1.447622	1.8772432	0.4406226
AGI	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs73402785	-0.563713	1.4448945	0.696432
AGI	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs34359922	-1.694364	1.3851695	0.2212473
AGI	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs111917515	-0.881255	1.2957565	0.4964359
AGI	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs113126535	-0.95712	1.401	0.4945
AGI	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs112898001	-0.967729	1.3948207	0.4878065
AGI	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs4924660	-2.80523	1.5915517	0.0779721
AGI	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.672559	0.3524423	0.0563548
AGI	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.672559	0.4203513	0.1096001
AGI	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	3.018114	1.6107775	0.0904561
DPP-4i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs2080714	-2.085584	1.3070779	0.1105763
Biguanides	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs17485664	-1.93461	1.4714498	0.1885891
GLP1RA	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs10305525	0.8859494	2.1308861	0.6775815
GLP1RA	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs228817	0.7185271	1.5179845	0.6359686
GLP1RA	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs12215108	1.0543523	1.4176684	0.4570442
GLP1RA	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs28360624	-0.084072	1.4857485	0.9548754
GLP1RA	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs11963172	0.2601667	1.2313333	0.8326621
GLP1RA	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs880347	-0.581962	0.9239234	0.5287725
GLP1RA	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs9462535	0.0194839	1.2375484	0.9874387
GLP1RA	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs142878626	3.3717512	1.7741014	0.0573623
GLP1RA	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.3556824	0.3798047	0.3490222
GLP1RA	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.3556824	0.4763817	0.455285
GLP1RA	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	2.1353259	2.1425066	0.3574159

Insulin	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs4031066	0.1163014	1.4552055	0.9363001
TZD	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs4684833	-0.559474	1.0029825	0.5769741
TZD	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs2881654	0.0295378	0.3147914	0.925242
TZD	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs1373641	0.6393694	0.889009	0.4720218
TZD	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs2120825	-0.003723	0.3321035	0.9910549
TZD	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs111327339	0.7652719	1.1117976	0.4912516
TZD	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs4135247	0.3236461	0.5136461	0.5286321
TZD	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs1699348	1.94104	1.5144	0.1999401
TZD	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs310752	0.1174615	1.4586154	0.9358162
TZD	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs2920503	-0.621628	1.2088372	0.6070868
TZD	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.1028403	0.1227885	0.4022894
TZD	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.1028403	0.1903217	0.588956
TZD	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.031979	0.3005048	0.9182358
Amylin analog	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs4663804	-0.603039	1.9246078	0.7540292
Amylin analog	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs12603201	1.4536437	0.7745344	0.0605459
Amylin analog	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs11654396	-2.545294	1.5856618	0.1084512
Amylin analog	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs1078523	-0.052813	1.1755625	0.9641668
Amylin analog	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs9905939	-0.48974	1.2493506	0.6950613
Amylin analog	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs59795094	-0.421692	1.4509231	0.7713288
Amylin analog	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs9892728	-0.111513	1.2414474	0.9284262
Amylin analog	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs73111954	-0.211191	0.9830213	0.8298927
Amylin analog	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs11772021	0.1565839	0.5312008	0.768167
Amylin analog	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs4724382	0.158018	1.7068468	0.9262381
Amylin analog	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs75390434	0.8829915	2.0113675	0.6606611
Amylin analog	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.1233226	0.2575484	0.6320576
Amylin analog	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.1233226	0.316355	0.6966671
Amylin analog	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.6697422	0.6926664	0.3588543
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs4561482	1.2287179	1.6420513	0.4542899
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs8057326	1.6884762	1.7820952	0.3434009
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs34497199	2.6993023	1.4724031	0.0667634
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs11150624	1.4767213	1.5459836	0.3394773

SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs11865835	-1.06	1.8534783	0.5673913
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs8057029	0.7564655	1.6718966	0.650938
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs12448775	2.2466346	1.835609	0.2209832
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs8054784	1.9265766	1.7236937	0.2636941
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.4494883	0.3896904	0.0001995
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.4494883	0.5925979	0.0144455
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	3.0863583	2.8332724	0.317816
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs4561482	1.2287179	1.6420513	0.4542899
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs8057326	1.6884762	1.7820952	0.3434009
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs34497199	2.6993023	1.4724031	0.0667634
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs11150624	1.4767213	1.5459836	0.3394773
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs11865835	-1.06	1.8534783	0.5673913
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs8057029	0.7564655	1.6718966	0.650938
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs12448775	2.2466346	1.835609	0.2209832
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs8054784	1.9265766	1.7236937	0.2636941
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.4494883	0.3896904	0.0001995
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.4494883	0.5925979	0.0144455
SGLT2i	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	3.0863583	2.8332724	0.317816
SU	Testicular cancer	rs77023203	0.689986	1.223285	0.5727245
SU	Testicular cancer	rs2074312	0.5146757	1.4792784	0.7278977
SU	Testicular cancer	rs116842927	-0.956124	4.2420915	0.821676
SU	Testicular cancer	rs7110898	2.3990426	6.287617	0.7027949
SU	Testicular cancer	rs4937311	-3.787778	4.4951746	0.3994343
SU	Testicular cancer	rs5219	-0.093263	0.7049973	0.8947565
SU	Testicular cancer	rs4148631	4.6570769	4.0577483	0.2510925
SU	Testicular cancer	rs10766393	0.684916	1.4496299	0.6365867
SU	Testicular cancer	rs5210	0.8201798	1.2755788	0.5202329
SU	Testicular cancer	rs10766395	0.5252782	1.2973835	0.6855694
SU	Testicular cancer	rs189603359	5.0975681	4.3200584	0.2380095
SU	Testicular cancer	rs10766392	0.7053229	1.4373802	0.6236384
SU	Testicular cancer	rs7110037	-0.125186	1.6454342	0.939355

SU	Testicular cancer	rs77902362	4.086526	3.4948377	0.2422814
SU	Testicular cancer	rs35271178	0.3343736	0.7922341	0.6729782
SU	Testicular cancer	rs147673442	-3.429404	2.8202332	0.2239848
SU	Testicular cancer	rs2355016	-0.225281	1.7361	0.8967544
SU	Testicular cancer	rs2285676	0.8214976	1.2632878	0.5155079
SU	Testicular cancer	rs739688	-0.669958	3.1199042	0.8299726
SU	Testicular cancer	rs79506407	-3.212993	4.8510949	0.5077641
SU	Testicular cancer	rs7112030	0.7187593	1.2875409	0.5766792
SU	Testicular cancer	rs117973841	-2.794848	3.8206291	0.4644646
SU	Testicular cancer	rs12816749	0.5256473	3.4808994	0.8799686
SU	Testicular cancer	rs74732083	-1.493733	3.0927578	0.6291115
SU	Testicular cancer	rs10841887	1.5592971	1.7380765	0.3696445
SU	Testicular cancer	rs59406438	-4.092389	2.7074419	0.1306526
SU	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.3034277	0.2203942	0.1685897
SU	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.3034277	0.3138735	0.3336842
SU	Testicular cancer	All - MR Egger	0.0332652	0.8255101	0.9681901
AGI	Testicular cancer	rs72681706	-7.54911	3.8555035	0.050229
AGI	Testicular cancer	rs72692396	-6.443174	3.4223553	0.0597448
AGI	Testicular cancer	rs174587	-1.349285	3.3955419	0.691095
AGI	Testicular cancer	rs112968754	3.4763455	3.8185976	0.3626262
AGI	Testicular cancer	rs8037100	5.0435333	4.8072462	0.294108
AGI	Testicular cancer	rs1659215	5.6191351	5.0629459	0.2670616
AGI	Testicular cancer	rs73402785	2.3650759	3.8916456	0.5433655
AGI	Testicular cancer	rs34359922	3.0925805	3.7483093	0.4093375
AGI	Testicular cancer	rs111917515	3.2674945	3.4788266	0.3476014
AGI	Testicular cancer	rs113126535	4.23092	3.759336	0.2604012
AGI	Testicular cancer	rs112898001	1.987757	3.7608367	0.5971238
AGI	Testicular cancer	rs4924660	2.692546	4.3163736	0.5327601
AGI	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.9085472	1.2527295	0.4682961
AGI	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.9085472	1.1144083	0.414916
AGI	Testicular cancer	All - MR Egger	-8.87057	4.1260522	0.0570748

DPP-4i	Testicular cancer	rs4233648	6.6860242	4.2057177	0.111892
DPP-4i	Testicular cancer	rs2080714	-0.463875	3.4265844	0.8923152
DPP-4i	Testicular cancer	rs75850673	-0.337486	4.8465714	0.944485
DPP-4i	Testicular cancer	rs188581353	-0.205605	3.7790113	0.9566109
DPP-4i	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.2179505	1.6889467	0.4708294
DPP-4i	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.2179505	1.9830204	0.5390901
DPP-4i	Testicular cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.948447	4.520569	0.7084637
Biguanides	Testicular cancer	rs150243609	4.3164571	3.4195429	0.2068442
Biguanides	Testicular cancer	rs17485664	-3.537197	3.8553903	0.3588975
Biguanides	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.8584664	3.8987387	0.8257226
Biguanides	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.8584664	2.5582582	0.7371976
GLP1RA	Testicular cancer	rs10305525	5.9700823	5.5030949	0.2779841
GLP1RA	Testicular cancer	rs228817	-0.796295	4.0867674	0.8455127
GLP1RA	Testicular cancer	rs12215108	3.1359689	3.8392435	0.4140316
GLP1RA	Testicular cancer	rs28360624	-0.117975	4.0828084	0.9769478
GLP1RA	Testicular cancer	rs11963172	-0.658711	3.2367222	0.838735
GLP1RA	Testicular cancer	rs880347	-4.468708	2.4438325	0.0674647
GLP1RA	Testicular cancer	rs9462535	-5.348329	3.358729	0.1113023
GLP1RA	Testicular cancer	rs142878626	-7.008779	4.1997926	0.0951492
GLP1RA	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.110526	1.3299212	0.1125227
GLP1RA	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.110526	1.2609226	0.0941709
GLP1RA	Testicular cancer	All - MR Egger	-8.331268	5.5130148	0.1814883
Insulin	Testicular cancer	rs4031066	-0.575999	3.6226644	0.8736698
TZD	Testicular cancer	rs4684833	1.9267588	2.6495088	0.4670951
TZD	Testicular cancer	rs2881654	0.0667198	0.8606212	0.9382057
TZD	Testicular cancer	rs1373641	0.459018	2.4076577	0.8488004
TZD	Testicular cancer	rs2120825	-0.401612	0.9242857	0.6639177
TZD	Testicular cancer	rs111327339	-5.660302	2.8581118	0.0476548
TZD	Testicular cancer	rs4135247	-0.445375	1.3714048	0.7453639
TZD	Testicular cancer	rs1699348	3.322064	4.096032	0.4173401
TZD	Testicular cancer	rs310752	-0.917954	3.9188308	0.8147973

TZD	Testicular cancer	rs76763697	-1.092	4.1493795	0.7924181
TZD	Testicular cancer	rs2920503	3.3736977	3.2662558	0.3016533
TZD	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.150028	0.4396384	0.7329122
TZD	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.150028	0.5152798	0.7709296
TZD	Testicular cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.809948	0.8207931	0.352648
Amylin analog	Testicular cancer	rs4663804	-1.838078	5.2676569	0.7271369
Amylin analog	Testicular cancer	rs11869741	-1.778036	3.4462674	0.6059026
Amylin analog	Testicular cancer	rs12603201	-4.489433	2.0619231	0.0294579
Amylin analog	Testicular cancer	rs11654396	-2.880221	4.2880809	0.5017871
Amylin analog	Testicular cancer	rs12941945	-4.482795	2.9942707	0.134361
Amylin analog	Testicular cancer	rs1078523	-2.604181	3.15175	0.4086537
Amylin analog	Testicular cancer	rs9905939	-5.523	3.2906429	0.0932699
Amylin analog	Testicular cancer	rs59795094	-3.339292	3.8995692	0.3918189
Amylin analog	Testicular cancer	rs9892728	-2.786888	3.3210263	0.4013769
Amylin analog	Testicular cancer	rs73111954	1.3561915	2.5508596	0.5949611
Amylin analog	Testicular cancer	rs11772021	2.0650642	1.4347847	0.1500698
Amylin analog	Testicular cancer	rs4724382	4.3827838	4.6124595	0.3420079
Amylin analog	Testicular cancer	rs75390434	5.8348889	5.4116068	0.2809367
Amylin analog	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.977884	0.9054421	0.280139
Amylin analog	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.977884	0.7926989	0.217347
Amylin analog	Testicular cancer	All - MR Egger	1.0014209	2.0194777	0.6297367
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	rs4561482	-3.54465	4.3746752	0.4177874
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	rs8057326	-0.703406	4.7872095	0.8831838
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	rs34497199	-3.502341	3.9270853	0.3724774
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	rs142133957	0.9109152	3.1903263	0.7752426
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	rs11150624	-2.142385	4.1956393	0.6096159
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	rs11865835	-4.790583	4.8559391	0.3238678
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	rs8057029	-4.273276	4.5769138	0.3504799
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	rs12448775	-3.552372	4.1443269	0.3913537
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	rs8054784	-3.058171	4.650018	0.5107511
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.411104	0.6750725	0.0003548

SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.411104	1.3997277	0.0849695
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	All - MR Egger	0.2255872	3.4013272	0.9489749
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	rs4561482	-3.54465	4.3746752	0.4177874
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	rs8057326	-0.703406	4.7872095	0.8831838
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	rs34497199	-3.502341	3.9270853	0.3724774
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	rs142133957	0.9109152	3.1903263	0.7752426
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	rs11150624	-2.142385	4.1956393	0.6096159
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	rs11865835	-4.790583	4.8559391	0.3238678
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	rs8057029	-4.273276	4.5769138	0.3504799
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	rs12448775	-3.552372	4.1443269	0.3913537
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	rs8054784	-3.058171	4.650018	0.5107511
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.411104	0.6750725	0.0003548
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.411104	1.3997277	0.0849695
SGLT2i	Testicular cancer	All - MR Egger	0.2255872	3.4013272	0.9489749
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs77023203	-0.114767	1.2772074	0.9284
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs2074312	-0.40299	1.5161882	0.7904
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs116842927	1.6988898	4.5571521	0.7093
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs7110898	-2.097672	6.6939265	0.754
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs4937311	-3.987398	4.5068882	0.3763
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs5219	0.0912111	0.7251195	0.8999
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs4148631	-0.132741	4.2528054	0.9751
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs10766393	0.4037035	1.5056313	0.7886
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs5210	0.0836018	1.3226229	0.9496
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs10766395	-0.133185	1.3429441	0.921
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs189603359	-1.879029	4.643048	0.6857
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs10766392	0.4056779	1.4870396	0.785
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs7110037	-0.259167	1.6841528	0.8777
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs77902362	-4.754392	3.9523142	0.229
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs35271178	0.1757443	0.818063	0.8299
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs147673442	-0.249906	2.7579463	0.9278
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs2355016	0.1385428	1.7956358	0.9385

SU	Thyroid cancer	rs2285676	0.0754928	1.3173214	0.9543
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs739688	5.3126904	3.8372139	0.1662
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs79506407	4.8142766	5.4096857	0.3735
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs7112030	0.0248015	1.3280256	0.9851
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs117973841	-5.117575	3.6648861	0.1626
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs12816749	-2.836252	3.6048019	0.4314
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs74732083	0.7639906	3.1355752	0.8075
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs10841887	-0.723533	1.7705646	0.6828
SU	Thyroid cancer	rs59406438	-0.550899	2.8514013	0.8468
SU	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.037198	0.1893711	0.8442723
SU	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.037198	0.3247222	0.908798
SU	Thyroid cancer	All - MR Egger	0.4773287	0.864096	0.585781
AGI	Thyroid cancer	rs72681706	1.3025392	3.7437856	0.7279
AGI	Thyroid cancer	rs72692396	3.2204222	3.210386	0.3158
AGI	Thyroid cancer	rs174587	3.7745914	3.5791072	0.2916
AGI	Thyroid cancer	rs112968754	-1.480828	3.9622182	0.7086
AGI	Thyroid cancer	rs8037100	-1.382573	4.9729977	0.781
AGI	Thyroid cancer	rs1659215	-2.150317	5.2428294	0.6817
AGI	Thyroid cancer	rs73402785	0.5820553	3.9280048	0.8822
AGI	Thyroid cancer	rs34359922	0.9599445	3.8242021	0.8018
AGI	Thyroid cancer	rs111917515	-1.539395	3.6357521	0.672
AGI	Thyroid cancer	rs113126535	-1.699384	3.928237	0.6653
AGI	Thyroid cancer	rs112898001	-2.23493	3.9579579	0.5723
AGI	Thyroid cancer	rs4924660	-2.011817	4.4581908	0.6518
AGI	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.1348676	0.6485436	0.8352645
AGI	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.1348676	1.1361115	0.9055053
AGI	Thyroid cancer	All - MR Egger	2.401741	4.0310407	0.564542
DPP-4i	Thyroid cancer	rs4233648	7.5348343	7.967441	0.3443
DPP-4i	Thyroid cancer	rs2080714	-0.475765	3.5237905	0.8926
DPP-4i	Thyroid cancer	rs75850673	0.2108219	5.1269564	0.9672
DPP-4i	Thyroid cancer	rs188581353	3.5838502	3.6015895	0.3197

DPP-4i	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.7249245	1.4180264	0.2238226
DPP-4i	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.7249245	2.1748229	0.4277001
DPP-4i	Thyroid cancer	All - MR Egger	3.6326457	4.4418694	0.4993929
Biguanides	Thyroid cancer	rs150243609	1.8505624	3.8686242	0.6324
Biguanides	Thyroid cancer	rs17485664	3.7765746	3.741538	0.3128
Biguanides	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.845723	0.9624691	0.0031096
Biguanides	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.845723	2.6894733	0.2900113
GLP1RA	Thyroid cancer	rs10305525	2.8887568	5.7566553	0.6158
GLP1RA	Thyroid cancer	rs228817	1.9897478	4.1534912	0.6319
GLP1RA	Thyroid cancer	rs12215108	-3.068361	3.8000033	0.4194
GLP1RA	Thyroid cancer	rs28360624	-4.452999	4.2250062	0.2919
GLP1RA	Thyroid cancer	rs11963172	-5.627347	3.4014808	0.09805
GLP1RA	Thyroid cancer	rs880347	0.1725596	2.5383148	0.9458
GLP1RA	Thyroid cancer	rs9462535	6.0774707	3.3963685	0.07355
GLP1RA	Thyroid cancer	rs142878626	-1.179448	4.2967053	0.7837
GLP1RA	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.429693	1.3980454	0.7585748
GLP1RA	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.429693	1.2954208	0.7401145
GLP1RA	Thyroid cancer	All - MR Egger	-5.23147	6.0589211	0.4210688
Insulin	Thyroid cancer	rs4031066	0.9934717	3.7232372	0.7896
Insulin	Thyroid cancer	rs144057856	5.5847747	2.486819	0.02472
Insulin	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	4.1683939	2.1205892	0.0493359
Insulin	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	4.1683939	2.0679629	0.0438313
TZD	Thyroid cancer	rs4684833	2.7698603	2.7772506	0.3186
TZD	Thyroid cancer	rs2881654	0.8968464	0.9117769	0.3253
TZD	Thyroid cancer	rs1373641	-2.883204	2.4210666	0.2337
TZD	Thyroid cancer	rs2120825	0.5112628	0.9625194	0.5953
TZD	Thyroid cancer	rs111327339	-0.56047	2.8207292	0.8425
TZD	Thyroid cancer	rs4135247	-1.285001	1.4029361	0.3597
TZD	Thyroid cancer	rs1699348	-1.853302	4.1670596	0.6565
TZD	Thyroid cancer	rs310752	3.012055	3.9793765	0.4491
TZD	Thyroid cancer	rs76763697	7.3394222	4.309187	0.08853

TZD	Thyroid cancer	rs2920503	-3.008035	3.3779344	0.3732
TZD	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.2845114	0.5278854	0.5899115
TZD	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.2845114	0.5361707	0.5956712
TZD	Thyroid cancer	All - MR Egger	0.6851173	0.8745736	0.4559714
Amylin analog	Thyroid cancer	rs4663804	9.4243164	9.3716787	0.3146
Amylin analog	Thyroid cancer	rs11869741	-14.30351	6.3062403	0.02332
Amylin analog	Thyroid cancer	rs12603201	1.5567282	2.1079095	0.4602
Amylin analog	Thyroid cancer	rs11654396	-3.657507	4.4688186	0.4131
Amylin analog	Thyroid cancer	rs12941945	-5.356332	3.184611	0.09258
Amylin analog	Thyroid cancer	rs1078523	2.0352494	3.2629904	0.5328
Amylin analog	Thyroid cancer	rs9905939	3.611586	3.4089615	0.2894
Amylin analog	Thyroid cancer	rs59795094	2.251346	4.0152199	0.575
Amylin analog	Thyroid cancer	rs9892728	1.5088797	3.4385803	0.6608
Amylin analog	Thyroid cancer	rs73111954	-5.52338	2.8141617	0.04968
Amylin analog	Thyroid cancer	rs11772021	-0.359206	1.4805299	0.8083
Amylin analog	Thyroid cancer	rs4724382	-0.341694	4.7455855	0.9426
Amylin analog	Thyroid cancer	rs75390434	-6.11995	5.4025184	0.2573
Amylin analog	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.665438	1.0006844	0.5060617
Amylin analog	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.665438	0.845762	0.4314045
Amylin analog	Thyroid cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.918507	2.3465956	0.4309553
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	rs4561482	0.6895189	4.4513753	0.8769
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	rs8057326	2.9260164	4.9035696	0.5507
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	rs34497199	0.9246954	4.0386766	0.8189
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	rs142133957	5.5779296	3.1636672	0.07788
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	rs11150624	1.7647638	4.3070808	0.682
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	rs11865835	7.2620522	5.1028923	0.1547
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	rs8057029	1.1304861	4.6372913	0.8074
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	rs12448775	-8.681618	4.8040572	0.07074
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	rs8054784	-0.969158	4.7641186	0.8388
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.6230177	1.429448	0.2562012
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.6230177	1.4441637	0.2610783

SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	All - MR Egger	2.0585638	3.6909757	0.5944081
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	rs4561482	0.6895189	4.4513753	0.8769
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	rs8057326	2.9260164	4.9035696	0.5507
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	rs34497199	0.9246954	4.0386766	0.8189
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	rs142133957	5.5779296	3.1636672	0.07788
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	rs11150624	1.7647638	4.3070808	0.682
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	rs11865835	7.2620522	5.1028923	0.1547
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	rs8057029	1.1304861	4.6372913	0.8074
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	rs12448775	-8.681618	4.8040572	0.07074
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	rs8054784	-0.969158	4.7641186	0.8388
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.6230177	1.429448	0.2562012
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.6230177	1.4441637	0.2610783
SGLT2i	Thyroid cancer	All - MR Egger	2.0585638	3.6909757	0.5944081
SU	Tongue cancer	rs77023203	-2.0685	1.9186893	0.2809982
SU	Tongue cancer	rs2074312	-2.177116	2.3203811	0.3481118
SU	Tongue cancer	rs116842927	-2.341264	6.6688235	0.7255314
SU	Tongue cancer	rs7110898	16.432553	9.9222979	0.0976968
SU	Tongue cancer	rs4937311	3.2580159	7.0572143	0.644327
SU	Tongue cancer	rs5219	-0.791822	1.1082382	0.4749258
SU	Tongue cancer	rs4148631	-1.187259	6.365042	0.8520307
SU	Tongue cancer	rs10766393	0.2003234	2.2734199	0.9297849
SU	Tongue cancer	rs5210	-2.140236	2.0010911	0.2848288
SU	Tongue cancer	rs10766395	-1.939571	2.0352982	0.3406069
SU	Tongue cancer	rs189603359	-0.519677	6.8066732	0.9391421
SU	Tongue cancer	rs10766392	0.2227589	2.2541302	0.9212792
SU	Tongue cancer	rs7110037	0.0206348	2.5820211	0.9936236
SU	Tongue cancer	rs77902362	2.0945747	5.4547403	0.7009846
SU	Tongue cancer	rs35271178	-1.572884	1.2450465	0.2064766
SU	Tongue cancer	rs147673442	4.5784456	4.452772	0.3038446
SU	Tongue cancer	rs2355016	-0.196567	2.7228972	0.9424505
SU	Tongue cancer	rs2285676	-2.07338	1.9818244	0.2954697

SU	Tongue cancer	rs739688	0.6779222	4.8978922	0.8899156
SU	Tongue cancer	rs79506407	10.33382	7.6517275	0.1768489
SU	Tongue cancer	rs7112030	-2.62067	2.0196179	0.1944225
SU	Tongue cancer	rs117973841	6.4187086	6.0218874	0.2864704
SU	Tongue cancer	rs12816749	8.3498817	5.4609112	0.1262577
SU	Tongue cancer	rs74732083	4.5606278	4.8145291	0.3435045
SU	Tongue cancer	rs10841887	1.8103618	2.7342265	0.5079
SU	Tongue cancer	rs59406438	-4.627653	4.2748837	0.2790209
SU	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.838326	0.4211616	0.0465349
SU	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.838326	0.4928278	0.0889331
SU	Tongue cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.70842	1.2966621	0.04751
AGI	Tongue cancer	rs72681706	2.5418501	6.0475878	0.6742604
AGI	Tongue cancer	rs72692396	-0.119599	5.3819361	0.9822706
AGI	Tongue cancer	rs174587	5.6807821	5.3263687	0.2861799
AGI	Tongue cancer	rs112968754	3.804687	6.0017073	0.5261238
AGI	Tongue cancer	rs8037100	4.4687744	7.5517436	0.5540153
AGI	Tongue cancer	rs1659215	5.5136216	7.9538919	0.4881853
AGI	Tongue cancer	rs73402785	2.6878228	6.1098734	0.6599989
AGI	Tongue cancer	rs34359922	5.2136441	5.8941949	0.3764054
AGI	Tongue cancer	rs111917515	3.7250185	5.4645756	0.4954498
AGI	Tongue cancer	rs113126535	3.755792	5.90424	0.5246997
AGI	Tongue cancer	rs112898001	4.3882869	5.9062948	0.4574909
AGI	Tongue cancer	rs4924660	2.8622069	6.7815517	0.6729828
AGI	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.6134271	0.4897799	1.61E-13
AGI	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.6134271	1.7504189	0.0389873
AGI	Tongue cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.755672	6.4812608	0.9094907
DPP-4i	Tongue cancer	rs4233648	-0.080621	6.6094355	0.9902677
DPP-4i	Tongue cancer	rs2080714	-7.148571	5.376039	0.1836139
DPP-4i	Tongue cancer	rs75850673	8.2273913	7.6252174	0.2806005
DPP-4i	Tongue cancer	rs188581353	1.4405257	5.9262453	0.8079468
DPP-4i	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.64624	3.0865541	0.8341573

DPP-4i	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.64624	3.1134153	0.8355676
DPP-4i	Tongue cancer	All - MR Egger	1.8893069	8.3740915	0.8424594
Biguanides	Tongue cancer	rs150243609	3.8546429	5.3881571	0.474367
Biguanides	Tongue cancer	rs17485664	0.6194164	6.0568773	0.9185451
Biguanides	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.425417	1.606606	0.1311321
Biguanides	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.425417	4.0257505	0.5468575
GLP1RA	Tongue cancer	rs10305525	-0.968595	8.6396203	0.9107355
GLP1RA	Tongue cancer	rs228817	-12.34667	6.4098295	0.0540784
GLP1RA	Tongue cancer	rs12215108	-6.349689	6.013886	0.2910423
GLP1RA	Tongue cancer	rs28360624	16.765689	6.4095808	0.0089039
GLP1RA	Tongue cancer	rs11963172	10.641833	5.0808833	0.0362168
GLP1RA	Tongue cancer	rs880347	-1.552038	3.8358373	0.6857603
GLP1RA	Tongue cancer	rs9462535	-4.183026	5.2803613	0.4282525
GLP1RA	Tongue cancer	rs142878626	2.6719585	6.6101152	0.686049
GLP1RA	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.536552	3.0802333	0.8617146
GLP1RA	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.536552	1.979598	0.7863596
GLP1RA	Tongue cancer	All - MR Egger	8.7071289	13.725433	0.5492411
Insulin	Tongue cancer	rs4031066	-7.958836	5.6944041	0.1622155
TZD	Tongue cancer	rs4684833	-1.553263	4.171307	0.7096185
TZD	Tongue cancer	rs2881654	-4.24779	1.3616798	0.0018114
TZD	Tongue cancer	rs1373641	-1.530955	3.7810405	0.6855488
TZD	Tongue cancer	rs2120825	-4.973847	1.4701125	0.0007162
TZD	Tongue cancer	rs111327339	0.593	4.4832326	0.8947702
TZD	Tongue cancer	rs4135247	-2.831528	2.1542225	0.1887088
TZD	Tongue cancer	rs1699348	-2.209408	6.434088	0.7313043
TZD	Tongue cancer	rs310752	-3.883269	6.1467077	0.527541
TZD	Tongue cancer	rs76763697	-3.275027	6.5443304	0.6167672
TZD	Tongue cancer	rs2920503	-4.143453	5.1330756	0.4195474
TZD	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	-3.822637	0.4403798	3.95E-18
TZD	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.822637	0.814704	2.70E-06
TZD	Tongue cancer	All - MR Egger	-4.638719	1.2985308	0.0072695

Amylin analog	Tongue cancer	rs4663804	3.4571863	8.2631863	0.6756663
Amylin analog	Tongue cancer	rs11869741	4.6103621	5.4191643	0.3949074
Amylin analog	Tongue cancer	rs12603201	-0.579725	3.2349798	0.8577767
Amylin analog	Tongue cancer	rs11654396	-5.259441	6.7413603	0.4352878
Amylin analog	Tongue cancer	rs12941945	0.8633668	4.7132314	0.8546573
Amylin analog	Tongue cancer	rs1078523	7.4065625	4.9502375	0.1346006
Amylin analog	Tongue cancer	rs9905939	7.9335065	5.1709221	0.1249672
Amylin analog	Tongue cancer	rs59795094	9.2069231	6.1252769	0.1328124
Amylin analog	Tongue cancer	rs9892728	8.8107237	5.2160263	0.091188
Amylin analog	Tongue cancer	rs73111954	4.5554043	3.9985362	0.2545914
Amylin analog	Tongue cancer	rs11772021	0.5772381	2.2543685	0.7979098
Amylin analog	Tongue cancer	rs4724382	-0.040387	7.2447387	0.9955521
Amylin analog	Tongue cancer	rs75390434	-4.919179	8.4800598	0.5618554
Amylin analog	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.4379713	1.0867692	0.0248762
Amylin analog	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.4379713	1.2449922	0.050204
Amylin analog	Tongue cancer	All - MR Egger	0.1002051	2.7999384	0.9720923
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	rs4561482	-2.647957	6.8721709	0.7000033
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	rs8057326	-4.4682	7.5235048	0.5525798
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	rs34497199	-6.431938	6.1652791	0.2968317
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	rs142133957	6.453752	5.0049918	0.1972372
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	rs11150624	-4.287902	6.5894262	0.5152243
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	rs11865835	-9.996696	7.6190087	0.1894955
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	rs8057029	-7.938198	7.1905086	0.2696006
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	rs12448775	6.2164423	6.5110897	0.3397057
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	rs8054784	-8.700901	7.3048288	0.2336079
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.355148	2.1700492	0.2777902
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.355148	2.1979514	0.283936
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	All - MR Egger	10.285135	5.3381858	0.0953832
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	rs4561482	-2.647957	6.8721709	0.7000033
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	rs8057326	-4.4682	7.5235048	0.5525798
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	rs34497199	-6.431938	6.1652791	0.2968317

SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	rs142133957	6.453752	5.0049918	0.1972372
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	rs11150624	-4.287902	6.5894262	0.5152243
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	rs11865835	-9.996696	7.6190087	0.1894955
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	rs8057029	-7.938198	7.1905086	0.2696006
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	rs12448775	6.2164423	6.5110897	0.3397057
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	rs8054784	-8.700901	7.3048288	0.2336079
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.355148	2.1700492	0.2777902
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.355148	2.1979514	0.283936
SGLT2i	Tongue cancer	All - MR Egger	10.285135	5.3381858	0.0953832
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs77023203	1.1951145	3.2358645	0.7118789
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs2074312	-2.344097	3.9147297	0.5493136
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs116842927	10.399216	11.349891	0.3595414
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs7110898	-3.869251	16.858936	0.8184745
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs4937311	34.271349	11.959206	0.004161
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs5219	-1.05016	1.8684388	0.5740804
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs4148631	9.9141259	10.746503	0.3562447
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs10766393	-0.673717	3.8346982	0.8605378
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs5210	0.320665	3.3770443	0.9243511
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs10766395	0.3334461	3.4341855	0.9226501
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs189603359	0.8030564	11.336498	0.9435266
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs10766392	-0.650195	3.8030208	0.8642488
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs7110037	-0.876726	4.3565526	0.8405085
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs77902362	6.4459091	9.1220455	0.4797966
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs35271178	0.0480467	2.099907	0.9817457
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs147673442	-7.300648	7.4917876	0.3298149
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs2355016	-1.510067	4.5928056	0.7423147
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs2285676	0.3279122	3.3444878	0.9218961
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs739688	7.8220958	8.282994	0.3449877
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs79506407	11.375474	12.7582	0.3725963
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs7112030	0.2477677	3.4059801	0.9420091
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs117973841	-9.940927	10.267649	0.3329547

SU	Vulvar cancer	rs12816749	5.5413314	9.2049112	0.547176
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs74732083	-5.7413	8.1189013	0.4794718
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs10841887	-9.251529	4.6004118	0.0443231
SU	Vulvar cancer	rs59406438	-2.174292	7.273277	0.7649839
SU	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.341592	0.7419078	0.6452123
SU	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.341592	0.8312638	0.6811235
SU	Vulvar cancer	All - MR Egger	-4.31361	2.1889595	0.0604074
AGI	Vulvar cancer	rs72681706	19.280023	10.067377	0.0554799
AGI	Vulvar cancer	rs72692396	4.4591617	9.0961277	0.6239737
AGI	Vulvar cancer	rs174587	-14.15877	9.0320112	0.1169696
AGI	Vulvar cancer	rs112968754	1.6662154	10.162358	0.869763
AGI	Vulvar cancer	rs8037100	8.2322564	12.788513	0.5197552
AGI	Vulvar cancer	rs1659215	8.8787027	13.471784	0.5098578
AGI	Vulvar cancer	rs73402785	-0.226724	10.356709	0.9825345
AGI	Vulvar cancer	rs34359922	2.7075254	9.9777966	0.786118
AGI	Vulvar cancer	rs111917515	4.1914391	9.2601107	0.6508125
AGI	Vulvar cancer	rs113126535	4.22936	10.00044	0.6723555
AGI	Vulvar cancer	rs112898001	2.1171633	10.010677	0.8325045
AGI	Vulvar cancer	rs4924660	16.907586	11.497816	0.1414253
AGI	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.9549765	2.543866	0.1200149
AGI	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.9549765	2.9605752	0.1815881
AGI	Vulvar cancer	All - MR Egger	14.543396	10.921968	0.2125558
DPP-4i	Vulvar cancer	rs4233648	11.100968	11.197903	0.3215179
DPP-4i	Vulvar cancer	rs2080714	-0.338827	9.0737013	0.9702126
DPP-4i	Vulvar cancer	rs75850673	-6.642671	12.884472	0.6061643
DPP-4i	Vulvar cancer	rs188581353	11.352491	10.010726	0.2567808
DPP-4i	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	4.3651181	4.1291454	0.290444
DPP-4i	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	4.3651181	5.2614681	0.406743
DPP-4i	Vulvar cancer	All - MR Egger	10.049475	11.978584	0.4897921
Biguanides	Vulvar cancer	rs150243609	21.601	9.3723429	0.02118
Biguanides	Vulvar cancer	rs17485664	7.1213755	10.136022	0.482317

Biguanides	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	14.927144	7.2176572	0.0386266
Biguanides	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	14.927144	6.8814085	0.0300676
GLP1RA	Vulvar cancer	rs10305525	-14.22266	14.551962	0.3283858
GLP1RA	Vulvar cancer	rs228817	15.264419	10.813178	0.1580532
GLP1RA	Vulvar cancer	rs12215108	-0.075949	10.169326	0.9940411
GLP1RA	Vulvar cancer	rs28360624	6.0876647	10.786707	0.5725042
GLP1RA	Vulvar cancer	rs11963172	10.873167	8.5723889	0.2046573
GLP1RA	Vulvar cancer	rs880347	7.7550239	6.4713876	0.2307786
GLP1RA	Vulvar cancer	rs9462535	17.654387	8.9035484	0.0473844
GLP1RA	Vulvar cancer	rs142878626	1.8519816	11.168618	0.8682985
GLP1RA	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	7.6476065	2.8301664	0.0068887
GLP1RA	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	7.6476065	3.3397034	0.0220268
GLP1RA	Vulvar cancer	All - MR Egger	-4.554586	14.214333	0.7595138
Insulin	Vulvar cancer	rs4031066	-2.787671	9.6123973	0.7718102
TZD	Vulvar cancer	rs4684833	1.8626316	7.0725877	0.7922737
TZD	Vulvar cancer	rs2881654	-0.516257	2.2784893	0.8207514
TZD	Vulvar cancer	rs1373641	6.2645495	6.3813514	0.3262494
TZD	Vulvar cancer	rs2120825	-1.186434	2.4391789	0.6266785
TZD	Vulvar cancer	rs111327339	-7.795453	7.66429	0.3090994
TZD	Vulvar cancer	rs4135247	1.5315496	3.6353887	0.673544
TZD	Vulvar cancer	rs1699348	3.90056	10.87048	0.7197288
TZD	Vulvar cancer	rs310752	14.627769	10.348462	0.1575025
TZD	Vulvar cancer	rs76763697	-12.87893	11.049063	0.243771
TZD	Vulvar cancer	rs2920503	23.085349	8.6866279	0.0078706
TZD	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.4569039	1.6378395	0.7802698
TZD	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.4569039	1.3643915	0.7377175
TZD	Vulvar cancer	All - MR Egger	-3.435578	2.1719149	0.1523474
Amylin analog	Vulvar cancer	rs4663804	20.986667	13.914118	0.1314777
Amylin analog	Vulvar cancer	rs11869741	-3.671281	9.1745682	0.6890398
Amylin analog	Vulvar cancer	rs12603201	0.3105405	5.4557085	0.9546087
Amylin analog	Vulvar cancer	rs11654396	0.6007382	11.369044	0.9578595

Amylin analog	Vulvar cancer	rs12941945	-15.46122	7.931048	0.0512411
Amylin analog	Vulvar cancer	rs1078523	2.7804438	8.356375	0.7393357
Amylin analog	Vulvar cancer	rs9905939	9.9334416	8.7333117	0.2553628
Amylin analog	Vulvar cancer	rs59795094	4.7709462	10.345615	0.6446864
Amylin analog	Vulvar cancer	rs9892728	2.6986711	8.8073684	0.759292
Amylin analog	Vulvar cancer	rs73111954	3.3924043	6.7273191	0.6140697
Amylin analog	Vulvar cancer	rs11772021	4.3334576	3.7622774	0.249396
Amylin analog	Vulvar cancer	rs4724382	0.7903802	12.228018	0.9484632
Amylin analog	Vulvar cancer	rs75390434	11.550855	14.273846	0.4183816
Amylin analog	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.3066728	1.8103347	0.2026034
Amylin analog	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.3066728	2.0929698	0.270416
Amylin analog	Vulvar cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.626944	4.6922734	0.8961225
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	rs4561482	4.0142051	11.603932	0.7293916
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	rs8057326	-3.15981	12.698762	0.8034937
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	rs34497199	1.6795504	10.415194	0.8718889
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	rs142133957	1.3903312	8.539478	0.8706663
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	rs11150624	-3.615057	11.102705	0.7447259
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	rs11865835	-5.589139	12.860783	0.6638617
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	rs8057029	-8.11344	12.127845	0.5035001
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	rs12448775	-4.365577	10.784038	0.685611
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	rs8054784	-3.187306	12.31973	0.7958547
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.8163	1.2897356	0.1590503
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.8163	3.708691	0.6243169
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	All - MR Egger	0.5081286	9.0377777	0.9567355
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	rs4561482	4.0142051	11.603932	0.7293916
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	rs8057326	-3.15981	12.698762	0.8034937
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	rs34497199	1.6795504	10.415194	0.8718889
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	rs142133957	1.3903312	8.539478	0.8706663
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	rs11150624	-3.615057	11.102705	0.7447259
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	rs11865835	-5.589139	12.860783	0.6638617
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	rs8057029	-8.11344	12.127845	0.5035001

SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	rs12448775	-4.365577	10.784038	0.685611
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	rs8054784	-3.187306	12.31973	0.7958547
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.8163	1.2897356	0.1590503
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.8163	3.708691	0.6243169
SGLT2i	Vulvar cancer	All - MR Egger	0.5081286	9.0377777	0.9567355